

The God Effect:

Exploring the Long-Term Influences of Elicited Mystical Experiences

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Abstract

This dissertation project provides a window into the lives of people who underwent a Mystical experience while attending one of the author's workshops. The experiences are particularly notable in that they were not random events. They were induced, taking place while participants were practicing techniques learned at the workshops. These techniques have been found to facilitate and elicit encounters with the Divine.

The research data reports the effect these experiencers had in the moment, but also reveals how their lives were impacted over time. The data and case studies demonstrate that while, at a minimum, an encounter with God is usually a strongly positive experience, in some cases it is powerfully life-transformative. In religious ministry, it is hard to imagine there is anything more valuable than facilitating an individual's direct experience with the love of God. The reader will find information that will aid ministerial efforts in this regard, including work in the fields of conversion, spiritual formation, and the cultivation of the gifts of the Holy Spirit.

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At present, we are witnessing a historic shift in the way many people view religion. With each passing year, more and more people identify as “spiritual but not religious” (SBNR). Particularly among the young, we are more likely to see many of them at a yoga or meditation class than at a Sunday morning worship service.

While traditional religion is declining, a surprising number of Americans are longing for Mystical experiences. A 2005 *Newsweek/Beliefnet* poll reported that 75% of respondents believed religion was very important “to forge a personal relationship with God”, while only 39% believed religion was very important “to be part of a community” (*Beliefnet.com*, 2005). In order to meet current needs, we in ministry need to familiarize ourselves with the factors involved in facilitating Mystical communion with God.

The author has discovered several techniques that have been found to successfully elicit Mystical experiences. The techniques are introduced and described in detail in Chapter 4. Testimonies reported by experiencers can be found in Chapter 5 and Appendix D. In Chapter 2, a review of the literature related to the phenomenon of Mystical experiences and their elicitation are provided. Chapter 3 explores the theological basis for this ministry and research project, while Chapter 4 describes the research model that guided it. Chapter 5 consists of an analysis of the data and a review of knowledge gained.

In sum, this dissertation project has made an earnest case for the need for ministers to provide a gateway for individuals in their congregations to achieve direct apprehension of the Divine, and that relatively simple techniques exist that have been shown to elicit this phenomenon. Readers are enthusiastically invited to adopt these techniques toward the goal of replicating these wonderful results. When reviewing the data, it is abundantly clear that Mystical experiences result

in long-term benefits to the experiencers and society at large, as well as comfort and fulfillment to the heart of God.

Chapter 1

Purpose of the Study

Statement of the Problem

Although many workshop participants have reported that the techniques employed produced Mystical experiences for them, some might object that these reports are merely anecdotal. This study was designed to produce a more systematic gathering and reporting of data surrounding them. This would not only more strongly demonstrate the efficacy of the techniques, but also gather data about the effects these experiences had on participants both in the moment and over the long term. This would enable a clearer understanding of the phenomena, and possibly provide an opportunity for improvement in their implementation.

Leadership Opportunity

When Charles Finney was a little boy at the turn of the 19th century, his family's remote location in the wilderness of upstate New York offered no opportunity for formal religious instruction. His parents professed no religion, he didn't possess a Bible, and his only exposure to anything remotely religious took place when itinerant preachers would visit his neighborhood. He was impressed by the level of ignorance some of them demonstrated, and recounts that people would sometimes return from a religious gathering laughing at "the absurdities which had been advanced" (Finney, 1876).

Nevertheless, at the age of 29, he had been wrestling with the issues of sin and the salvation of his soul for some time when he firmly decided to take his concerns directly to God. He walked deep into the woods near the small town of Adams and after some difficulty managed to open his heart to God in prayer. In his autobiography, he recounts how a scripture popped into his mind at a crucial moment: "Then shall ye go and pray unto me, and I will hearken unto you. Then shall ye seek me and find me, when ye shall search for me with all your heart" (KJV, Jer. 29:12-13). He

intuitively felt that it was the voice of God himself speaking to him. Because he had surrendered his heart, a doorway opened to a powerful direct encounter with the Divine.

Finney gives this vivid description of the culminating point in his Mystical experience:

... As I turned and was about to take a seat by the fire, I received a mighty baptism of the Holy Ghost. Without any expectation of it, without ever having the thought in my mind that there was any such thing for me, without any recollection that I had ever heard the thing mentioned by any person in the world, the Holy Spirit descended upon me in a manner that seemed to go through me body and soul.

... I could feel the impression, like a wave of electricity, going through and through me. Indeed it seemed to come in waves and waves of liquid love, for I could not express it in any other way... No words can express the wonderful love that was shared abroad in my heart. I wept aloud with joy and love... (p. 14).

The very next day, Finney abandoned his budding law career and went into the ministry. He helped spark revivals in upstate New York, as one of the leaders in what came to be called the Second Great Awakening. It is estimated that his ministry resulted in the conversion of hundreds of thousands of souls.

As ministers, wouldn't it be wonderful if we possessed tools that we could impart to our congregants that would elicit experiences similar to the one Finney had? These tools exist, and over the last several years have been shared in workshops with startling results. Three of these techniques are: guided meditation, hands-on healing, and what the author calls "Journaling with God."

Here is an example of one of these workshop Mystical experiences. (Note: This was translated from a video recording of a workshop held in Europe. The woman is Japanese but was speaking in Italian. Therefore, the language may appear a little unusual.)

I started the meditation by following him (indicates Ron Pappalardo). It came right away just like a light, slow at first and then stronger and stronger, bit by bit it came closer to me, like a wave vibrating, small vibrations at first, then wider, going into the sun, and as I was searching for my light (indicates forehead), I found a strong reference point with white light, and as I was trying to bring it

toward my heart, a word came. “Thank you, thank you.” I did not understand why at first, but then He (God) said, “Thank you, I was searching for you for so long.” (She became emotional here and paused for a moment.)

He thanked me and said, “I have been searching for you very much.” My heart was saying “Thank you.” I felt how important this moment was to me and how grateful I was. He said, “Finally we met.” In my heart I felt that I didn’t want to leave this powerful moment, this encounter with someone with a strong, strong embrace, who did not want to leave me. My hands were vibrating, and I was feeling this deep love, this strong warmth, like a mother’s strong embrace. And it said, “I will never leave you.”

This was a strong message. Deep peace, calm, and tranquility came over me. I had been waiting, searching for such an encounter with God, and I expressed my gratitude to him, saying “Thank you.” I didn’t want to leave that moment, but he (Ron) said he was going to end it, little by little, but I did not want to. I could not leave this moment of an encounter so important, something that my heart had been desiring and searching for from the beginning. (Again, she paused with emotion).

Now I understand that God is always with us. He was living within me in silence, I who hadn't understood that God gave me the gift of feeling His love all the time. It was a very short, short time of meditation, but I am tremendously grateful for this opportunity, for this moment I was able to have due to Ron’s workshop meditation today. We have this capacity that God gave us. I will not forget this moment. Thank you.

Afterwards, this woman mentioned that she had been a member of her church for over forty years and had never had an experience like this. She was deeply moved to discover that God knew her personally. “He knew my name,” she said.

Charles Finney lamented the fact that most religious activity is strong on dogma, but weak on actual experience: “When I first became religious ... in all the preaching I had heard, there had been so little said of the testimony of personal experience” (Finney, 1858).

Finney believed that the Gospel should be taught as an experience, and that experiential religion results in the awakening of a higher consciousness. As Sean Welch (2022) says, “Inducing this conversion experience – what many modern evangelicals refer to as being ‘born again’ to a saving faith in Christ – was the chief aim of revival practitioners” (p.286). We can see here that

the idea of attempting to elicit Mystical experiences is not a new one. What is new is the discovery of specific techniques that have been shown in many cases to trigger them.

A leadership opportunity exists within the author's ministry, and for ministry in general, to guide people into direct Mystical encounters with God by employing these techniques. Through this research project, one goal was to gain a deeper sense of just what was going on with these techniques, what the long-term effects of them could be, and what, if anything, could be done to more effectively facilitate and elicit Mystical experiences.

More broadly, it would be well for those of us in ministry to pay close attention to these spiritual phenomena. It is hoped that others will work with these techniques with the goal of duplicating these extraordinary results. The techniques can be used not only in a workshop setting, but also in Sunday schools, worship services, and in the classroom. Perhaps they will be incorporated into courses related to the field of spiritual formation.

One possible application would be to create a course curriculum centered around the techniques. Age-appropriate versions could be tailored for use in elementary schools, middle schools, high schools and higher education. It could also be used in churches for Sunday school classes and adult education programs. As has been demonstrated through this ministry, they also work well in one or two-day workshop settings.

Description of the Ministry Context

We have seen in Chapter one how a person with no religious upbringing was completely transformed by a single powerful encounter with the Divine. Charles Finney's 1821 Mystical experience compelled him to give up his law career and immediately enter the ministry. He became one of the key leaders of America's Second Great Awakening and contributed to the conversion of hundreds of thousands of souls. Finney is not the only historical figure who wound up changing history because he had an encounter with God.

Judaism began when Abraham heard God speak to him, telling him to move his family more than four hundred miles south to a land where “all peoples on earth will be blessed through you” (Gen 12:3). Christianity began when Jesus started his ministry after hearing the voice of God tell him “You are my Son, whom I love; with you I am well pleased” (Mark 1:11).

St. Mother Teresa is a more recent example of a person whose ministry not only improved the world during her lifetime but whose influence continues to be a force for good around the world today. The following quote reveals that she knew God personally and intimately and therefore should also be considered one of the world's great Mystics: “I can understand the greatness of God but I cannot understand his humility. It becomes so clear in him being in love with each one of us separately and completely. It is as if there is no one but me in the world. He loves me so much.” (St. Mother Teresa, 2006. p.12).

Countless others have also begun ministry in its various forms as a result of a Mystical experience. It's appropriate that this phenomenon is often referred to as a calling to ministry. We may never know their names, but their Mystical experiences are no less significant than the ones listed above.

This ministry began in approximately 2009 around the time of the publication of the author's first book, *Reconciled by the Light: the After-Death Letters from a Teen Suicide*. The ministry gained momentum after receiving an endorsement from Robin Graham, then president of the Unification Theological Seminary (UTS) Alumni Association, the organization that subsequently co-sponsored a nationwide tour of two-day workshops beginning around 2014.

The ministry most often involved two-day long workshops. Unificationists in particular are quite comfortable with this format; most of the early American members joined the movement as a result of first having attended a two-day workshop that often took place over a weekend.

The workshops closely resembled a classroom setting. They were most often held in church meeting rooms or sanctuaries. Other venues included rented hotel or office spaces, and sometimes interested parties would offer the use of their private residences. Several have been held in the author's home.

The main focus of these workshops was to guide participants in the practice of three techniques that have been found to facilitate or trigger Mystical experiences. These techniques are hands-on healing, guided meditation, and a writing technique the author refers to as "Journaling with God." They are also central to this dissertation project.

The ministry has enjoyed the support of two former presidents of UTS, who wrote the following endorsements:

The Divine Principle has a revolutionary doctrine of God's Heart of love. And yet, we have not been able to run a good Church due to our inability to understand God's Heart truly. We have caused so many problems. Ron's approach, I believe, is to bring back God's Heart to our lives and our Church, and also to the rest of the world eventually. Therefore, I really want to endorse it" (Theodore Shimmyo, PhD, January 26, 2014).

I attended Ron Pappalardo's workshop and learned a lot about the spirit world and grew my heart and refreshed my relationship with my family, self, and God" (Tyler Hendricks, PhD, February 23, 2013).

When the author joined the Unification Movement in 1975, it was in its infancy, especially in the United States. There were no traditional church buildings, Sunday services, or congregations such as exist with most established churches. We were a small new religious movement, almost exclusively composed of young people in our 20s, unmarried, and living in communal church centers. We were unpaid volunteers and spent most of our time either fundraising or witnessing to gain new members.

Some government agencies classified our church centers as “monasteries.” Like many Roman Catholic monks and nuns, we adhered to the practices of poverty, chastity and obedience. Our lives were extremely religious. We rose early every day to attend morning services where we prayed and studied our religious teachings. We routinely performed spiritual conditions, such as praying for a set amount of time. For example, we might pray for 21 minutes every day for 40 days, focusing on some particular religious goal. We fasted. For example, before we were considered qualified for marriage, we were required to fast for seven days. Some members have fasted for as long as 40 days.

Traditionally, Unificationists have performed special conditions with the goal of eliciting a direct encounter with God. Prayer conditions are a regular part of this tradition. For example, it is not unusual for a Unificationist to perform an all-night prayer vigil in order to access God.

Unificationist theology emphasizes each person's responsibility to accomplish something called “the three great blessings” (Moon, 1996, p.96), based on the biblical theme “to be fruitful, multiply and have dominion over the earth” (Gen. 1:28). Because most of us were single, there was a lot of emphasis on personal spiritual growth, what Unificationists referred to as working to fulfill the First Blessing.

In 1982, there was a paradigm shift in the movement’s consciousness, after a large portion of the membership participated in a mass wedding of 2075 couples at Madison Square Garden in New York. This event epitomized the transition from a movement composed of young and single people to couples who began establishing families over the next few years. Living in monastic centers began to be less and less of a phenomenon as many couples began establishing their own family households.

Now that most members have established families, Unificationists usually think of marriage when they hear the term “Blessing,” not individual spiritual growth or completion. Many Unificationist parents are far more concerned – some might say obsessed – with getting their children “Blessed” in marriage than about their children's individual spiritual growth. Many of them have forgotten that Rev. Moon taught that marriage is the Second Blessing, and that they still have a responsibility to fulfill the First Blessing, which is individual maturity or completion in their relationship with God. When Rev. Moon was preparing us for marriage, it was understood that he was asking us to promise him that we would take personal responsibility to complete the First Blessing. He referred to it as entering into the “direct dominion” of God (Moon, p.44).

That has been and continues to be the focus of this ministry. The focus is not couples or families, it is the individual. Theologically, it is inspired by Paul's teaching, “Don’t you know that you yourselves are God’s temple and that God’s Spirit dwells in your midst?” (1 Cor. 3:16). Rev. Moon also emphasized the need for individual spiritual maturity or perfection. His *Exposition of the Divine Principle* states:

The world which has realized the ideal of God will be in the image of a perfected individual. Every person in that world is united with God vertically, and this forms the basis upon which they can naturally live in harmony with each other horizontally... Due to the fall the vertical bond of love between God and people was broken...

Moon teaches that we are now living in the time when this bond of love can be reestablished: In the last days, therefore, many faithful believers will acquire the ability to communicate with God... (Moon, 1996, p. 97-98).

Ministry Team and Responsibilities

For a large number of the workshops, the ministry team was led by a partnership between the author and the then president of the Unification Theological Seminary Alumni Association, Robin Graham. By working with a worldwide network of seminary alumni, Mr. Graham was

successful in providing the groundwork for workshops in major cities across the United States, Europe, and Canada. Alumni living in selected cities helped secure locations and spread the word about the workshops.

Mr. Graham accompanied the author on most of the early workshops, coordinating activities and serving as a master of ceremonies. The team agreed that it was best to serve snacks, beverages, and luncheon on-site to help build camaraderie among the participants. The author's wife and other volunteers helped augment these efforts.

Goals and Objectives

This ministry's goal was to guide people, one by one, to reestablish that vertical bond of love by experiencing a Mystical encounter with God. On that foundation, they could establish a continuous relationship that could develop into Mystical oneness with God. It is a union in which God can fully dwell within each one of us and express himself through us. In this author's view, this is how the Kingdom of God emerges on earth.

Methodology

The project consisted largely of gathering surveys and participant testimonies about the Mystical experiences they had while practicing these techniques, both during the workshops and afterward.

Spiritual Autobiography

Roman Catholic Beginnings

In the pre-dawn darkness, I trudged my adolescent body up the street to assist Father Hunt. It was to be a 7 am weekday morning Mass, so I knew attendance would be sparse. I arrived at the church before the priest, and as I entered the sacristy, I was struck by the calm stillness inside. There was no sound except for the "tic-tic-tic" of the wall clock. I stopped for a moment and took

in the sacred atmosphere. I'm convinced now there was a Presence in that peacefulness, but I was not able to recognize it at the time. Like a powerful magnet, the heart of God was pulling me, and eventually my heart would meet with his.

My first 16 years revolved completely around the Roman Catholic church. I was baptized as an infant in 1955. My parents were both born into Catholicism; my father was an immigrant from Sicily, while both of my mother's parents were from Ireland. I loved being Catholic. It gave me a strong sense of identity and purpose.

Richard B. Patterson, in his book *Writing Your Spiritual Autobiography*, says that if we are "fortunate enough," we may meet someone who facilitates an experience of "unconditional love" (Patterson, 2002). I certainly felt unconditional love through my close relationship with my Irish grandmother. A second person was my first-grade teacher at Epiphany Catholic school in South El Monte, California, Sister Mary Ambrosine. To me, she was like Mother Mary in the flesh. I remember that when I hugged her around her knees I would be enveloped in the thick warm folds of her nun's habit, feeling safe and loved. I suspect that my early Catholic experiences might have engendered within me my longing to know – and experience – God on a deeper and more intimate level. I was motivated to become an altar boy, sang in the choir, and seriously considered becoming a priest or brother.

By the time I was 14, my soul had become restless, longing for something more fulfilling than what the traditional Catholicism of my local parish was providing. I was also struggling theologically. I was taught that the Roman Catholic Church was the only one true church, and that anyone who was not baptized in that church was destined for eternal damnation in hell. This didn't seem to make sense to me. I had a close friend who was baptized in the Methodist Church; it

seemed absurd that he was destined for damnation because his church didn't have the word "Catholic" in it.

I told my mother about my restlessness, and she suggested that I visit the parish my grandparents attended in the next town. She said there was a priest there who was "good with young people." I went to see him, and he simply told me, "Just keep going to Mass (Sunday service) and receive the sacraments, and everything is going to be OK." I was disappointed with the meeting, but I obediently followed his directions. Nothing changed. Finally, at the age of 16, I had an experience that caused me to give up on Catholicism.

It was a Sunday in Lent, and our church had the opportunity to hear a sermon from a visiting missionary priest. I always gravitated to the missionary priests; they had been in the field, seen tremendous suffering, and seemed to possess deep and compassionate hearts.

I approached the priest after mass and asked him what I thought was a fairly simple question, "Father, isn't there more to being a Catholic than just going to Mass on Sunday and receiving the sacraments?"

The priest took his pipe out of his mouth and said with his Irish accent, "Now look, we've been in this business of saving souls for 2000 years, and by God, we know what we're doing!" Without another word, he turned and walked away from me.

A Search for Meaning

Disappointed, I sadly concluded that if I were to find a deeper understanding of life and my relationship with God, I would have to search beyond the confines of Roman Catholicism.

One of the thought systems I discovered in my high school library was *rationalism*. Rene Descartes famously said, "Cogito Ergo Sum (I think, therefore I am)." These words had a powerful effect on my thinking. I decided that from that day on I would only accept ideas that I knew to be true. I knew I existed because I was thinking. Some person must be doing the thinking; that person

is me. That's the only thing I was convinced was true. I would start from scratch and try to find the rest of the truth by adding to that, idea by idea.

I was later attracted to the teachings of Maharishi Mahesh Yogi. He taught a system of thought called the *Science of Creative Intelligence* (Forem, 2012). I practiced his *Transcendental Meditation* technique for about six months, and it did what it was advertised to do. It reduced my level of stress and made me feel calmer. Ironically, it made me more aware of the empty space in my heart. Even though I considered myself agnostic at the time, my soul was longing for a relationship with a personal God. It was difficult, however, for me to imagine getting hugged by something called Creative Intelligence.

The years from age 16 to 20 were the most difficult and frightening of my life. I lived in what psychiatrist Victor Frankl would call an "existential vacuum" (Frankl, 1946). Frankl taught that what really motivated human beings was not the quest for pleasure or power; it was the search for meaning. Because I had discarded my Roman Catholic belief system, I no longer had a guidance system that provided me with purpose and direction for my life or gave me a moral compass for decision making. I had become a disciple of rationalism. I was caught up in my head and disconnected from my heart. Yes, I was searching for truth, but I didn't learn until later that the heart is a much more powerful tool for cognition than the head. I would try to make sense of life and the universe with my reason. I remember trying to do this over and over again until my head hurt, and I felt that my brain had been twisted into a pretzel. It was not until I discovered the power of the heart as a doorway into spiritual knowledge that I would be relieved from this mental suffering.

When I was 20 years old, I had a very powerful dream – a vision really – that moved me to make the decision to break up with a girlfriend I had been seriously dating for more than a year.

I did not understand rationally why I should do this, but I think that on a subconscious level I believed that this relationship was blocking me from connecting with God. I felt sorry that she might be emotionally hurt by my action; ironically, she seemed to do just fine, and to my surprise I was the one who suffered most from the breakup. I realized that my relationship with her was a kind of addiction. I believe that because my heart was finding refuge in my relationship with her that there was no room for God to get in. I believe that is the reason why I was guided to end the relationship.

Not long after, I experienced what I refer to as my “dark night of the soul,” a phrase made famous by a poem of Saint John of the Cross. It was May 19, 1975, I was still living with my parents, and it was about eleven o’clock at night. Everyone had gone to bed, but I couldn’t sleep. My mind was tormented with questions and fears – “I’m already 20 years old, and I have no idea who I am, or what purpose and direction to take in my life.”

Desperate for consolation, I started thinking about my ex-girlfriend. She used to be able to calm me down when I was anxious. I started reaching for the telephone to call her, but I stopped myself, still convinced that it was somehow wrong for me to be relying on her. After a while, I gave in to the temptation and dialed her number. Her roommate answered and told me that my ex-girlfriend had gone away for the weekend with some other boy. I was crushed!

There is a familiar saying in ministry – “Man’s extremity is God’s opportunity.” I was in a box with no way out. I grabbed a spiral notebook and wrote a letter to my ex-girlfriend. I never intended to show it to her; I just needed to vent. Then I did the strangest thing. I turned the page and started another letter. “Dear God,” I wrote. “I’ve been trying to find you for six long years, why do you make it so damn hard. Throw me a towel; show me the locker room. Pinch me so I can wake up from this nightmare.” I continued pouring out my heart onto the page. Considering

the fact that I was an agnostic at the time, it did not appear to me as rational to be writing a letter to God. That is the wonderful thing about the human heart; it is more powerful than the rational mind, and when it is able to override the mind, wonderful things can happen. Three days later, after a series of “coincidences,” I was born again.

Making a Covenant with God

A young man my age approached me on a street in downtown Long Beach, California, and asked, “Excuse me, do you believe in God?” Intrigued, I followed him to a missionary center of the Unification Church to hear a lecture presentation called “The Principle of Creation.” I was so impressed by it that I was invited to stay for lunch so that I could listen to another lecture afterwards. I wound up staying for about six hours, during which they taught me the entirety of their new religious teaching called the Divine Principle.

I was stunned. The teaching seemed to answer all the questions I had wanted answers to as a Catholic. It filled in the gaps, imbuing me with wonder and a sense of exhilaration. It concluded by proclaiming that we were living in the time of the Second Coming of Christ, and implied that Christ had presently returned to the earth living somewhere as a human being. I asked the lecturer, “Are you telling me that Christ is on the earth right now?”

He calmly and quietly nodded his head.

“Do you know where he is?” I asked.

He nodded his head again with a mischievous little knowing smile.

“What do you want me to do?” I said in sacred surrender.

“Study the teachings more,” he said.

“How do I do that?”

“There is a van leaving in a couple of hours to take people to a three-day workshop in the mountains near San Bernardino.”

“I’ll be on that van,” I said.

At the workshop site, I was given a more in-depth view of the Divine Principle. After spending several days there, I realized that these people were convinced the Second Coming of

Christ had indeed taken place, and that their founder, the Rev. Sun Myung Moon, was the new Messiah. I immediately began to struggle with that idea, because he did not fit into my concept of what a Messiah would be like.

That night I brought the matter to God in prayer:

“Heavenly Father, I used to be a Roman Catholic. I thought that Catholicism was the absolute truth, and then I found out it wasn’t the complete truth. Then I practiced Transcendental Meditation. I thought that it was the ultimate truth, and then I found out it wasn’t all the truth. I thought that my girlfriend loved me; I thought that was the truth, and then I found out that wasn’t the truth either. So, I no longer trust my own judgment. This Divine Principle really sounds like the truth, but how can I know if it’s the truth or not?”

Just then a Bible verse popped into my mind “You shall know them by their fruits” (Matt 7:20). I felt sure of what God was telling me, so I made a covenant with God. “It’s clear to me that the fruit of Rev. Moon’s work is nothing but goodness. Therefore, I promise you I will follow him. But if I ever see that the fruit is not good, I will not follow him anymore.”

Then I had a vision. On top of the highest mountain, a cloud began to flash with lightning. I took this as recognition from God that he had heard my prayer and had agreed to this sacred covenant between us.

A Tidal Wave of Love

I spent close to 20 years in the Unification movement, and I learned that it was possible for anyone to have direct experiences with God. I had several Mystical experiences during that time, and a couple of them illustrate the overcoming of obstacles to Divine communion.

In early 1976, I was working full time as a volunteer on a church fundraising team, raising money for a bicentennial “God Bless America Festival” we were planning to hold in Yankee

Stadium that June. One day, it rained and rained. By the time the sun went down, I was in bad shape. I had gotten wet because the rain had penetrated my jacket. I was cold and my muscles were starting to ache from that feeling they get after being cold and wet for hours. My only rain gear was a black plastic trash bag that I used primarily to keep my box of candy dry.

For the last run of the day, the team captain dropped me off on a highway dotted with old motels and gas stations. As I walked across the lawn in front of one motel, my feet made that “sploosh, sploosh,” sound you hear when you think you are stepping on grass, but you are really walking into a couple of inches of hidden water. Now my feet were completely soaked. My body began to tremble and shake as it flirted with the first stages of hypothermia.

In this miserable tired state, I determined to keep going beyond the discomfort of my physical condition. At that moment, I decided to pray. “Heavenly Father,” I said, “Don’t worry about me. I’m going to be just fine. I’m going to keep going until I sell all this candy, so we can have a great “God Bless America Festival” in June!” On the outside, I looked like the most miserable person, but on the inside, I was upbeat and determined.

Then, something really strange happened. Off in the distance to my left, from the other side of the highway, I felt like something was approaching. It was like the feeling you might have when you hear a very faint distant roll of thunder. It is miles away, you cannot see anything, and yet you know a storm is coming.

As this feeling came closer, I sensed an energy building and coming right toward me. Now it felt like a giant tsunami was rising, coming closer and closer. Yet, I felt no fear, only a sense of curiosity wondering, “What is this thing?” The unseen wave now rose above me and broke the way you see a wave crashing onto a beach. It poured itself all over me.

The “water” that broke over me was pure Divine Love, something I had never felt in my life before. It was a love that I had never known—unconditional, all embracing, and powerful. The feeling was so strong that I felt like it was too much. I immediately burst into tears, but they were good tears, tears of reunion. I felt the power of God surrounding me, embracing me in a perfect love.

“Turn it down, Heavenly Father, turn it down,” I prayed. I felt that the love was too much and my heart might burst. After about thirty seconds, the wave subsided. I wiped my tears and continued my candy-selling mission, not sure of how to explain what had just happened. At the appointed meeting place the team captain showed up in the passenger van that was our “home away from home,” but I was surprised to find it empty except for him. The van should have been filled with the five or six other members of the team.

As I climbed into the passenger seat next to him, he turned to me and said, “Ron, I just want you to know that because everyone was having such a rough time, I decided to pick everybody up and take them out to a movie. When I got to your area, I couldn’t find you, so we just went without you.” In another circumstance, I might have felt sad at being left out, but that thought did not even cross my mind. Instead, I actually felt sorry for my teammates. “Those poor guys,” I thought, “they had to spend time in a theater watching some stupid movie while I was out having this amazing experience.”

Something else went deep into my soul that was much more profound and had a permanent impact on my life. It slowly dawned on me that at the time the wave broke over me, I was the only person on the team, and maybe the only person in the Memphis area, that was voluntarily out in the miserable weather thinking about and working to help God by raising money for the “God Bless America Festival”. That realization penetrated my heart and I could not deny the truth of it.

I felt that God was saying to me, “You’ve always defined yourself as some miserable sinner, undeserving of my love. Well, how about now? Can you continue to deny that you are indeed lovable and deserving of my love? In your miserable state, you didn’t complain, but instead tried to comfort me. You moved my heart! How could you not be deserving of my love?”

He had me. I had to surrender. His argument was too compelling and the experience was too real. The inescapable truth was that God did not view me as a miserable sinner, but as his child, who was deserving of his love.

Falling in Love with God

A second experience went even deeper. In 1980, I was working as a missionary in Rhode Island. That summer while fundraising, I noticed my energy level was dragging, and I was finding it harder and harder to motivate myself to work. My intuition told me that while the weather was hot and my body was tired, the real issue was that there was a problem with my relationship with God. For some reason I was still holding back, not fully committed to him.

I asked for and received permission to do a spiritual retreat, so I traveled to the small town of Accord, New York. When I arrived, I was greeted by a young woman named Annie Redmond who had been assigned to take care of me. I immediately felt a connection with her. I could sense the saintly heart she possessed and just knew that I could trust her.

“Here’s what I suggest you do, Ron,” she said. “Go for a walk in the woods. Go as deep into the woods as you need to be sure that you have privacy. Then, just open your heart and talk to God. Lay all your cards on the table. I want you to tell him exactly how you feel, and tell him everything you feel, even the bad stuff. In fact, especially the bad stuff.”

Annie seemed so confident and spoke with such care and compassion that I was sure she herself must have had a close relationship with God. Because of that, I was able to set my fear of

God aside. It seemed that Annie had a special “hotline” to God. I imagined that as soon as I walked off into the woods, she would get on her “spiritual telephone” and tell God something like: “I’m sending this young guy out to talk to you, and he’s really struggling. Please go easy on him, okay?”

So, I went with total trust in my heart. After walking for a while, I found a place where there was an ancient stone wall, and I sat on top of it. Then I started to pray. I searched my heart, trying to find what was bugging me. Then I said something I would never have dared to say if I hadn’t known that Annie had my back. “Heavenly Father,” I said. “The way I see it, you are the one who is responsible for all the suffering of mankind.”

I still was not sure whether or not a lightning bolt was going to come out of the sky and vaporize me for my impertinence. To my relief, nothing bad happened. Instead, I could strongly sense the presence of God there in the woods with me. This time it was more than just the powerful energy and unconditional love I had felt from the “tidal wave” of love in Memphis. I actually received words! From some place deep inside my heart God opened a door. This time the experience was not from the outside in; it was from the inside out. I knew, clear as a bell, what God wanted to say. He said it without a shred of excuse-making or defensiveness, and to my amazement, he said it with absolute humility. “This is true,” he said, “and I accept the responsibility for it.”

I was taken aback by the selflessness of this answer. It wasn’t what I was expecting. I had always imagined God as an imperious, majestic being, and to admit responsibility for a problem just did not fit in with my conception of what his personality would be like. “You are cruel, uncaring, domineering,” I continued. “I am none of these things,” God calmly replied. “Those who suffer bring it upon themselves. It is the only hope for them to change.”

There was no hint of judgment in this statement. He was just stating the fact, and there was a tinge of sadness in his “voice.” “What about those who are innocent, yet suffer?”

When I asked that question, God lost his composure. I was stunned to realize that just as I was being completely and painfully honest with him, he was being completely honest with me. Again, his humility and open-heartedness just floored me.

He burst into tears and seemed to tremble from someplace deep within his heart.

“Oh, I can’t bear the pain! If a parent chooses to beat his child, I cannot stop it. Yet, even then, if that child could follow me, I could save him. I trust you, Ron Pappalardo. You can help my children. I can’t, but you can! Oh, please, I beg you, won’t you do it?” (Strong tears)

By the time he finished this part, I was crying, too. I felt like I was listening to a parent whose heart was aching for his children. I was humbled by the sincerity and honesty of the expression. He was sharing with me as if I was a long time and trusted friend. I felt bad for the other things I needed to say, but I knew it would be a mistake if I did not get everything out.

“Forgive me, my Lord, but this also must be confronted: I have suffered, Father. I tried so hard to find you – to find the truth. From my infancy I tried. I have never been malicious, have I? I tried so hard, and I feel betrayed. Maybe this is blasphemy, but I really feel I need an apology from you. I need to know you won’t take advantage of me. Why didn’t you come to me when I was lonely?”

With great anguish he replied, “You didn’t cry out for me!” When he said this, it rang true in my heart. Even though I had searched for God in books and exerted my reason until my brain hurt, I had never cried out directly to him until that night I wrote him a letter in May of 1975. “I’m sorry, Father. I didn’t know how.” “When you cried out for me, didn’t I answer? Immediately, I

answered. It was me, (In tears) you must believe me! It was me! It was me – no one else – who answered you! In three days, I led you to my son.”

These words penetrated my heart, and I wept and wept. I felt such a genuine closeness and intimacy with this Being. I eventually stopped crying, and things were quiet for a while. I thought I was done. What more could I say to this? Nevertheless, the presence of God was still there with me in the woods. I could feel it palpably. He was still there, waiting for something, but I did not know what to say. He helped me by breaking the silence. “Something’s still bothering you,” he said. “It’s okay. You can tell me.”

Searching my heart, what I found in there surprised and disturbed me. Nevertheless, I just knew it had to be spoken. If I left it unsaid, it would have been like being dishonest, and I would miss this precious opportunity for healing. “It’s weird,” I replied, “but I still feel like saying ‘I hate you.’” He was not surprised at all or offended. His demeanor was one of absolutely gentle kindness and I felt as if he smiled at me with tenderness.

God: *Ron, you don't hate me. You really don't. You just want to know if I love you. In reality, I have felt your love for me.*

Ron: I was really lonely before, Father. It hurt so bad I wanted to die,

God: *If I hadn't allowed you to have that experience, where would you be now?*

I knew exactly what he meant by this. It was only when I had nowhere else to turn that I finally cried out to him, and that cry brought me to him.

Ron: You’ve got a good point, I admitted.

God: *Do you think it was easy for me to watch you suffer? I only hoped it would be for a short time.”*

I realized that God had been waiting and waiting for this meeting even more than I had, wondering how long it would take before I realized that I needed him this way.

Ron: I can see now that it was out of your love for me.

God: *(Embracing me) I really love you, my son. You should know that. Don't worry about anything, just know that I love you.*

Through this experience, I was born again – again. I'm now convinced that we can have more than one conversion experience in our lives, on deeper and deeper levels.

Leaving the Spiritual Plateau

I fell in love with God that day, and I have been crazy in love ever since. I had many wonderful experiences in the Unification movement, including opportunities to do church work in places such as Japan, Korea, Russia, Ukraine, Belarus, Uzbekistan and Honduras. In about 1993, I had a vivid dream in which Rev. Moon appeared to me and said that I had “fulfilled my mission.” At the time, I did not interpret the dream to mean that it was time for me to move on to something else, so I lingered within the Unification movement.

However, my spiritual life plateaued and then declined. I became dry, like a raisin. In a desperate attempt to salvage my spiritual life, I eventually stopped attending Unificationist Sunday services and began attending Pentecostal Christian services. Even though I was uncomfortable with the theology, I felt the Holy Spirit there and it healed and nourished me.

Losing a Son to Suicide, and Learning the Power of Forgiveness

Another important thing I learned in the Unification movement is the power of forgiveness. I now teach a “Forgiveness Meditation” at my workshops. Through this meditation, I was able to overcome my own resentment towards my father. I began this meditation by pretending I was my father's own father, or even his Heavenly Father, and reviewed his life through God's eyes. I paid special attention to his childhood and youth, with the attitude of a parent. This caused my heart to soften and forgive him. I actually wept for his suffering; he went from being my enemy to my hero.

A more difficult challenge was acquiring the ability to forgive myself. I didn't master this until after I lost my 17-year-old first-born son, Joshua, to suicide in 2003. Holding myself responsible, I lived in fear of an angry ghost. I thought that my son might be full of anger and resentment towards me for not having been able to save him from death.

Through the gift of a woman's mediumship, I received a message from Joshua in the afterlife that led to my healing. Here is a key excerpt of that message:

... this is what weighs so heavily in my heart—the family and friends whom I hurt through my stupid choices, my attitude, and my passing. I took my life, and no one should feel so proud before God and their parents as to feel that they have the right to do this. Mom and Dad, please don't try to just skim over these words from my heart because they may bring you pain and regret. I need to express this from my heart because it is what I am working through at this time. It is a road I must travel in the process of healing. I want to walk it with you. Please, please hear me. I love you so much, and I need you to feel this love because I know that in the last years and months I have not expressed it to you. In my rebellion I tried to hurt the world back, and it was you who I was hurting. It was you, and I am so shocked to see what I was doing to you. How could I have been so blind in my heart not to see this? (He cries at this point and is silent)

Dad, I am so proud of you as my father. I am so proud to be your son.

(He cries again)

These were the words my soul had been aching to hear. Upon hearing them, the dam that was holding in my emotions burst asunder. I wailed loudly as the feelings poured out:

Tears rolled down my cheeks and my nose ran and ran. Saliva even oozed from my mouth. I became a soggy mass of wet. Meanwhile, my stomach churned inside my gut, the muscles becoming sore from the intense contractions. The noise of my wailing would probably have been disturbing to anyone who heard it. I grabbed a pillow and buried my face in it to mask the sound – my wailing was so loud I thought someone might call the police.

The agony of the years of stress and anxiety over the struggle to save my boy gushed out the way water flows from an open fire hydrant... Within the cascade of jumbled emotions, two stood out above the rest. They emerged like two mighty stones protruding from the middle of a swirling whirlpool, offering me refuge from the flood – forgiveness and liberation... (Pappalardo, 2010.)

Because Joshua had forgiven me, I could forgive myself. Also, I knew now that Joshua was not bound by the chains of anger and resentment. He was free, and because he was free, I was also free. I felt the joy of liberation beginning to soothe my soul.

Discovering Christian Spiritualism

Finding the Spiritualist church was a watershed spiritual moment in my life. I am convinced that I was led to it by the Holy Spirit. I visited the church because I had heard that they practiced the “gift of prophecy.” I was interested in learning more about prophecy and possibly getting more communication from my son. After attending the Sunday service, a couple of times, I was surprised to find myself filling out one of their membership forms on the spur of the moment. I had no intention of joining their church, but I felt I was being led, and I certainly did not want to resist the prompting of the Holy Spirit; my intention is to always be obedient to God’s calling, even though it sometimes takes me in unexpected directions that I do not understand at the time. Oftentimes, I gain understanding later, which is comforting, because it affirms that I made the right decision initially.

This decision changed my life. The changes were dramatic, sometimes almost overwhelming. I was compelled to let go of some of my long-held beliefs, open my mind and heart, and receive new information that was at times difficult to accept and process.

Letting Go of Dogma through Life Experience

As a result of my son’s passing, I took a renewed interest in spiritual healing modalities, such as the “laying on of hands.” I took classes in hands-on healing, and later studied another healing technique called Reiki.

Because I got certified as a Reiki Master, I was asked to serve at one of the healing chairs at the local Spiritualist church I had begun to attend. This led to another surprising experience. When I am honest and true to my heart, I sometimes have experiences where my religious doctrine is challenged by my life experience. In those moments, I am forced to make a choice. Am I going to cling to my religious doctrine, or am I going to surrender to what my heart and intuition are telling me? For example, because of my Catholic and Unificationist background, I possessed the belief that homosexuals were sinful and Satanic. I was rather afraid of them and avoided them as much as possible.

One day I was working as a healer, inviting anyone who wanted to sit in my healing chair during Sunday service. A lesbian in the congregation stood up and I could tell she was coming to sit in my chair, so I could not escape. As she approached my chair, I began to feel how much God loved her, and I got choked up. When I laid my hands on her and prayed over her, God said to me “This is my beloved daughter, in whom I am well pleased.”

I had to decide whether to believe my experience or hold on to my dogma. I chose to embrace my experience and let go of my dogma. Then I felt liberation fill my heart. I was now free to love homosexuals. Now I can love them with all my heart as precious sons and daughters of God. In fact, I now feel free to love everyone equally, believer or atheist, saint or criminal.

Developing the “Gift of Prophecy”

The pastor of the church asked me to serve as an assistant pastor and to enroll in the Spiritualist seminary – the *Morris-Pratt Institute*. I accepted the appointment as assistant pastor but resisted her request regarding the seminary. After a couple of more unsuccessful entreaties from her, she once again told me that Spirit really wanted me to go to the seminary. She said not to worry about the money. She said that someone in the congregation felt called to donate the

money for my tuition. I finally surrendered, even though I really didn't personally want to do it; of course, if I'm convinced God wants me to do something, even though I don't want to do it personally, I'm going to do it anyway.

Studying the Morris Pratt Institute material sometimes left me with my mouth hanging open in stunned amazement. The material literally proved – yes, proved – the existence of the spirit world. For example, one of the books I read was a two-volume work by the famous mystery author, Sir Arthur Conan Doyle. Entitled *The History of Spiritualism*, this book details the overwhelming evidence for life after death collected through research by numerous eminent scientists such as Sir William Crookes, the president of the British Royal Society; Professor Charles Richet, Nobel laureate; and Madame Marie Curie, who also won the Nobel Prize for physics. For example, some of these scientists experienced and recorded instances where spirits entered locked rooms and materialized just as Jesus did in the presence of the apostles after his resurrection.

Experiencing the Feminine Aspect of the Divine

I have had many Mystical experiences with God in recent years, but I want to recount one of the more special ones here. It happened in March of 2011. I had just returned empty-handed from a convention of college activities coordinators, trying to get bookings to speak about suicide prevention on the college speaking circuit. I had borrowed the thousands of dollars it took to go to the convention, and I had nothing to show for my efforts.

As I lay on the couch in my living room praying and meditating, I received a vision in my mind. I saw a small alpine lake and a stream cascading down from the surrounding mountains. The lake was perfectly still, as calm as glass, and the stream's water flowed down a mountain and disappeared into the lake.

I asked God for an interpretation of the vision.

The stream represents your efforts. Even though they disappear into the lake, nothing is lost. The stream is relentlessly filling the lake. Eventually the bank of this lake will burst, and a powerful work will pour forth from your efforts. Don't be discouraged! Nothing is lost.

After I received this message, I closed my eyes again and focused some more. I practiced one of the meditation techniques I use for connecting to the Holy Spirit, and it led me to the place where I often see God. I was shown two chairs. On the one closest to me sat a woman; next to her on her right sat a man. I knew that the woman represented the Heavenly Mother; the man represented Heavenly Father. Heavenly Mother did the talking:

Ron, first I want you to know that even though you see two here, I am only one. I am only one. The reason I am manifesting to you as your Divine Mother is because it is most appropriate for me to come to you this way because of where you are right now in your spiritual growth.

She invited me to come and sit on her lap. I took the form and position of a child and did so. “I want you to spend a lot of time right here during this period. I am healing you of certain wounds that you still possess from your childhood,” she said.

This experience went on literally for hours. It seems silly now, but at the time I started getting worried because I had some important business to do at the Post Office. Heavenly Mother eventually told me “Go ahead and take care of your business, but as soon as you come back in the front door of the house, please come right back here to this sofa and we will pick up where we left off, okay?” I did as she said, and when I got back, sure enough, her presence was still there, and the experience went on for hours more.

For about the next eight months, God only appeared to me as Heavenly Mother. After that time, the Heavenly Father manifestation returned, but God can manifest to me as either the Heavenly Father or the Heavenly Mother. In my view, God is not exclusively masculine or feminine. Now when I pray, I address my prayers to “Heavenly Father/Mother, God.” After this

experience, to my surprise, I wound up getting over a dozen bookings to speak on college campuses.

Called Back to the Unification Movement

Even after disassociating myself from the Unification movement, I continued to have recurring dreams in which I was participating in – and sometimes leading and teaching – programs that included large numbers of Unification movement members. Perhaps the most striking was a prophetic dream in which Mother Moon appeared to me. This was around 2012, several months before her husband passed away. She looked at me and spoke to me with tears streaming down her face. She pleaded with me – “Please teach all these things you have learned to the members,” meaning the “members” of the Unification movement.

It was a vivid dream that I did not know what to do with it, so I dismissed it and “filed it away” in my mind. I was perplexed by this dream. I could not see how this dream could ever be fulfilled. I was no longer formally a member of the Unification movement; I assumed that I might not even be welcomed there anymore.

Rev. Moon passed to the spirit world in 2012, and about three days after he ascended, he visited me in my office. In a vision, he appeared near my desk in his trademark suit and tie. He looked around and then spoke to me. “I like what you're doing,” he said, and disappeared. I was puzzled by this vision, because I didn't understand why he would be interested in my work since it had nothing to do with his movement anymore. A few months later I received a surprising phone call from a representative of the Unification Theological Seminary (UTS) (now HJ International), asking me to make a presentation there. As a result of the positive reception of that presentation, I was asked to present a two-day seminar to teach “all these things” that I had learned to an audience of Unificationists. To my surprise, I spent most of the next several years traveling all over the

United States and a few other countries giving seminars in which I teach “all these things you have learned to the members.” I have also written five books on these topics. I am convinced that Rev. Moon had a lot to do with causing the workshop tour to happen.

Called Back to UTS and Future Possibilities

I completed about half of the requirements for a Master’s degree from UTS in the 1990s. From time to time, the idea of completing it would cross my mind. When I prayed a few years ago and asked God what he would think if I re-enrolled to complete my degree, he said he would be very happy if I did that, and he was quite emotional about it. He said he was not “telling” me to do it, but he was so happy when I asked; it provided an opportunity for him to express his feelings about it. Of course, after feeling his heart, I chose to re-enroll; however, I did not know exactly why he wanted me to do that. I received a Master of Religious Education (MRE) degree in 2020 and thought I had finished what God hoped I would do, but that does not seem to be the case. I started receiving spiritual promptings and messages that compelled me to begin working towards the Doctor of Ministry degree.

Lately, I have been receiving messages that after I graduate, I will probably continue to be involved with UTS; perhaps God wants me to teach, as Mother Moon put it, “all these things you have learned.” If it turns out that my time at UTS is over, I will most likely continue my independent ministry.

Theologically, I am currently a practitioner of a Hawaiian religion called Ho’oponopono, as taught by Ihaleakala Hew Len, Ph.D. It is based on the idea that we create our own reality through the thoughts and emotions that emanate from our minds and hearts; we must practice techniques to “clean” our inner selves from incorrect thoughts and feelings. Central to this practice

is the chanting of a mantra: “I’m sorry. Please forgive me. Thank you. I love you.” I don’t fully understand why this system works, but I have experienced extraordinary results by practicing it.

I am still conducting my “First Blessing” workshops, and I host a monthly Zoom webinar called GEMs, which stands for “God-Experiencing Mystics.” It is attended mostly by people who have graduated from my workshops. It provides follow up support, by sharing Mystical experiences and other information that can help people make progress in their relationship with God.

Conclusion

I have already lived a fulfilling and long life. The things I look back on as having been the most valuable and rewarding part of my spiritual autobiography are those experiences which enabled me to, as Henry Nouwen might say, move “from the mind to the heart” (Nouwen, 2010).

I am immeasurably grateful for the many teachers and experiences, even though some might have been painful, which brought me into a direct experience and understanding of the love of God.

I do not know how many years I have left on the earth, or what path I might find myself on. I only hope and pray that I can be successful in discerning what God may intend for me and following that path to the best of my ability.

Methodology

The methodology for this dissertation project began with the workshops I started teaching more than 10 years ago. They were designed with the intention of deepening participants’ understanding of their relationship with God to the point of employing techniques intended to elicit the Mystical experiences studied in this project.

Workshop participants were recently contacted for the purpose of gathering data about their experiences from surveys. The target population included participants who had attended at least one of the author's workshops and reported having had an elicited Mystical experience while attending. A more detailed description can be found in Chapter 4.

Expected Outcomes

Some workshop participants reported Mystical experiences that had far reaching implications. For example, many have challenged orthodox Christian theology and traditional ministerial methodologies. They have revealed a God that is far more unconditionally loving, compassionate, and empathetic than is traditionally presented in mainstream Christianity. This God is also non-exclusivist. The techniques have appeared to be successful no matter what the theological background – or lack thereof – of the experiencers. Although these reports were extraordinary in their implications for theological and ministerial practice, one might reasonably dismiss them as anecdotal. It would be helpful to have a larger pool of data. It was hoped that this research project would provide a larger quantity of data so as to provide a broader understanding of these phenomena.

It was also hoped that the project would provide a deeper understanding of what the long-term effects of Mystical experiences have been on the experiencers. In particular, it would be interesting to know how the experiences affected their day-to-day living. For example, how did it affect their interpersonal relationships. One teenaged workshop participant reported that after her Mystical experience she stopped bullying her fellow high school students. Her experience was not just a momentary phenomenon but brought about a transformative effect on her life.

Did the experiences they had in the workshop lead to subsequent Mystical experiences? One participant had a very powerful profound conversation with God while using the “Journaling with God” technique during the workshop. Surprisingly, even though in that experience God

encouraged him to keep journaling in order to continue the dialogue, he did not do it again until four years later. It was hoped that this project would shed light on how we can help someone like him make quicker progress in developing a day-to-day communion with God. On the other hand, others who adopted one of the techniques into their regular spiritual practice had many subsequent Mystical experiences as a result. It was hoped this project would help reveal a deeper understanding of why some participants chose to continue the practice, while for others, there was little or no development beyond the workshop experience.

What was learned from this study could have a significant effect on how the author and others conducts future programs. Hopefully there would be more success in the facilitation of Mystical experiences. Perhaps the significance of the study would be that it could stimulate others in ministry to consider the possibility of facilitating Mystical experiences in their congregations and begin conducting programs similar to the author's. At a minimum, others may obtain some useful suggestions, tips, or insights about how to be successful in this pursuit. The same might hold true for educators; perhaps academic courses or seminars will be created with an orientation toward eliciting Mystical experiences for the students. In particular, educators in the field of spiritual formation may find this study relevant to their work.

Chapter 2

Review of the Literature

Search Criteria

Search terms that were employed to find sources related to this dissertation project include: mystical, mysticism, mystical experience, elicited mystical experiences, vision quest, and contemplation.

Mystical Experiences Are Not Ineffable

If we are to accept the premise of this dissertation project, we must first address the issue of ineffability. We cannot meaningfully discuss the effects of Mystical experiences if we embrace the idea that Mystical experiences are impossible to describe.

This position harkens back to the work of William James, one of the pioneers in the study of Mystical experience who is often referred to as the “Father of American psychology.” In 1903, his seminal book was published, *The Varieties of Religious Experience*. Therein James supports the position that religion in general makes a positive contribution to the human condition. He believed that religious experiences could enhance well-being, provide comfort, and offer a sense of purpose. These findings are in alignment with the data collected in this dissertation project.

However, regarding Mystical experiences, James lists “ineffability” as one of their four characteristics. He reports that subjects remark that the experience “defies expression, that no adequate report of its contents can be given in words” (James, 1903, p. 257).

Further study has led to a reevaluation of James’ position on ineffability. Some researchers have found that experiencers *can* describe their Mystical encounters in ways that can help others arrive at a significant understanding of what the experience is like. It may take a concentrated

effort, but it is not impossible. The authors of *The Language of Ineffability: Linguistic Analysis of Mystical Experiences* found that “People can meaningfully communicate their mystical experiences” (Yaden, et al. 2016, p. 244). That has been this author’s finding as well.

Other Studies

There have been numerous studies related to the elicitation of mystical experiences. While some have argued against the validity of certain types of elicitation (Granqvist et al. 2005), others have used a variety of techniques with reported success, producing encouraging results, while also addressing long-term effects:

We find that our experimental paradigm is indeed enough to elicit mystical experiences. Based on subjective ratings of experience, rich descriptions from interviews, and data obtained three months after the study, our data indicate that the experiences reported by the participants had a high degree of authenticity and had lasting effects in terms of memory and attribution. These findings demonstrate that at least some forms of mystical experience can be studied in a controlled environment (Anderson et al., 2014).

One crucial difference between the Anderson study and the present research project is in the definition of mystical experience. When one examines the data, it is clear that Anderson uses the term mystical in a very broad sense, as do many other researchers in this field. While many of Anderson’s participants report sensing a “presence,” none of them seem to equate the presence with God. Here are a few examples:

Participant #23. I clearly sensed that I was making contact with the other side (...) I sensed a masculine energy....) You know, when you walk past a person, it feels like there is a wind of sorts. That was how it felt, except it felt more constant.

Participant #9. I experienced a person that came very close to me. (...) I did not have dialog with him (...) It was as if he wanted to say: ‘Do you see me?’ (...) I could clearly see his facial features; his broad nose and eyes.

Participant #8. Someone was definitely there. (...) sometimes my arm or leg made a twitch (...) it felt like someone was inside of me (...) something that at some level took control of me.

Participant #10. I experienced a shift in temperature from warm to cold.

Spiritualists would classify these as spiritual experiences, but these would not be considered Mystical experiences as defined for this study. Most likely, some of the participants are having encounters with entities other than God. For example, participant #10 feels the temperature drop from warm to cold; a spirit that manifests with a cold temperature is usually not a very highly evolved entity. When one makes contact with the Spirit of God, the feeling is usually a warm one, and it is accompanied by what is often an almost overwhelming feeling of Divine Love personally directed towards the recipient.

This dissertation project capitalizes the word Mystical to denote that it is referring only to a subset of mystical experiences that include what the experiencers perceive as genuine communication from God. While Anderson's data indicate that some participants are having authentic spiritual experiences, they would not be classified here as Mystical.

Anderson's study does add valuable insight to the field. In particular, he provides a clear and succinct description of two seemingly conflicting views on the nature of mystical experiences. On one end of the spectrum, the *perennialist* view posits that mystical experiences "are universal in content and occurrence, and that religious techniques and practices elicit similar experiences at all times and in all cultures" (p.218). At the other end, the *particularist* view posits that mystical experiences are mediated, i.e., all experiences are shaped by the cultural concepts and expectations which the individual brings to the experience (Katz, 1978).

Data collected in this dissertation project provide support for both positions. Determining whether an experience is exhibiting perennialist or particularist characteristics should be done on a case-by-case basis. On one hand, as a perennialist might argue, there seem to be some universal elements to the Mystical experience. For example, the experiencers in our study, regardless of

background, unanimously report a benevolent God who seems to have their best interests at heart. There is no hint of judgmentalism, exclusion, condemnation or punishment. Secondly, when respondents report a sense of how God views them, one might say he views them through the eyes of unconditional love. Thirdly, the experience is universally reported as a positive one. Self-esteem is enhanced, confidence is bolstered, and experiencers are motivated to become more loving people.

Our finding that God is benevolent and not interested in punishment is echoed by the English Mystic Julian of Norwich (c.1343-1416) in her book *Revelations of Divine Love*. Julian lived through one of the most severe episodes of the Black Death, which in some locations, killed more than half of the population. It was commonplace for people of the time to believe that the plague was a punishment meted out by a wrathful God in response to human sinfulness, but Julian's Mystical experiences convinced her that this was not the case:

For I saw no wrath except on man's side, and He forgives that in us, for wrath is nothing else but a perversity and an opposition to peace and to love (Julian of Norwich, Ch.48).

Other studies that have shown success in eliciting mystical experiences include ones employing the use of semi-structured nature experiences (Hood, 1977), hypnosis (Sacerdote, 1977), and psilocybin (Barrett et al, 2015). However, these studies do not use the same criteria for defining Mystical experiences as this present study and are not focused on discerning the long-term effects of Mystical experiences.

Nancy Clark, in her 2012 book *Divine Moments: Ordinary People Having Spiritually Transformative Experiences*, provides an excellent research study of Mystical experiencers. Although the experiences are not elicited, valuable information is provided regarding the long-term effects on the experiencers. Ms. Clark is the founder of the Columbus chapter of the

International Association of Near-Death Studies (IANDS), an organization founded by Dr. Raymond Moody, who wrote a groundbreaking book in 1975 called *Life After Life*. The IANDS website is an exceptional source for information related to Mystical experiences.

Other Techniques for Eliciting Mystical Experiences

The author's techniques presented in this dissertation project are by no means an exhaustive list of techniques that are used for facilitating Mystical experiences. Diverse religious and spiritual communities have a long legacy of such techniques.

The Vision Quest: a Native American Tradition

The vision quest is a Native American practice that has the facilitation of prophetic experience as its goal. It can be described as a coming-of-age program; the participants are often teenagers (Dell'Angela, 2002). A participant under the guidance of a shaman called a "Medicine Man" is taken to a remote location in nature. Oftentimes it is on the summit of a hill or mountain. The participant will usually spend one to three days and nights alone practicing techniques for the express purpose of facilitating a prophetic experience. Elements include ardent prayer and fasting from food and drink. Rhythmic drumming is also used. The focus of the prayer is asking for guidance and direction for one's life from the Great Spirit. The prophetic experience often manifests in the form of visions and/or prophetic dreams.

The goal is to receive direct communication from God and/or other spirit guides. This guidance centers around providing clear purpose and direction for the life of the participant.

"If you think of a pipe stem, it is hollow. It's a representation of us being hollow, to allow that breath of God, that vibration, that force, to move through us without any restrictions" (William Walk Sacred).

Sufism: The Path of the Dervish

The Mystical branch of Islam is called Sufism. One who embarks upon the Sufi path is called a dervish; he submits himself to the guidance of a spiritual teacher called a sheikh, who has already mastered the prophetic techniques. Two techniques that the sheikh might teach to facilitate a Mystical experience are meditation and breathing exercises. The Sufi meditation technique that is perhaps most widely recognized by western observers is the whirling meditation; a practitioner is known as a “whirling dervish.”

Huston Smith writes that all Muslim expects to see God after death, “But the Sufis were impatient for their reward, if we may put the matter thus. They wanted to encounter God directly in this very lifetime. Now.” He notes that Sufis are willing to undergo the disciplines that make that possible” (Smith, 1991, p.259).

Yoga

In the West, the word yoga is widely associated with what Hindus call *hatha* yoga. The secular approach is to use hatha yoga bodily postures called *asanas* to enhance physical health, but there is much more to yoga than viewing it merely as a physical exercise routine. Besides hatha yoga, Huston Smith describes four main types: *jnana* yoga, the way to God through knowledge; *bhakti* yoga, the way to God through love; *karma* yoga, the way to God through work; and *raja* yoga, the way to God through psychophysical exercises. What these four yogas have in common is that they are “designed to unite the human spirit with the God who lies concealed in its deepest recesses” (Ibid, p.27).

All four of these yogas contain elements that could be adapted for use in the classroom with the goal of eliciting Mystical experiences. For example, *bhakti* yoga contains the tradition of chanting the name of God while singing and dancing in a rhythmic fashion. This exercise heightens the spiritual vibration of the practitioners to open the doorway to a direct encounter with God.

“Lectio Divina”: The Path of the Contemplative

This practice originated in monastic communities of the Roman Catholic Church.

Lectio Divina, which translates to “divine reading” in Latin, is a traditional method of praying with Scripture. It is a contemplative practice that involves reading, reflecting, praying and contemplating on a passage of Scripture in order to deepen understanding, grow spiritually and develop a personal relationship with God ([The 4 Steps Of Lectio Divina - Practical Catholic Living](#) accessed August 6, 2024).

The four steps of Lectio Divina are:

1. Lectio (Reading)

Slowly and thoughtfully, read the Scripture passage the first time. What word or phrase captures your attention and grabs your heart? Linger with it whenever this happens.

2. Meditatio (Reflection)

Slowly and prayerfully, read the passage again. What is God saying to you in this passage? Offering you? Asking you? What feelings are arising within you?

3. Oratio (Prayer)

Slowly and prayerfully, read the passage again. Respond to God from your heart. Speak to God of your feelings and insights. Offer these to God.

4. Contemplatio (contemplation)

Possibly read the passage another time. Sit quietly in God’s presence, asking, “What are you saying to me?” Rest in God’s love, and listen (Eldredge, accessed August 6, 2024).

Contemplative Pedagogy: A Catholic Approach

Patrick R. Manning is Assistant Professor of Pastoral Theology and Chair of the Department of Pastoral Theology at Immaculate Conception Seminary School of Theology, Seton Hall University. He has written a paper extolling the virtues of a program of meditation and prayer in religious education which he calls contemplative pedagogy (Manning, 2020). Manning comes

very close to advocating for the facilitation of Mystical experiences but does not seem to go quite that far.

He states, and this author agrees, that many of today's problems stem from personal alienation – alienation from God that leads to alienation from ourselves and each other. His solution is a contemplative pedagogy that includes a practice of breathing meditation for undergraduate students and contemplative prayer for graduates. He places emphasis on bringing unity, but in traditional Catholic fashion, the focus is on community – unity within ourselves and unity with each other. There does not seem to be a focus on God in the sense of establishing a two-way communication between God and student. For example, Manning states – “Jesus prayed that we all ‘might be one’ and instructed his disciples, ‘love your neighbor as yourself’” (p.279). However, a fuller reading of this scripture in the Gospel of John reads that we all might “be one, just as you, Father, are in me and I am in you. May they also be one in us...” (John 17:21).

In this scripture, Jesus implies that he is encouraging us to establish the same kind of Mystical communion – a two-way communication – that he experienced with his Heavenly Father. Sadly, many Christians, Catholic and Protestant alike, are convinced that this type of oneness was a relationship that was exclusively within the purview of Jesus. Somehow, we are not qualified to attain this level of relationship, even though Jesus exhorted us to “Be perfect, therefore, as your heavenly Father is perfect” (Matt 5:48). Nevertheless, by offering the opportunity for contemplative prayer at the beginning of some of his classes, Manning is teaching a technique that can facilitate a prophetic experience in a classroom setting.

Chapter 3

Biblical and Theological Context

4Scripture Supports Encountering God – the Mystical Experience – as the Ultimate Goal of Religion

Just before Jesus began his ministry, he was baptized at the Jordan River by John the Baptist. There are several similarities between the experience Jesus had there and the one Charles Finney had in the woods in 1821. Jesus was 30 years old; Charles was 29. Both of them were single. Both of them were seeking something from God. We know this because Finney's experience was preceded by his restlessness of spirit and ardent prayer, while the gospel of Luke tells us Jesus also was praying as he was being baptized (Luke 3:21). It might be said that both of them were seeking God "with all" their hearts (Jer 29:13).

Mark tells us that "Just as Jesus was coming up out of the water, he saw heaven being torn open and the Spirit descending on him like a dove. And a voice came from heaven: 'You are my Son, whom I love; with you I am well pleased'" (Mark 1:10-11).

Jesus experienced what Finney referred to as "a mighty baptism of the Holy Ghost." The experience was so powerful that "the Spirit immediately drove him into the wilderness" for forty days. Jesus cancelled whatever other plans he may have had for his life and, like Finney, he immediately chose the path of ministry, powerfully infused with the Holy Spirit.

When he returned from the wilderness, he began his ministry with a significant emphasis on baptism. Like John the Baptist, Jesus and his disciples began practicing full immersion baptisms (John 3:22,26). He talked of baptism as a gateway to a new life: "Jesus answered, 'Very truly I tell you, no one can enter the kingdom of God unless they are born of water and the Spirit'" (John 3:5). Was not Jesus hoping that by submitting to the baptism ritual, people would have a Mystical experience similar to the one he had?

Traditional Definition of Religion as Experience

Many scholars believe that the word *religion* originates from the Latin verb *ligare*, from which we derive the word *ligament*. *Ligare* means “to connect” or join together. Combined with the prefix *re*, which means “again,” the word *religion* can be translated as “to connect again.” So if religion means to connect again, what is it that is meant to be reconnected? God and human beings.

Therefore, religion in its simplest purest form is any human activity that is practiced for the purpose of reuniting humans with God. From that perspective, a person who is walking in the woods talking to God is practicing religion. In fact, many people have had more profound experiences communing with God in nature than they have had while participating in a church service on a Sunday morning.

This is often what people are really trying to communicate when they say – “I’m not into *religion*; I’m into *spirituality*.” Many people are not completely fulfilled by participating in formal religious activities such as worship services, rituals and theological studies; they would rather have a personal spiritual encounter with God.

So, if the essence of religious practice is to help God and humans reconnect, how do we go about accomplishing that? There are specific spiritual techniques that we can employ in order to connect to God. As ministers, we need to provide people with simple, concrete, practical techniques that are designed to produce real, direct, and personal experiences with God.

The *Collins English Dictionary* defines mysticism as “a system of contemplative prayer and spirituality aimed at achieving direct intuitive experience of the Divine.” Mysticism is that branch of religion that has the direct experience of God as its goal.

Can there be anything more beneficial to a person’s life than having a direct personal encounter with God? The main feature of such an experience is the discovery that God is a Being

of unconditional love. Knowing that we are, at our essence, the beloved child of a Heavenly Parent is a powerfully transformative realization. When we know that we are loved absolutely that knowledge has the power to heal us from our suffering, give deep meaning to our lives, and empower us to achieve our highest potential.

Unificationist Perspective: Tradition and Scripture

Unificationism has a strong tradition of advocating for direct communion with God. Prayer and fasting are two techniques encouraged for this purpose. In the main Unificationist scripture, *Exposition of the Divine Principle*, Sun Myung Moon teaches that we are living in an age in which this phenomenon will become more and more common:

Gradually, the spirituality of fallen people has been rehabilitated as they enjoy the merit of the age in the providence of restoration. In the last days, therefore, many faithful believers will acquire the ability to communicate with God, as was prophesied in the Bible. “In the last days... I will pour out my spirit upon all flesh, and your sons and your daughters shall prophecy, and your young men shall see visions, and your old men shall dream dreams – *Acts 2:17*” (p.96-97).

Reason – Substitutionary Atonement Theory, a Misunderstanding of God’s Heart

In light of the unconditional love that resides in the heart of God, which was revealed by Jesus in such parables as “the prodigal son” and “the lost sheep,” it is not reasonable to view God as a God of wrath and punishment. Embracing a wrathful God is often an impediment to Mystical experience. Nevertheless, a considerable number of the world's Christians subscribe to the belief that their earthly life is a kind of test or challenge to live according to what they perceive to be the moral imperatives of the Divine Will. They believe in what some refer to as the rewards/punishment paradigm; if we live according to the will of God we are rewarded by eternal life in heaven, if we fail we are sentenced to the torment of unquenchable fire in hell. A central tenet of this world view is that human beings, due to the fall of Adam and Eve, are inherently sinful, inheriting original sin from our ancestors. Because of our fallen nature and sinful actions,

it was necessary for Jesus to come and die on the cross in place of us, thereby placating a wrathful God.

The eminent Franciscan priest and theologian, Father Richard Rohr, rejects this interpretation of the meaning of the crucifixion, which is called *substitutionary atonement theory*:

The Franciscan view of atonement theory is a prime example of our alternative orthodoxy. The Franciscan School was dissatisfied with the popular theological idea that Jesus came to Earth as a necessary sacrifice to appease an angry God. As human consciousness advances, more and more people cannot believe that God would demand Jesus' blood as payment for our sins. It seems to be inevitable that our old logic needs to break up before we can begin to grow up.

The most common reading of the Bible is that Jesus “died for our sins”—either to pay a debt to the devil (generally believed in the first millennium) or to pay a debt to God (proposed by Anselm of Canterbury in the 11th century and holding sway for most of the second millennium). But even in the 13th century, Franciscan philosopher and theologian John Duns Scotus (1266–1308) agreed with neither of these understandings.

Duns Scotus was not guided by the Temple language of debt, atonement, and blood sacrifice, which was understandably used by the Gospel writers and by Paul. Instead, he was inspired by the cosmic hymns in the first chapters of Colossians and Ephesians and the Prologue to John's Gospel (1:1-18). While the Church has never rejected the Franciscan position, it has remained a minority view.

The terrible and un-critiqued premise of many “substitutionary atonement theories” is that God demanded Jesus to be a blood sacrifice to “atone” for our sin-drenched humanity. As if God could need payment, and even a very violent transaction, to be able to love and accept God's own children (Rohr, 2020).

Biblical support for Rohr's position is found in the words of Jesus. In the parable of the prodigal son, the son squanders his inheritance on “wild living” (Luke 15:13). It does not take much imagination to conclude that Jesus was referring to behavior that many people would refer to as sinful and immoral. Only when a famine places him in a life-threatening desperate situation does the son think about returning to his father:

When he came to his senses, he said, “How many of my father's hired servants have food to spare, and here I am starving to death! I will set out and go back to my father and say to him: Father, I have sinned against heaven and against you. I am

no longer worthy to be called your son; make me like one of your hired servants” (Luke 15:17-19).

That is not how the father saw him, and that is not how God sees us.

... while he was still far off, his father saw him and was filled with compassion; He ran and put his arms around him and kissed him. (v.20)

Summary

There is significant scriptural and theological support for recognizing Mystical experience as the central purpose and goal of religion.

Father Rohr’s position and the experiences of workshop experiencers challenge the traditional belief that people are sinful and therefore not worthy to experience the love of God. The workshop experiences demonstrate that this traditional mindset is the number one block to people having a direct Mystical experience.

The influence of Judeo-Christian or Islamic belief systems makes one vulnerable to this problem because of the emphasis that is placed on the concept of sin and unworthiness. The experiences of the workshop participant and many Mystics affirm that this does not appear to be something that God emphasizes. On the contrary, God does not appear interested in judging anybody; we are much harsher critics of ourselves than is our Heavenly Parent.

It seems that sin is not so much about what one does, but rather is a state that one might be in, i.e., the state of being alienated from the Heavenly Parent. It does not take understanding complex theology to heal that rift; all it takes is an open heart and a willingness to reunite, and then practicing techniques that have been shown to end the alienation. We have to be willing to let go of – and to fight if necessary – the false belief that we are not worthy of God’s love.

In scripture, Jesus exhorts us to be born again of water and the Holy Spirit. Just as he experienced at the Jordan river, religion’s primary focus should be to provide someone a doorway

to an encounter in which they can also hear God say to them “You are my son (daughter), I love you, and I am well pleased with you.” Therein lies the fundamental theological basis for this ministry.

Chapter 4

Design of the Study

Key Design Elements

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this study was to gather data regarding the long-term effects of Mystical experiences upon those who had such an experience at one of the author's workshops. Particular attention was paid to the effects related to everyday living such as interpersonal relationships, work and spiritual growth.

Since the experiences were not random events but induced through the practice of specific techniques, it was hoped that this research project would help provide a deeper understanding of the efficacy of these techniques, what their long-term effects could be, and what, if anything, could be done to more effectively facilitate and elicit future Mystical experiences.

Project Goals and Objectives

It was hoped that others would work with these techniques with the goal of duplicating these extraordinary results. The techniques could be used not only in a workshop setting, but also in Sunday schools, worship services, and in the classroom. They might also be incorporated into courses related to the field of spiritual formation.

Research Questions

The essential research questions developed for this project were:

- 1) Do elicited Mystical experiences have long-term effects on people's lives? If so, what kind of long-term effects do they have?
- 2) Do elicited Mystical experiences result in an enhanced relationship with God?

The project also hoped to gather data that might provide insight into a few other related questions, such as:

- 1) Does a one-time Mystical experience have a deep impact, or does it take multiple experiences over a prolonged period?
- 2) Did participants in the workshops have additional experiences on their own as a result of the training received in the workshop, or only in the workshop environment?
- 3) How can the workshops and follow-up ministry, be improved to better support people having meaningful Mystical experiences, developing their relationship with God?
- 4) Does a person's religious background affect their ability to have a Mystical experience?

Most of the Mystical experiences occurred during the practice of techniques that had been repeatedly found to elicit them in some participants. Here we take a deeper look into three of the most successful ones. They were hands-on healing, guided meditations, and what the author refers to as the “Journaling with God” technique.

Workshop Techniques for Mystical Experience Facilitation

Hands-on Healing Technique

“At sunset, the people brought to Jesus all who had various kinds of sickness, and laying his hands on each one, he healed them” (Luke 4:40). Hands-on healing was a simple exercise that can be used to facilitate prophetic and/or Mystical experiences. The author learned the basics of this technique from the Rev. Mary Mooney at an evening class she taught over a few weekly sessions at the Unity Church of the Triangle in Raleigh, NC several years ago. The author added more elements to her basic instructions in order to enhance the facilitative effect. The author was also a certified Reiki master and incorporated some Reiki elements into this technique.

Almost anyone can perform this technique. Meditation and journaling might appear as a less daunting exercise to students if preceded by a hands-on healing exercise. In a workshop or classroom setting, hands-on healing is often the first technique introduced, serving as a “warm-up” exercise before meditation and/or journaling. One of the reasons hands-on healings can be easier to perform is that the participants make use of their physical bodies as well as their minds, while meditation and journaling are primarily exercises of the mind and heart which require more mental and emotional focus and concentration than hands-on healing.

To prepare the students, have them imagine that their arms will be used like a garden hose. The energy of the Holy Spirit is going to come down on top of their head, flow down their shoulders, through their arms and out through their hands. While the purpose of a garden hose is to convey water from a source outward to the plants growing in a garden, during that process the inside of the garden hose also gets wet as the water passes through. In the same way, during hands-on healing the participant is a conduit for the healing power of the Holy Spirit to pass through them. Just as the garden hose gets wet with water, the hands-on healer gets “wet” with the Holy Spirit. Most will feel a warmth or tingling in their hands while performing this exercise; many report that the warming or tingling begins even before they lay their hands on someone. This has the effect of encouraging the students. “Wow,” they might think, “Something is really happening here. Maybe I will actually be able to have some type of holy experience!” This type of positive thinking is helpful in facilitating a prophetic experience. *Believing* that something is possible greatly increases the chances of success. As Jesus said to the woman who was healed from her hemorrhagic condition – “Daughter, your faith has healed you” (Luke 8:48).

The workshop leader should have the students imagine this energy as a bright white light that descends from heaven like a searchlight. It comes down and touches the top of the head, and

then pours through the students' arms and out through their hands. Explain that the exercise is simple and easy. They just need to imagine that they are like a garden hose. Water flows from a source through the garden hose and out through the end. In this case, the student is not conveying water, but the healing energy of the Holy Spirit. The primary source of this healing energy is the unconditional love of God. It cannot be emphasized enough how important it is for both teacher and students to embrace a mindset of God's unconditional love in the classroom while preparing for and executing this exercise.

After the exercise, most participants will report some type of transcendent experience. They will range widely, from simply feeling the hands warming up or tingling, to the experience of a spontaneous physical healing of some ailment. Expect comments like, "While I was laying my hands on (name), I started to choke up, because I could feel how much God loved them." Someone might report that they experienced nothing particularly notable, but even so, they will most likely sense something transcendent in the classroom. The spiritual atmosphere and energy heighten when our hearts align with the love manifested by the Holy Spirit, and most if not all participants will sense that to varying degrees – "For where two or three gather in my name, there am I with them" (Matt 18:20).

Most participants will also report that they felt a feeling of peace, calm, and tranquility. Feelings of safety and feeling "I am at home" are reported. This experience opens the mind and heart to the possibility of even deeper encounters with God. It prepares students for the often powerfully transformative Mystical encounters that occur through the guided meditation and "Journaling with God" techniques.

Hands-on Healing Procedure

- 1) Pairing: Half of the students stayed seated in their chairs. Chairs were arranged in pairs, partnering a classmate to stand behind each seated student. (If there were an odd number of participants, the facilitator also participated.)
- 2) Name: Each standing student leaned over and asked the seated student for their name.
- 3) Permission: Each standing student asked the seated student if they were comfortable with having hands laid upon their shoulders. (If the seated student was uncomfortable with being touched, the standing student placed their hands hovering just above the shoulders without touching them. Alternately, the standing student could place their hands hovering above the head of the seated student without touching the head.)
- 4) Laying on of hands: The standing students laid their hands on (or above) the shoulders of the seated student. The students were instructed that they didn't need to do anything to “push” the healing energy, but just let it flow through them. The Holy Spirit was doing the healing; they were just a conduit.
- 5) Seeing with God’s eyes: The standing students were asked to place a finger on the side of their face next to their eye and repeat --“Heavenly father, let me see (recite name) with your eyes. Let me see (name) them as your precious child.”
- 6) Feeling with God's heart: The standing students were asked to place a hand over their heart and repeat -- “Heavenly Father, let me feel (name) with your heart. Let me feel how much you love them.”
- 7) Prayer: The facilitator prayed just before beginning the exercise similar to the following: “Dear Heavenly Father, we ask you to send your Holy Spirit to us right now. We open our hearts and minds to your presence. Scripture teaches us that we are God's temple and that your Holy Spirit dwells inside of us. Please let your Holy Spirit descend upon us and flow

through us for the purpose of bringing healing to your precious children, our brothers and sisters. Please let us see this person with your eyes. Please let us feel this person with your heart. May they find complete healing in body, mind, heart, and soul. Amen!”

- 8) Chanting: the participants were led with the following words: “God's love, flows through me, for the purpose, of healing (person’s name) now!” The words were repeated slowly, over and over, like a chant or mantra, for about 5 minutes.
- 9) Focusing: At some point during these 5 minutes, the healers were reminded to ask God to let them see the person sitting in the chair in front of them as a precious beloved son or daughter of God. They were instructed to ask God to let them feel what God feels for this person. Some of them telepathically received words from God such as “You are so loved,” or “Everything is going to be OK,” or “This is my beloved son (daughter) in whom I am well pleased.” The workshop facilitator sometimes triggered such prophetic experiences by suggesting to the healers to “Ask if God wanted to say something to the person in your chair, what would God's message be?” Mystical experiences were sometimes triggered not only for the healer, but also for the participant sitting in the chair.
- 10) Changing Hand Positions: participants were encouraged to trust their intuition regarding hand positions. After some moments, some received the inspiration to move their hands from the shoulders to the top of the head, sometimes hovering above the head. Some sensed that they should move their hands differently, placing one hovering over the heart while the other hand hovered over the middle of the back. Others felt moved to shift the hands from the shoulders to the sides of the head, hovering over the ears.

11) Change Places: After practicing the technique for about five minutes, the seated student stood and took the position behind the chair, while the student who was standing sat down in the chair. Steps 2 through 9 were then repeated.

12) Testimonies: Participants were invited to share their experiences as both recipients and senders of the healing energy. Sometimes they reported this orally to the entire group, in other cases they wrote their testimony.

Guided Meditation Technique

Introduction to the “Sun Meditation”. There are many types of meditation techniques, and they are performed for a variety of different purposes and goals. This particular meditation technique has as its purpose the facilitation of a Mystical experience involving two-way communication with God. It is a guided meditation, which simply means that the facilitator will give oral directions and guidance to the participants throughout the meditation.

The author created this meditation by adding elements to an “on the beach” relaxation meditation that many others have used. Some teachers and practitioners use other variations. The element of moving a small light from the forehead to the heart was the author’s addition. It was a variation on a technique learned from a Hindu guru who was a guest speaker several years ago at the Unity Church of the Triangle in Raleigh, North Carolina; efforts to identify or locate this guru have been unsuccessful.

Facilitator Preparation. Before beginning to lead these meditation exercises, it was important to prepare with prayer. Prayer was focused on facilitating the highest good of each participant, asking God to reveal himself to them, so that they might feel his presence during the meditation. It was helpful to have a participant list, with photos if possible. It was also helpful to look at the pictures before the time of the meditation exercise and speak their names, asking God

to let them be seen with his eyes and heart, and to become a conduit of his love, and then project God's love to each student one by one. Included in the prayer was the exhortation that each student could have an experience of God's unconditional love, that each one might know that they are loved completely and uniquely, again asking God that he might reveal his presence to them. This was done at various times - for days leading up to the class, the night before the class, the morning before the class, or just before the beginning of the exercise.

Here is an example of the type of prayers used:

Dear Heavenly Father, I'm praying right now for John Doe, your precious son. Please let me see John with your eyes and heart. (You might pause here to let the feeling of God's love well up within your heart.) I pray that this meditation will be for his highest good. I pray that he can experience your presence, and your unconditional love. I pray that he will know that he is loved completely and uniquely by you.

The participants were prepared by slowly and carefully explaining what they were about to experience, going through each step of the meditation before beginning. This was done because participants otherwise might become stressed with the thought of "Am I doing this right?" This reassured them by telling them that there was no wrong way to do the meditation. comforting them by explaining what might happen during the meditation:

Now we are going to practice the Sun meditation. This meditation has been designed to help facilitate a direct encounter between yourself and God. It helps you to become relaxed, to let go of any fear or anxiety you might have, and to open your heart to let God commune with you.

We will start by taking a few deep breaths for relaxation. I will have you imagine you are sitting on a chair at the beach. You'll be barefoot, and able to feel the sand under your feet. It's a beautiful, clear day, there's not a cloud in the sky, and the bright sunshine feels warm and soothing on your skin.

The sun will be right out in front of you up in the sky over the ocean. After we relax into our chairs with a few deep breaths, I will ask you to look right into the sun. You will notice that the light does not hurt your eyes. Then I'll ask you to notice that the color of the sun begins to pale from yellow to white.

Then I will have you shift your focus from the sun to your own forehead. I will have you imagine that you have a little ball of bright white light right in the center of your forehead. Then I will invite you to move this ball of light. You will let it drift down from your forehead down between your eyes, down your nose, past your lips and chin, down your neck, until it comes to rest right in the center of your heart.

Then you'll get the feeling that the light in the center of your heart wants to shine out. So, you will imagine a little beam of light or ray of light extending out from your heart about 6 inches in front of your chest. Then it will grow to 1 foot, 2 feet, etc. This beam of light will extend out in front of you across the sand and the waves, out over the ocean as it heads up, up, up into the sky towards the bright white light of the sun.

I will guide you to connect your beam of light right into the center of the sun, and that's when the magic may happen. When you make your connection, you may have a spiritual experience.

All you need to do is to observe what happens. Make note especially of your feelings, your emotions. Make note of what you see, and listen to see if you hear anything, including words. You may speak if you feel so inclined. I will be silent during this time, and you won't hear me speak for a few minutes. Afterward, I will guide everyone back out of the meditation.

If during the meditation you begin to have a spiritual experience, please disregard my voice if it interferes with your experience. Trust your experience and go with it.

Sun Meditation Procedure. Take a deep breath. Focus on your breath. It relaxes you and helps to stop the mind from wandering. This is accomplished by focusing on the space under the nose where the nostrils and the top of the upper lip meet. Imagine you are sitting in a chair at the beach, in the sand facing the water, and you can hear the waves gently rolling up in front of you. It is a perfectly clear day. You might smell a subtle hint of salt in the air. The warm sun is in the sky right in front of you. Barefoot, you can feel the warm sand with your toes. The light and the warmth of the sun are so delightful; you are drawn to the sun. Go ahead and look into it; it won't hurt your eyes. Notice that the yellow color begins to pale until it eventually changes to bright white light.

You notice that you possess your own bright light, right in the center of your forehead, about the size of a ping pong ball, sitting in the place called “the third eye.” This light belongs to you and you alone. It is the same quality as the light of the sun in front of you; it’s just a smaller version. Slowly move your little ball of light. Imagine it begins to descend your face, from your forehead down to the space between your eyes, then sliding to the tip of your nose. Let it continue down your neck, to your chest, until it eventually stops at the center of your heart.

This little ball of light is now dwelling right in the center of your heart. Imagine that it is emitting a small beam of light straight out in front of you, about six inches out. It slowly extends itself from six inches to one foot in front of you. Then two feet, three feet. It’s going out over the sand in front of you. Now it’s ascending over the water, six feet, ten feet. It glows strongly with the love energy of your heart. It heads towards the sky and is slowly approaching the bright white light of the sun. It goes up, and up, and when you reach the sun, let your beam of light connect right to the center of the sun and become still.

Now, just relax and experience. Notice what this feels like. Take some time to listen, look, and feel. You can send your emotions, thoughts, or questions along your beam of light, up to the light, and receive responses. You can listen for words coming from the light and feel its emotions. If an inspiration or message comes to you, write it down.

(Silence for four to five minutes.)

(Speak in a soft voice) Ok. That’s good. If you are still having an experience, continue with your experience until it ends. When you are ready, gently disconnect your ray of light, and slowly let it return to the center of your heart. When you are ready, you may open your eyes.

Make sure you write down anything that happens – any feelings that you have, thoughts that pop into your head, or words that you sense.

Journaling with God Technique

Procedure. Journaling was the author's preferred technique for helping people get in touch with God and establish two-way communication. It's simple to learn and often gets extraordinary results. One could describe it as a form of prayer in which one writes their prayer instead of using the spoken word. One way of thinking about Journaling with God is to imagine writing God a letter, an email, or a diary entry. Participants were instructed that after writing to God they should take the time to get quiet, take a deep breath, and listen to see if they could sense God responding to them and that it helps to listen with the heart. Sometimes it helps to put a hand over the heart while listening.

The key to success in this exercise, is to ask God this question – “Is there anything you would like to say to me right now.” Then participants were instructed to write down the very first thing that pops into their mind. It happens very fast. There may be just one or two words, but by the time one finishes writing down those one or two words, something else will pop into one's mind. As that is written down, something else will come, and so on. As the process continues, many are surprised to find that they are receiving a substantial message. People often get the most amazing, profound messages when they take the time to stop, listen, and then write down what they receive.

Participants were instructed that it's extremely important to start by writing the first thing that pops into the mind. Even if it makes no sense or sounds absurd. They were told that they should not try to analyze or rationalize what they were receiving. This is an exercise of the heart. Oftentimes in life, one receives intuitive inspirations or insights, and then has what are called “second thoughts.” We try to analyze what we receive, and doubts creep in. By doing so, the process can suffer a “short circuit” and shut down.

Workshop/Classroom Atmosphere. A prophetic experience is one in which the mind and heart are intimately engaged. The success of facilitating such experiences is directly related to the sensing of the presence of the Holy Spirit, and the mental and emotional state of the participants. It was possible – and essential – for the facilitator to do everything in their power to nourish an atmosphere that opens the mind and heart to the possibility of prophetic experience. The facilitator was someone who has had their own personal prophetic experience and therefore has the confidence to lead others to such experience; the more the facilitator believes this, the more likely it is to happen.

As Scripture teaches us, “God is spirit, and his worshipers must worship in the Spirit and in truth” (John 4:24). The best thing a facilitator can do to help trigger Mystical experiences is to raise the spiritual atmosphere, raise the spiritual vibration. It was essential that prayer should be a part of each exercise. In addition, one of the best ways to raise the spiritual vibration was the corporate singing of hymns or other songs characterized by joy, enthusiasm, celebration, and laughter. One effective song for inducing a joyful atmosphere is to have everyone stand in a circle and sing the children’s song “If You're Happy and You Know It Clap Your Hands.” Others were “We Are One in the Spirit,” and “All the Lands that I Loved.”

God being omnipresent, in order to experience his presence, all that was necessary was to simply raise our vibrations so we could approach the “wavelength” he came in on. It was like tuning a radio to a specific radio wave – a type of vibration – so that we can listen to what is playing on a certain radio station.

Research Population and Sampling Measure

The survey population was confined to only persons who had participated in one of the author's programs. In a ministry that began around the time of the publication of the author's first book in 2009, more than 1000 people have attended one of these programs. The participants in this study attended programs between the years 2014 and 2024. Over the years, around 450 email addresses had been gathered from these participants. This project began with an e-mail addressed to 421 of these participants, entitled "Did you have an experience with God at my workshop?" Recipients were asked to respond with just a one-word answer: "Yes" or "No" (Appendix A). After receiving perhaps 20 responses, a second version of the e-mail was sent with the title "Dissertation time. I need your help!" Thirty-three people responded to these two emails in total. Thirty said "Yes," and three said "No."

The 30 "yes" respondents then received an e-mail requesting that they sign and return a participant consent form. Twenty-six of them returned the form. These 26 were then sent the multiple-choice survey. Twenty-five filled out the survey and returned it. These 25 were then sent one final question, which was an essay style question. Twenty-one answered this question and sent back their essay.

Ethical Guidelines

Prior to receiving the project survey, all participants were required to sign and return a participant consent form approved by HJ International Graduate School for Peace and Public Leadership. This consent form outlined the following ethical guidelines for the research project.

Participants were informed that they could withdraw participation at any time or refuse to answer any of the questions without any consequences. This withdrawal could take place up to two weeks after submitting the survey. In cases of withdrawal, all data received from participants would be deleted. Participants agreed that they had the purpose and nature of the study explained

to them in writing and had the opportunity to ask questions about the study. They were told that they would not benefit directly from participating in the research. All information was to be treated confidentially and only available to the researcher during the research process. Each participant's identity would remain anonymous in any report on the results of the research. This would be accomplished by changing the name and any disguising details of the survey that might reveal the identity of the participant or any people the participant might speak about. Participants were informed that disguised extracts from their survey might be quoted in the researcher's Doctor of Ministry dissertation project, published papers, and conference presentations. All participants certified that they were at least 18 years of age (see Appendix A).

Methodology and Instrumentation

The topic of this dissertation project was chosen as a result of suggestions from a fellow doctoral candidate and the recommendation of one of the author's professors, Dr. Andrew Wilson. These developments took place during a discussion in the context of the professor's class. The format and design of this study came about as a result of information gleaned from a doctoral studies class that had been introduced in a course taught by Dr. Jennifer Tanabe, which focused on basic survey formats and the Google Forms application.

The survey questions were submitted to both the second reader and faculty advisor for review. The survey was finalized only after receiving feedback and approval from these advisors.

To the 30 "Yes" respondents, a follow-up e-mail was sent asking them if they would be willing to sign a participant consent form to participate in the research project. Twenty-six of them signed. Then a Google Forms survey of 13 questions was sent to these signatories. This survey was designed to be user friendly. It only required respondents to answer "yes" or "no," or check the boxes in multiple choice questions. 25 out of 26 signatories filled out the survey. Twenty-one

of those who filled out the survey offered additional comments by answering the 14th question, which was an essay style question.

Essay style questions were purposely left out of the initial survey in order to maximize the number of participants that might successfully fill out and return the survey. This was done as a result of a consultation with an industrial-organizational psychologist, who has a lot of experience with these types of surveys as a result of his career. The psychologist reported that some survey respondents will give up completing a survey when confronted with an essay question and fail to send in the survey. Not only does the researcher fail to get the essay question answered, but they also don't get the multiple-choice survey questions answered either. Therefore, the final essay style question was sent in a separate e-mail only after respondents had completed the initial 13 question survey. As expected, some of those who filled out the initial survey did not complete the final essay question. Nevertheless, 21 out of 25 did, an impressive 84% participation rate.

Reliability and Validity

The survey questions were designed in a manner to increase the reliability of the study. For example, the reader might find it suspicious that 100% of the respondents reported, in relationship to their Mystical experience, that “the overall effect it had on me was positive.” However, in this multiple-choice question, respondents were invited to “check all that apply.” Included in those choices were “it had absolutely no effect,” “it made me feel uneasy,” and “the overall effect it had on me was negative.” The fact that not a single respondent checked any of those three choices adds strength to the argument that Mystical experiences are overwhelmingly positive ones.

Similar suspicion might be aroused when the reader sees that 96% of respondents reported that “my experience at the workshop helped me continue to make progress in my relationship with

God.” However, in this multiple-choice question, respondents could have also chosen “my experience at the workshop had no effect on continuing my progress in my relationship with God,” or “my experience at the workshop made it more difficult for me to continue to make progress in my relationship with God.” These responses strengthen the finding that Mystical experiences, even those induced or elicited in a workshop setting, can have a powerful positive effect on progress in one's relationship with God.

Chapter 5

Results of the Study

Limitations of the Study

In many cases, follow-up emails, physical mail, text messages, and telephone calls were employed to remind participants to send in either their consent forms, surveys, or final essay questions. For example, for one elderly participant who had a difficult time navigating Internet technology, a consent form was sent by physical mail. This mailing included a pre-addressed and postage-stamped return envelope to make the return process as simple and easy as possible. Patience and persistence are recommended to get the largest response.

Even though over 1000 people have attended these workshops, contact information for only 427 of them was found. This greatly reduced the pool of potential respondents to the survey. The requirement that participants had to sign a consent form deterred some workshop graduates from participating in the survey. Having to deal with some elements of Internet technology slowed the process of gathering data, and deterred a few people, especially the elderly, from participating. Only 25 participants fully completed the survey.

Did the Data Answer the Research Questions?

Here we will take a look at the research questions in light of the answers received. Three questions were:

- Q1: Do Mystical experiences have long-term effects on people's spiritual lives?
- Q 2: If so, what kind of long-term effects do they have?
- Q 3: Do Mystical experiences result in an enhanced relationship with God?

The most striking finding related to these three questions was revealed in the answer respondents gave to survey question #9. Respondents were offered three choices related to the effect, if any, their workshop Mystical experience had on their ability to “continue to make progress in my relationship with God.” They could choose “my experience at the workshop had no effect,” “my experience... helped me continue to make progress,” or “my experience... made it more difficult for me to continue to make progress. Almost all respondents, 96%, said the experience “helped me.” Only one (4%) said it had “no effect.” None chose that it made progress “more difficult.”

About one in four (24%) reported that their workshop experience was the first time in their life that they had a Mystical “experience where God communicated something to you.” Therefore, in some cases, not only did participants have their first Mystical experience, but it was also the beginning point for subsequent Mystical encounters with God.

In conclusion, it was clear that in almost every case, these Mystical experiences elicited by the workshop techniques had long-term effects on the experiencers’ spiritual lives. In particular, they made it easier for them to continue making progress in their relationship with God.

- 1) Does a one-time Mystical experience have a deep impact, or does it take multiple experiences over a prolonged period?

The data indicated that in some cases, even one Mystical experience can have, not just a deep impact, but a life-transformative impact. In survey question #8, when presented with the opportunity to check “What effect has this experience had on you,” 100% of respondents chose “The overall effect it had on me was positive,” and 56% chose, “It changed my life.” No respondents chose “the overall effect it had on me was negative,” or “it had absolutely no effect.”

Seventy-two percent chose “It made me feel better about myself,” 52% chose “I felt a sense of liberation,” 48% chose “It increased my self-confidence,” and 40% chose “I felt as if something was healed.”

- 2) Did participants in the workshop have additional experiences on their own as a result of the training received in the workshop, or only in the workshop environment?

Since 96% chose that the “experience... helped me continue to make progress in my relationship with God,” we can deduce that many of them had subsequent Mystical experiences. This question is answered even more conclusively in survey question #6, where respondents were asked, “Was this a one-time encounter with God, or did you have more experiences after the workshop?” 88% reported that they had “more experience(s) after.” 12% chose that it was a “one-time” experience, so for this group it was their only encounter with God.

- 3) How can the workshops, and follow-up ministry, be improved to better support people having meaningful Mystical experiences, developing their relationship with God?

Answers to this question can be found in the comments section of the survey which was based on an essay type question (survey question #14. See Appendix D for complete answers).

E#6 reported:

I didn't know what to expect but am always searching for experiences with God. That first workshop was deeply personal and inspiring and so I have gone to four other workshops with Ron. ... the workshops have a higher atmosphere that helps more people have experiences on their own with God and the high spirit world.

Ron has also done 74 Zoom sessions beginning during the (Covid) pandemic with people searching for experiences with God. I have participated in 71 of them. No other group gives you the experience of people sharing how they have broken through, sharing their techniques, dreams, visions, explorations. He has had many guest speakers of exceptional quality sharing their visions, near death experiences, flashes of God's love, journaling messages, books read, etc. I look forward to these sessions also.

This experiencer recommended attending more than one workshop. He believed that the spiritual atmosphere at the workshop was heightened, which added to the potential for people to have Mystical experiences while attending. He also recommended that people attend the Zoom sessions conducted by the author.

4) Does a person's religious background affect their ability to have a Mystical experience?

For this group – and in the workshops generally – religious background did not seem to be an impediment to the Mystical experience. Respondents were from a variety of backgrounds: 44% Unificationists, 28% former Unificationists, 20% Catholic, 4% Protestant, and 4% Other. The preponderance of Unificationists and former Unificationist respondents is simply due to the fact that the vast majority of workshops were held in Unificationist venues.

In one of the first workshops held in the author's home, a powerfully life-transformative Mystical experience was received by a teenage girl of LDS background. Regarding non-Christian participants, the author has received testimonies from workshop participants of Japanese origin who had Mystical experiences; coming from a non-Christian background seems to pose no impediment.

What the Survey Questions Revealed

The data collected in Questions #1 through #3 support the idea that God is equally available to people regardless of their background. For example, men and women were almost equally represented in the experiencer population, 60% men and 40% women. Religious background and age likewise seemed to provide no impediment. Catholics, Protestants, Unificationists and members of other smaller religious groups reported, both in this data and anecdotally, that they had powerful Mystical encounters with God.

Theologically, this has important implications. Fundamentalists of many religious persuasions have a tendency to present their theological positions as exclusivist. For example, the

author, who spent nine years in Roman Catholic parochial schools, was taught that one needed to be baptized into the Roman Catholic faith; if not, one was destined for eternal damnation in Hell. Some Catholics would even argue that God didn't listen to the prayers of anyone who wasn't Catholic.

Based on the data, one could argue that God disagrees with this position. The data helped to confirm the author's suspicion that God loves all of his children equally, and that he longs to establish a direct personal relationship with each one regardless of their background or beliefs.

Questions 4 through 6 helped affirm the efficacy of the workshop techniques. For example, almost 25% of respondents reported that participating in one of the techniques resulted in their very first occurrence of a Mystical experience in which God communicated something to them. For those who had already had a previous Mystical experience, 44% reported that their workshop experience was stronger than previous encounters with God.

Eighty-eight percent of the experiencers reported that they had additional Mystical experiences after the workshop. At a minimum the goal of this ministry is to guide people into at least one Mystical experience in their lifetime; even one can be a permanently life-transformative experience. Beyond that minimum goal, it is hoped that the workshop experience can be a springboard to a long-term experiential relationship with God.

Question 7 reported the frequency of Mystical experiences reported using each of four techniques. "Journaling with God" was selected by 64%, guided meditation 60%, something the author or someone else said during the workshop 40%, and hands-on healing 24 %.

Question 8 reports some of the effects the Mystical experience had. Participants had the opportunity to check a box denoting if it was a positive or negative experience. One hundred percent of respondents chose "The overall effect it had on me was positive," while not a single

negative response was given. Ninety-two percent chose “It made me feel closer to God.” Eighty-four percent, “I felt a loving presence,” 72% checked three boxes that said, “I felt a sense of peacefulness,” “It made me feel that God knew me personally,” and “It made me feel better about myself.” Fifty-six percent reported “It changed my life,” 52% checked “I felt a sense of liberation,” and “It made me feel more committed to God.” Forty-eight percent reported “It increased my self-confidence” and 40% chose “I felt as if something was healed.” No respondents checked the boxes that said, “It had absolutely no effect,” or “It made me feel uneasy.”

Question 9 reported that 96% of respondents chose “My experience at the workshop helped me continue to make progress in my relationship with God.” No one said it “made it more difficult...”

Question 10 dealt with the topic of interpersonal relationships. Seventy-six percent reported that their experience had “a positive effect on their family” and “non-family” relationships. Sixty percent chose “It had a positive effect on my work.” No one reported any negative effect on relationships or work.

Eighty-eight percent answered “yes” to question 11, “Did anything surprise you? Was there something about your experience that you did not expect?” Some respondents went into more detail about how they were surprised and why. This is revealed in the answers given to question #14, which are discussed in more detail below, under Theological Implications.

Question 12 asked “Did your experience have any effect on your beliefs or theology?” 76% chose “yes,” 16% chose “no.” Sixty percent chose “It affirmed that some of the things I had suspected about God were true, even though these were not part of my traditional religious education,” 32% chose “It strengthened my belief in my faith traditions teachings” and 24 % chose “It made me question my belief in some of my faith traditions teachings.” The same number

responded that “It contradicted some of my faith traditions teachings,” while 16% check the box that said, “The experience was different from what I would have expected, given my theological background.”

Mystical Experience Vis-a-Vis Theology

In most cases, the Mystical experiencers were surprised to find that their experiences did not align with the traditional theology of their upbringing. About one in four went so far as to affirm that “it contradicted some of my faith traditions teachings.” Others have reported the same phenomenon (Blum, 2009):

Drawing on empirical examples, I show that accounts of Mystical experience do not always accord with context or mainstream religious doctrine, and sometimes diverge from them in significant ways (p.ii).

The medieval German Mystic, Meister Eckhart (1260-1328), is widely quoted for this short but relevant description of the difference between mystics and theologians: “Theologians may quarrel, but the Mystics speak the same language” (IMERE, 2024).

The Hindu Mystic Eknath Easwaran (1991) echoed Meister Eckhart and expanded upon the theme:

Theologians may quarrel, but the mystics speak the same language. They may use different words, but they are talking about the same reality. The language of mysticism is the language of love. It is the language of the heart, not the head. It is the language of experience, not of theory (p.22).

Mystics from all religions have said the same thing in different words. They have said that God is love, that we are all one with God, and that our true home is in God. They have said that we can experience God here and now, through love and compassion. The language of love is the language of the heart. It is the language of experience.

In Question 13, respondents reported that 92% of them “felt that God loved me personally,” 80% chose “I think it makes me want to be more loving towards others” 76% chose “I felt that God loved me unconditionally,” while 60% were “... surprised by how much God loves me.” No one chose the box that said, “I felt that God wouldn't love me unless I was more qualified somehow.”

Question 14 was an essay question: “In your own words, please describe the effects the experience had on you.” Respondents were encouraged to be as detailed as they wanted, such as explaining why they responded in a specific way. Respondents were also encouraged to provide additional feedback about any previous question and to be as detailed as possible, because even a point that may not appear as significant might well be. Respondents were also instructed to feel free to contact the author with additional comments via email. The responses are provided later in this Chapter.

Specific Technique Efficacies

The data revealed that, at least for this small population of 25 respondents, some techniques were more successful than others in eliciting Mystical experiences. When asked “If there was a particular technique used during the workshop that triggered your experience with God,” 64% chose the “Journaling with God” exercise, 60% chose guided meditation, 40% chose “something Ron or someone else said during the workshop,” and 24 % chose “hands-on healing.”

It was not expected to receive as much affirmation about the hands-on healing technique. It was particularly satisfying to learn that this technique was effective in about one in four cases, because it was the simplest technique compared to the others. Participants merely needed to stand behind another participant while laying their hands on their shoulders and repeating a simple

mantra. It did not take as much concentrated mental and emotional effort as the guided meditation or Journaling techniques. Because it was so simple, it was usually the first technique introduced at the workshops. It served as a good warm-up for the more difficult techniques.

This testimony from a recording of two workshop participants working together – one male and one female – supports the idea that it is efficacious to learn to trust and follow one's intuition while performing the hands-on healing technique:

Male Unificationist:

Martha was my partner. It's interesting when you do the mantra, because I know it helped to calm me down, and to open up a connection. I know when she had her hands on me she was saying (the mantra). I was sitting in the chair, but I found myself saying it (the mantra) to her. I was kind of repeating it, so that she may also feel some of it. But then I was thinking “Well, by me doing this, then I'm kind of not really receiving what God wants to give to me.” And I thought, “Oh.” So I stopped. And I started to focus on how she was helping me. A lot of times it's harder – sometimes it's easier to give than to receive. So I realized I had to stop that.

Female Unificationist:

I thought, when I had my hands on his shoulders, I kept feeling that I wanted to, you know, put my hands on his head, so that, I think that helped (him) to stop thinking. I wasn't sure if I should do that because I thought, “What if I'm doing it wrong” (Pappalardo, 2016).

This short testimony is revealing and quite significant for the following reasons:

- 1) During this exercise, the consciousness of participants often ascended to a place that is closer to God's consciousness. In that state, the intuitive faculty was heightened, and participants often received profound messages and insights.
- 2) He intuitively accepted that it was more important for him to just receive. Many people have a harder time receiving than giving.
- 3) The woman intuitively received that she should shift her hands from his shoulders to the top of his head. He said later that it was at that exact moment that he received the insight that he should stop thinking and just surrender to the exercise and focus on receiving what God was trying to give him.
- 4) Self-doubt: Even though the participants had been instructed to follow their intuition if they had a feeling that they should change their hand position to a different part of the body, the woman struggled with this. Nevertheless, she surrendered to her intuition, and by relocating her hands to the top of his head, she facilitated a very meaningful experience for him.

Three more testimonies from participants are presented below as examples of the type of experiences typically had at the workshops.

Hands-on Healing Testimonies (Testimonies were given by adults unless otherwise indicated. Names have been changed to protect privacy).

Male Unificationist:

Initially, this whole thing about the hands, I felt at peace, during the mantra. And then, it was electric on my fingers. It wasn't heat. I was like tingling. And then, I knew I was a conduit for God's love opening, and then I had a little stoppage thing where – and you (Ron) just brought it out – “Gosh, if I was a better person, the water would flow through better,” and so, that really struck me. Then, I reversed (He and his partners changed places. He sat down and his partner stood behind him), and I was sitting down, and I was so happy, at peace – right – and I could really feel that I was really floating – right – so, it's all about the energy, and God's love pouring in. Even though I hesitated thinking “Gosh, am I really qualified to be a conduit for You,” I like your comment (Ron) where “God's going to accept you,” and this should be a growing experience for me, doing this (Pappalardo, 2016).

In the author's experience, the most prevalent obstacle to having a Mystical experience is self-doubt related to low self-esteem. Many believe that they are not worthy or deserving to have such an experience. The success of the exercise does not depend on whether they are what others might judge as a sinner or a saint. To illustrate, we can compare two garden hoses. One is brand new, just purchased from the store, bright and shiny and unblemished. The second one has been in someone's yard for 20 years, covered with mud in places, weather-beaten, and faded from the sun. But on the inside, they are exactly the same. They are simply an open channel for water to flow through. By definition they are perfect conduits. That's all that matters.

God's opinion about this “I'm not good enough” obstacle or block to the Mystical experience was exemplified by this next testimony in which God spoke the words “*You are*

enough.” Notwithstanding his doubts about his own self-worth, this participant had a meaningful experience:

Female non-Unificationist and Male Unificationist:

Well, I had the experience of feeling – towards the end of the mantra, as it were – that we sort of melded. I felt like I didn’t know where Josh stopped, and I began. We sort of came – I got small... And I did have some words that I got. One was, (message for Josh) “You are loved. You are enough.” And for me, it was to “Live in joy. You are safe.” Thank you (Pappalardo, 2016).

Afterwards, the man testified that he sometimes entertained self-criticism in his mind, the idea that he was not good enough or was not doing enough for God.

It is significant as well as affirming that God often communicated the same message to the students/participants that he communicated to Jesus at the Jordan River: “And a voice came from heaven: ‘You are my Son, whom I love; with you I am well pleased’” (Mark 1:11). The author had this similar experience while performing hands-on healing in a Spiritualist church:

...because of my upbringing as a traditional Roman Catholic, and my experiences in the Unificationist movement, I possessed the belief that homosexuals were sinful and Satanic. I was rather afraid of them and avoided them as much as possible. One day I was working as a healer, inviting anyone who wanted to, to sit in my healing chair during Sunday service at the spiritualist church. A lesbian came towards me, and I could tell she was coming to sit in my chair, so I could not escape. As she approached my chair, I began to feel how much God loved her, and I got choked up. When I laid my hands on her and prayed over her God said to me “This is my beloved daughter, in whom I am well pleased.”

As a result of this experience, the author felt liberated and permitted to love every person no matter what their background or sexual orientation might be.

Guided Meditation

Meditation was a challenge for most people because of the tendency of the mind to wander while trying to focus. Especially for beginners, guided meditation is more efficacious than self-

practicing meditation because the voice of the guide helps keep the mind focused. Sixty percent chose this technique for their trigger.

As examples of the type of experiences that participants had using the guided meditation technique, three examples are presented here.

Meditation Testimonies

Female, Latter-Day Saint background, 16 years old:

Kristen (not her real name) was sitting all the way in the back, off to my right. When I looked over at her, I was taken aback. In front of her face was a rotating vortex, but it wasn't the size of a trumpet like I saw in front of some of the other participants, it was the size of a tuba! This thing was so huge it was as if she was completely immersed in spiritual energy. I knew that something amazing was going on with her, and I was dying to know what it was.

When the meditation finished, I stood up and returned to the front of the room.

I could tell that you guys had some kind of spiritual experience," I said gesturing to the ones I saw the little tornadoes in front of, "and Kristen, you had a lot of stuff going on, didn't you? All Kristen could do was nod her head. I could see that her face was drenched in tears. She was still gently sobbing.

I asked each person if they wanted to share what had happened to them during the meditation. Just as my vision had indicated, the two participants that didn't have the vortexes in front of their faces said that while they enjoyed the meditation because it made them feel relaxed, they didn't have any experience out of the ordinary. One of them said her mind kept wandering, thinking about other things and distracting her from getting deeper into the meditation. This is a common challenge for beginners.

The ones that had the little tornadoes in front of them did have spiritual experiences. One woman choked up as she described a visitation she had received from her deceased husband. Another had a deep realization about a particular question she had regarding her spiritual life path. I honestly can't remember what the others said.

Finally, I asked Kristen if she would like to share something. She was still crying a little bit, even though a few minutes had passed since the meditation ended. I'm so grateful for her willingness to share her experience because I think it can be beneficial to a lot of people.

“After I got relaxed into my chair on the beach, I looked down the beach to my left, and I saw Joshua (Ron’s deceased son) down there,” Kristen said. “So, I jumped out of my chair, ran down the beach as fast as I could, and tackle-hugged him. It was so great to feel his embrace. I just stayed there and talked with him. I told him how grateful I was to him for being my friend and for all he had done to help me.

He just held me for a moment and then he spoke to me. He told me ‘Actually, Kristen, you really shouldn’t be thanking me. There’s someone else who is really the one who helped you the most, and I’d like to introduce you to him.’ Then he pointed to his left. When I looked over there, there was this bright white light. It was coming from the person standing next to Josh. As I looked to see who it was, I knew right away that it was God.

I felt kind of nervous—I mean this was God! So, I told him I was sorry—sorry because I felt I had been kind of ignoring him and didn’t have a very good relationship with him. Then he said ‘No, I’m sorry. I’m sorry that you have had such a difficult childhood. I’m sorry for what you have had to go through; it was never my intention that it should be like that.’ Then he just hugged me, and I really started to cry then. I could actually feel him holding me. The feeling is just impossible to describe. I felt so accepted and loved—so loved! I didn’t want it to end.

Then he said, ‘I’ve placed certain people in your life to help you. Joshua is one of them, but there are others on earth also. They are there just for you, because I love you so much! I am here for you also, whenever you call out for me! I also want to encourage you. You have so much love inside your heart, I hope you will share it with others—give it out. If you do this, it will be very good for you’ (Pappalardo, 2012, pp 31-32).

Male Unificationist:

When I focused on the light, it started moving towards me. As it moved towards me, getting closer, it appeared as the outline of a human-like figure. At first, it was indistinct, and I couldn’t make out its features. But as it came closer, it began to become better defined. I had the distinct feeling that this was God, but I couldn’t see him very clearly. Then, as I focused on the face, the face took distinct form, and I was startled to find that the face of God was my face.

In trying to reflect on this experience with you (Ron), I believe I felt empowered to be Godlike, and forgiven of my past sins. I felt serene and at peace, separated from the nervousness that comes with embracing power (and the worry of a conscientious mind about abusing such power). I felt complete and at ease in myself in that empowerment.

I think God wanted to encourage me to stretch myself and have manifest confidence in myself and my choices, rather than worrying about getting everything “right.” I believe God is within, but I needed to work on that confidence that my desires are very aligned with His. And that in choosing and acting, God is living through me.

Male Unificationist (This testimony from a European workshop was delivered orally, video recorded, and then translated):

As you all know, my wife went to the spirit world two years ago, and the first year I felt really lonely. But more recently, I started to search for a way to communicate with her.

I even visited a spiritualist who lives near xxxxxxxx, and she told me that I would have been able to communicate with her because I had the gift of writing (scripture). But I did not believe her that much, because I have never been into writing. But now, when he (indicates Ron) said, after the meditation, "You all try to write", I put myself into it (pause, voice breaks) and I let my hand go. Some things now I do not understand, I wrote them so. My wife says... “You know how much I love you, and you have received my forgiveness (he cries), and how much Heavenly Father thinks of us, you know how much (is) His love for us.” I feel this is like assurance that I am not alone in this time, and she is close to me. Thank you.

His experience exemplified the fact that the prophetic experience was not limited to direct communication with God only. It could also involve communication with deceased loved ones; in his experience, it was his deceased wife who spoke to him after the meditation. In the case of Kristen in section a) above, Kristen first encountered the author’s deceased son Joshua, who then introduced her to God directly.

Journaling can be even more challenging than meditation. It requires honesty and sincerity. The participants must be emotionally present and allow themselves to be vulnerable. For some, this can be a daunting task. Nevertheless, at 64%, more respondents chose journaling as their trigger than any of the other techniques.

As examples of the type of experiences participants had using the journaling technique, three examples are presented here.

Journaling with God Testimonies

Female, former Unificationist:

March 31, 2015

Cary, NC

Dear Heavenly Mother,

Here we are at Caribou, writing the book. Funny how it's impossible to work at home. I have to go somewhere else, far from dirty dishes, laundry and hungry husbands. I can even type, sort of, almost, well... better anyway!

Right now, I'm getting the sense that you want me to share this moment with you, here at Caribou. Are you wanting to see everything, smell, feel, this afternoon here... like through me? Do you see it all? Of course, but how do I see everyone, every person here through your eyes? How do you see them through me?

Humm, that's pretty complicated. I have been thinking about this a lot lately. In the past, or among many Christian communities, there is a certain attitude of condescension towards "non-believers" or anyone outside a certain preferred faith. I know that even you, in your past as a missionary held a belief that there was your community and then there were the "outside people". A wall was built between you and everyone else. The love given to those outside was a conditional love – if they were saved, if they accepted certain religious doctrines, if they behaved a certain way. My love was held high and above, so unattainable and fearsome, few could dare to reach for it. This has been a big problem for me. I never wanted this and it has not been until now, until this new generation that I feel confident of this attitude being done away with for good.

When I look around at all the people in this coffee shop, I don't see... a Christian, an Atheist, a Jew, a Muslim... I just see a wonderful mix of people, personalities, all trying their best to get through this thing we call life. I have so much respect for every single one of them. They are all a reflection of me, you know. Can you imagine that? The girl with the blue hair, on the left table, in front of you. I can see that. I can relate. She wants to try something new. She has so much love and passion in her heart and sometimes it's just impossible to express it. So, she dyes her hair blue. Wish I could do that. And I do in a way, through her. I know how she feels. See?

I am not so mighty to not understand what it feels like to be her. I don't look at her and say... "Oh, my poor daughter! If only she..." No. No one needs to be pitied, especially not by me. I respect her. That's true love. To look at everyone here and see how amazing they are and how I am manifesting through them and their lives. This is kind of a radical thought.

I don't think most people, even those who are always trying to figure me out, can be easy with the notion that I am manifesting in every cell and pore of the human existence. The drug addict, the prostitute, the murderer even.

What? The murderer? What? ISIS? What?

You have stopped. Looking at these words, you don't like them. I get it. They are difficult and hard to understand. You wonder if you should publish this. Will you have to explain? I know you don't understand. You, everyone has been raised with the notion that God, me, is all about "good" and the attitude has always been "compassion".

Don't get me wrong. Compassion is wonderful and no doubt a way to live that can surely heal the world. And goodness – yes, that is what colors me – but I can still live in the heart of darkness, the most brutal and hateful. I can sit there, lying in wait, crouching in a corner, hoping for an opportunity to engage, to act. If not me... who? You wouldn't believe the things I have had to endure. You could not stand it. You would go mad and run away.

Okay, I see now.... kind of...

I don't expect you to understand. I am always growing, changing, evolving and even this concept is, in a way, in the process of being born. So, on one level, I don't fully understand it. All I know is that when I look at people, I feel no judgment, no pity, no regret. I just want them to seek happiness and, in that pursuit, they will connect to me, whether they know it or not. If I see someone living their life full of passion, love, and determination, I don't care if they acknowledge me or not. I am not interested in recognition.

But don't you like it that I write to you, that I think of you, God, and would you miss me if I stopped?

Oh... (She smiles) when it comes to you, yes, you got me. But that's because you have always known me and we have this friendship, but please don't think I love you more than the atheist across the room. It doesn't work that way. You are you and I love you as you are. The same for anyone else, even if they are blind to me or hate me... I meet them where they are and love them through that lens. Ok?

Yes, I see it. Don't worry. I am not jealous.

Love, Con

Good! Well, we better wrap it up. This was a good one. Hope you put it in the book (Pappalardo, 2015).

Male Unificationist :

Dear Heavenly Parent,

Thank you for this seminar. It has made our connection so much more intimate, even though I still feel like I'm swimming through a pool of molasses and in a stupor trying to connect to you consciously. I'm sorry for being so thick.

What Ron just said about connecting with his own children, I am continually shocked by the resentment and sense of being threatened that come back at me from my children.

I feel like I am completely unaware of the ways in which I threaten and hurt them. At this point they are all married, so in that sense I should certainly chill and just sit back and celebrate them and support them. Are you confident to take responsibility to reach out to the next generation without pressure and guidance from me to my children?

I understand that you have been working through history longing for three generations to be connected to you. So, I would hate to fail you somehow and let this opportunity slip away because of my own lack of discipline to train our children successfully. On the other hand it would be so much more joyful, just to love them and endorse them and let them live their own lives with confidence that they have received all that I can teach them and knowing that you will work with them and even more so with their children to guide them going forward.

I have done my best to organize our spirit world to support them and their families, too. Did I do it effectively or are there ways I could improve? Is it enough? I would sure relish some feedback and guidance. Let's be a team, with active give and take on the strategy level. In the time I have left on Earth, I could sure get a lot more done for you and the providence if we could develop that active give and take.

I'll stop here and listen.

My dear son, thank you for all your efforts and hard work. You sure have grown over the years, and now, as a grandfather, you are beginning to understand my heart more. Each person has their own course. There is only so much you can guide them. However, if you love them unconditionally, the time may come when they will ask you for guidance. When that happens, then they can receive it more. People like to discover things for themselves. No one likes to be pushed. When you give something to someone who is longing for it, it is not a push, it is a gift. You are quenching a thirst. That is the exact opposite. That is why I wait until people long for me. To reach out to someone before then is counterproductive. And even then, it is important to be measured on how much you give. If you keep giving after an appetite is satiated, it quickly can turn to pushing.

Focus on unconditional love. Celebrate your amazing children. Ask them how you can support them in their dreams. Love them with my love. Let's do this together.

Wow. That's a paradigm shift! Please help me hold onto it in the moment.

Please continue journaling. I will welcome the opportunity to dialogue with you in this way. Let's do great things together.

Female Second Generation Unificationist (17 years old):

This was a very powerful experience for me. A few weeks ago, I was reflecting on life and I realized there was a big hole in my heart. I thought that after a year of NGA activities – sharing my heart and letting out my pain – that I had cried it all out and the pain was gone. Unfortunately, a few weeks ago I searched for my heart again and found a deep hole there. I cried and I thought to myself that no one will ever be able to fill in this hole – not even God's love.

Today, the message from God was him telling me that he is aware that I hold so much in my heart, and that I need to fill in the hole with love – his love. It was just spot on to how I've been feeling, and I felt that this message was legit. I truly felt that God came to tell me this message. So afterwards I was crying and apologizing to God telling him that I'm sorry that I once felt like his love wouldn't be enough to fill in my hole. Now I'm more open to the idea that his love is enough.

Surprisingly to the author, 40% reported that they were triggered by something “Ron or someone else said during the workshop.” This was higher than expected.

Facilitating Additional Mystical Experiences

For 24% of respondents, the workshop encounter with God was the first Mystical experience of their lives. Especially in light of this fact, it is very significant that 88% reported that they had more Mystical experiences after the workshop. Ninety-six percent also reported that “My experience at the workshop helped me continue to make progress in my relationship with God.” It was gratifying to find that for many attendees, the workshop served as a beginning point for a continuing relationship with God.

Making People Better

Most respondents reported that their experience contributed to an improvement in their personal relationships. Seventy-six percent chose “It had a positive effect” on both their family and non-family relationships and 60% reported that it had a “positive effect on my work.” No one chose that “It had a negative effect” on relationships or work. Eighty percent chose “I think it made me want to be more loving towards others.” A good example of this phenomenon was the case of a teenage workshop participant who had a life-transformative Mystical experience during a guided meditation. She had been battling depression, practicing self-harm, and causing concern among friends and family over possible suicide. During the “beach” meditation, she had an encounter with God that was presented earlier in this report (p. 81-83).

A couple of weeks later, this experiencer was asked by this author if anything in her life had changed:

Oh, yeah, she said. Lots!

Can you give me an example?

Well, in the past, if I saw some geeky boy wearing a ridiculous shirt to school I might say something snarky or sarcastic to him. I *never* do that anymore. I’m a lot kinder and patient with people now (Ibid p. 33).

A number of people who have participated in this ministry's programs were considering suicide. As a result of their Mystical experience, they repented of the thought, and are still with us today (For another example of suicide mediation, see below concerning the testimony of E5).

Spiritual Procrastination

Even though the workshop Mystical experience is often reported as life-transformative, there is sometimes an unexpected effect. Experiencers will sometimes fail to follow up the experience by continuing to practice the techniques that have been shown to elicit them.

Surprisingly, some have declined the opportunity to continue even after having been directly invited and encouraged to by God.

E3 is an example of this phenomenon. He had an extraordinary dialogue with God through the “Journaling with God” exercise in which he expressed anxiety over his performance as a father, feeling like a failure for being unable to convince his children to follow some of his directions:

God: *Focus on unconditional love. Celebrate your amazing children. Ask them how you can support them in their dreams. Love them with my love. Let's do this together.*

E3: Wow. That's a paradigm shift! Please help me hold onto it in the moment.

God: *Please continue journaling. I will welcome the opportunity to dialogue with you in this way. Let's do great things together.*

The author remembers E3 saying afterwards that he felt liberated by the message. At the end of the message, we can see that God requested E3 continue practicing the journaling technique. When asked sometime later if he had done so, surprisingly, E3 replied that he had not. After encouraging him and making a couple of more suggestions, the author discovered that it was not until several years later that E3 made a further attempt at journaling, and was successful.

E17 similarly made no further attempts at journaling after receiving a beautiful loving message from God. Here is an excerpt:

*Slow your hand now, slow your heart now (Ron...my heart wants to explode with tears of joy and relief, even now as I'm typing this...) slow your mind now. It's all going to sort itself out as it all flows to the sea.
I am comfort, I am hope, I am calm.... I am the river.*

In this deeply moving and poetic message, God comforted the heart of E17. Nevertheless, when the author contacted him years later, E17 reported that he had made no further attempts at journaling. At the time of the workshop, E17 reported that he felt a large burden lifted from his heart; the author was surprised to find that he had not continued the communication.

The author must plead guilty to this tendency as well. After one particularly life-transformative Mystical experience, it took 20 years before finally beginning to practice something God suggested and requested in this communication. It was not even a very difficult thing God asked, simply a request for communication each morning and night:

We paused for a moment, as I tried to take in all he was saying. Then he spoke again.

Amazing how small your problems have become, isn't it? he said with a smile.

By this time, I was feeling many different emotions—beloved, calm, peaceful, liberated, amazed, in love. Yes, I felt in love! I had been a devout Catholic, an altar boy, and a missionary for many years, but I had never felt anything like this before. This was the day I really fell in love with God. I've been in love ever since. I felt so accepted, so known and understood. There wasn't a single person on earth that I felt as close to as this unseen Father who spoke to me through a doorway in my own heart. Again, I thought we were done, but he had one more thing to say.

By the way, I wish you would talk to me more often. Don't you think it's a good idea?

Yeah.

Can you do it every morning and every night? I can really help you if you do.

I'll try.

Okay.

It was over. I just sat there for a moment, amazed at what had happened. Fortunately, I had brought my journal with me, and I had been writing everything almost word for word as it unfolded (Pappalardo, 2012).

Theological Implications

Important theological implications arose from the collected data. Even though the survey respondents came from a wide variety of theological backgrounds across the spectrum of Christianity, and a few non-Christian backgrounds, they reported experiences that were strikingly similar in significant ways.

The experience may be colored by one's theological background. A case in point can be seen here in a journaling message received from a European graduate of the workshop experience, who continued the journaling technique long-term. The experiencer is a Unificationist, so God tailored his remarks to be relevant to and resonate with the experiencer's theological context. While much of the verbiage would perhaps sound esoteric or be incomprehensible to the average listener, it makes perfect sense in the context of Unificationist theology (Note here that this message has been translated, so the English may appear unusual in places):

In the last few days, at the end of this year 2014, I have had many internal conflicts about my mission. That is why this morning I invited Heavenly Father to come to me, wanting to discuss with him what I should do in the New Year 2015. He came to me in an atmosphere of peace. I was just enjoying his love, and then he started to speak to me:

You have many problems. You are going to your brothers and sisters seeking for advice and solutions. But who made you? Who knows your problems better than I do? Why don't you come directly to me? I don't only know the answer but also the remedy.

I know you are very busy during the day, but try to find at least half an hour, make a little space in a corner of your heart, ask me to come (I cannot come if you don't want), put away all your worries and tell me sincerely about your situation. Can you trust me? But please after that don't go away, wait for my answer. Send away all your thoughts and make room in your mind for what I want to tell you. Be also ready to hear things that are unusual for some other people. It is not necessary to tell others about our talk, follow your intuition. It can remain a secret between us. I like to have some secrets with my beloved children.

I see you are very busy looking for guidance in the Holy Scriptures. This is good. But you are forgetting that I am the one who gave those words to the prophets and great teachers of the past. I taught them all the wise words that they passed on. But many followers of the World Religions believe more in their Religious Teachers than in me. Sometimes they even worship them.

Actually I have been longing to speak directly with you and on the foundation that True Parents made, this time has come. I called you to learn the Divine Principles, to teach them, but also to live them in your daily life. Not just to make a library of the past and present Holy Scriptures and to forget about their purpose.

I was very happy when you were teaching about the Growth Period. This is essential for me. Many years ago you met True Parents, you received the Blessing at the top of the Growth Stage where Adam and Eve fell, and walked together with True Parents for more than 30 years in the Completion Stage. The TP fulfilled their mission and my son, Sun Myung Moon, came to meet me in the Spiritual World. Now I'm waiting patiently for you to find the courage to enter the Perfection Stage. This means you'll be in my direct dominion. Very few people had such courage until now. I hope you can do it as soon as possible. I'm waiting for you. Or are you maybe waiting for somebody to tell you when you are perfect and to give you permission to come to me? Don't worry if you have some problems, I have more problems than you. Please don't wait anymore. We can grow together and build my kingdom together, or even better our kingdom, because we are one family.

Please don't wait anymore. I have lived long enough almost alone, with just a few people. Now is the time to realize the Kingdom of Heaven. Don't forget, our kingdom begins in our hearts, and nobody can destroy it, unless you make the mistake of leaving me (Pappalardo, 2013).

In this next case, a woman's theological background served as an impediment to a Mystical experience. This participant shut down her encounter with God because her Roman Catholic upbringing conditioned her to self-identify as a "sinner" unworthy of having such an experience:

After one of the sessions, a husband approached me. He asked me if I would be willing to speak to his wife. We had just concluded an exercise called the Sun Meditation which is designed to activate the inherent connection between God and each participant. She was upset about something that happened – or rather, something that didn't happen – during the meditation.

"The meditation was going well," she said to me. "I could see the Light of God, and could sense his presence. Then the light began coming down, out of the sky, and moving toward me. It came closer and closer. Then, just when it was about to touch me, it stopped."

Puzzled, I asked her if she had any idea why it never reached her. With a sense of sadness she said, "I blocked it." She was quite upset about this. She knew that the presence of God had been there, and that she was about to have a direct personal experience with her Heavenly Parent. She could tell that the energy that was moving towards her possessed Divine Love. Yet, just as the moment was about to happen, she had shut down the encounter, and she didn't understand why.

I felt so much compassion for her, and was saddened by the fact that she had gotten so close without making the final connection. I asked her to take a deep breath, get calm, and ask herself if she could discover inside herself the reason why she had

blocked the experience. I asked her to ask her heart. Sometimes when I do this, I will ask the person to put their hand on their heart and then ask the question.

The woman got quiet and closed her eyes. In just a few seconds she opened her eyes with an expression that revealed to me that she had found the answer. “I blocked the experience of receiving the love of God because I didn’t think I deserved it. I believed that I wasn’t worthy of it.”

When she said this, I started to choke up. Even though she was a middle-aged woman, I could feel her heart as if she were a young child. The Spirit of God welled up inside my heart and I embraced her. As I tenderly held her, I began to speak, feeling that I was speaking for God to his daughter. I told her how precious she was to God, how much he loved her and appreciated everything about her. I could feel the energy of God’s love flowing through me to her, and she could feel it also. She began to cry, and I’m sure this was a profound and important experience for her.

Nevertheless, I was saddened by the fact that she didn’t feel worthy to receive love directly from her Heavenly Parent and had blocked the experience.

... Having worked with hundreds of people in this way, I have found that the number one block to having a Mystical experience is this one – a sense of unworthiness. Many people feel that they are in some way just not good enough for God to love them (Pappalardo, 2015, p. 54-55).

God is a God of Unconditional Love

Traditionally, Christianity has placed a high degree of emphasis on sin, salvation, and fear of damnation in Hell. In these experienter responses, we did not find any evidence of a God of judgment and punishment. Instead, we found a God of unconditional love and support. When given the opportunity to check a box that said “I felt that God wouldn’t love me unless I was more qualified somehow,” no one chose it. Instead, 92% chose “I felt that God loved me personally,” while 60% were “surprised by how much God loves me.”

The sentiment was epitomized by E16:

After so many years of believing (at least in part) that God loved me in proportion to what I did, what I accomplished, how many spiritual children I brought, how much money I donated, it felt like ‘pure rain,’ ‘pure beauty’ to experience my Heavenly Father who actually wanted nothing from me, just that I would receive from Him a vast, warm, love emanating from His embrace.

E12 adds to this finding:

Growing up in the Catholic Church... It seems to me that God was a punishing God and I wanted to have nothing to do with this entity (if it even existed). ... I found God at Ron's workshop.

The second day came and everybody around me was having spiritual experiences, but not me. Nothing. At some point on the second day, I remember thinking, "Here we go again, nothing is happening for me, I am not good enough for God to pay attention to me." I regretted coming to the workshop. I felt so deflated.

That's when something happened. Ron was guiding us through a guided meditation... It's really hard to describe what happened and how I felt. I wasn't in the room and I couldn't hear Ron's voice anymore. I was bathed in light, a blinding white light. I heard nothing but felt a presence. I suddenly felt a love that cannot be described in human words. It felt almost too much for me. This presence was love itself.

I was completely baffled by what happened and really surprised! Finally, God knows I exist and HE loves ME!

Challenging Traditional Theology

This brings us to another finding; in many cases, the Mystical experience was quite different from what experiencers might have expected given their theological backgrounds. While 32% chose "It strengthened my belief in my faith traditions teachings," a far greater number experienced the opposite. Sixty percent chose "It affirmed that some of the things I had suspected about God were true, even though these were not part of my traditional religious education." Sixteen percent said, "The experience was different from what I would have expected given my theological background" while 24% chose "It made me question my belief in some of my faith tradition's teachings," and 24% went so far as to choose "It contradicted some of my faith tradition's teachings."

Revealing the Heart of God: Experiencer Testimonies

Perhaps the reason why these Mystical experiencers were so moved is because their encounters with God revealed not just the presence of God, but the feelings God had towards each

person. There were hints to the nature of God's Heart in scripture, which were affirmed by these experiences. For example, in the *Parable of the Prodigal Son*, Jesus tells us that the father, when catching a glimpse of his approaching son, runs to him: “But while he was still a long way off, his father saw him and was filled with compassion for him; he ran to his son, threw his arms around him and kissed him” (Luke 15:20).

Then there is this from the Muslim scriptures:

... if he comes one span nearer to Me, I go one cubit nearer to him; and if he comes one cubit nearer to Me, I go a distance of two outstretched arms nearer to him; and if he comes to Me walking, I go to him running [Bukhari, Tawhid 16, 35; Muslim, Dhikr 2, (2675), Tawba 1, (2675)].

It appears that this longing for reunion and relationship with his children is powerfully embedded deep within the heart of God. We saw more hints of it in these selected excerpts from the testimonies of the experiencers. Except for the first testimony below, which was provided by a workshop participant, the rest are excerpts from experiencer responses to question #14 of the survey. Complete responses are recorded in Appendix D:

He came to me in an atmosphere of peace. I was just enjoying his love, and then he started to speak to me:

... who made you? Who knows your problems better than I do? Why don't you come directly to me?

... make a little space in a corner of your heart, ask me to come (I cannot come if you don't want)... Can you trust me?

... I have been longing to speak directly with you...

...I'm waiting patiently for you to find the courage...

... please don't wait anymore. I have lived long enough almost alone, with just a few people.”

E3: *... you are beginning to understand my heart more...*

Please continue journaling. I will welcome the opportunity to dialogue with you...

As I shared above, I didn't continue. I left her (God) hanging... I imagine that she almost went crazy... hoping for me to write another message, and each day being so hurt when I didn't... I sincerely apologized for taking so long to respond. Heavenly Mother just brushed it aside and said:

Don't worry about what you missed by not beginning your journaling earlier. I was dropping a seed. It had to germinate.

E5: (She had been planning to commit suicide).

God is a personal God. He loves uniquely, intimately, and with great care and detail.

I know you want to come to me. I want you to come as well. But it isn't your time yet. I know your life is hard and you are lonely. This is why I brought Ron into your life. He understands me the same way you do so I brought him into your life so that you would not feel as alone...

I remember just crying and feeling so grateful for everything that had transpired. He didn't tell me some version of “get over yourself.”

... He carried me out of my dire situation and then he gave me someone who had experience with the exact thing I was struggling with. These were gifts... and experiences I carry with me to this day. I will... be forever grateful to him (Ron) and to God for bringing us together. I no longer feel like suicide is the answer and have found ways to work through difficulties that come my way.

E6: ... I had a deep experience with God, a spiritual experience, humbling, a presence. I didn't know what to expect... deeply personal and inspiring...

E7: Ron was leading the portal meditation... I knew God would be there. As I opened the door, I felt God's presence, all the love and warmth...

E8: The very first time I began journaling with God, the message I received was personal to me and one of overwhelming love and acceptance for who I am, as I am. God responded with a sense of playfulness, lightheartedness, and love. I felt to the core of my being how much God loves me. Tears welled up as I read the message that had flowed from my pen to the paper.

If you spend time with me every day, I promise I will convey my messages and love through you to many people in many places – just wherever you are. Relax and trust me. Play, have fun and enjoy life as you wish. That makes me most happy.

E9: Ron's workshop surprised me greatly... The workshops were a launching pad that set my life on an unexpected utter fascination for knowing the nature of God and experiencing the depths of God's love. It is the first time I fell in love with God. It is the first experience of feeling like I got in touch with an unfathomable wisdom and clarity. Journaling to God brought me to tears, and as I felt God inviting me to live a life of boldness and freedom, I believe I have touched a truth of the beauty and magnificence of God's love that has me coming back for more. And my journey

to know God more fully and truly comes from the pure desire that has never left me since its awakening at Ron's workshops.

E10: I was instructed to "feel the love of God" and try to be one with the feeling. "Could I feel God," I thought. Doubt crept into my mind, but another voice was saying "you can do this." After the meditation... we were instructed to write in our journals as if we were talking to our best friend... I read what I had written. It was profound. I learned things about myself that I did not know. Things were explained to me that I had not voiced before but only dwelled in my heart. I pleaded to myself that I would continue to seek out God when I returned home. And I did.

After the six years from the time of the workshop, I have been faithfully writing letters to God and getting answers to some of my most puzzling questions.

... I have come to learn and feel that God is ever present and forever surprising me with His/Her attention to my desires if they are pure and sincere. I have filled up four notebooks of my conversations with God and working on a 5th. I hope to publish them some day to encourage others to believe that it's possible to communicate with God just like I did in the workshop.

E11: He led us in meditation and I had a personal experience with God. When the meditation was complete, I felt so much of God's love I was crying tears of joy. I also started meditating as a regular practice after that. It has helped me work through life challenges and bring me closer to God.

E12: ... I remember him guiding us to a beach and sitting on a chair at the beach, and that's all I remember. It's really hard to describe what happened and how I felt. I wasn't in the room and I couldn't hear Ron's voice anymore. I was bathed in light, a blinding white light. I heard nothing but felt a presence. I suddenly felt a love that cannot be described in human words. It felt almost too much for me. This presence was love itself.

I knew without a doubt it was God's presence. I felt so immensely loved! I don't know how long the experience lasted but I suddenly felt my body begin lifting off from my chair! I started crying and the tears were just flowing.

... I wanted to stay with this incredible light and love! When I opened my eyes my cheeks were wet from my tears and I was sobbing... I was completely baffled by what happened and really surprised! Finally, God knows I exist and HE loves ME!

... I always felt I wasn't good enough for God to love me but he took the time to show me his love and to talk to me directly. I knew for certain after that experience that God is always with me and that his love for me will never change.

E14: I felt God's presence in such a clear and overwhelming way. It was as numerous facts that I had already known to be true coming together in a much bigger 3-dimensional picture. So many moving pieces coalescing to one vision about God's presence in this country. I had never heard anything put together quite

like that. But again, it wasn't just the facts lining up one after another. It was the feeling of experiencing an unmistakable presence and “heart” behind those facts.

E15: My first memory of that weekend is a feeling of “home” ...

During the guided meditation, I had a profound experience with God as my parent. My loving, forgiving, supportive, embracing... Parent. No judgment, no expectations. Just love. For the first time in several years... I felt SAFE.

... it felt like “pure rain,” “pure beauty” to experience my Heavenly Father who actually wanted nothing from me, just that I would receive him, a vast, warm, love emanating from His embrace.

E17: *I'm no mystery; As simple as pie – with vanilla ice cream. Warm me up and enjoy! Slow your hand now, slow your heart now (Ron... my heart wants to explode with tears of joy and relief, even now as I am typing this...) slow your mind now. It's all going to sort itself out...*

E18: Ron did not know me nor I him. However, somehow, he began speaking words from God to me. The main part of the message was, “Never forget how much I love you.” That came as a shock to me. I felt it was a direct answer from God to my prayer... two years prior. The effect was huge because prior to that I thought God did not want to hear from me.

I considered a raging river between myself and God with no way to cross over. I only prayed out of desperation from time to time hoping He might be listening. But through my experience it was as though God crossed the river. Not me. He wanted a relationship with me. I was filled with happiness. The next morning, I laid out all my shortcomings in prayer. Everything I could think of throughout my life. I felt God was with me.

The main effect on my life is that I now know that God wants me to pray to him. There is nothing which I cannot tell Him.

E20: ... nine years later, just last weekend, as I watched the recording of Ron Pappalardo's workshop, I had a Mystical experience with God, as I realized that my Heavenly Parent has been trying to reach me with the same message of love through Ron's workshop, other mediums, and in numerous other ways! I didn't feel any judgment for not realizing this early, but like the prodigal son, I only felt the embrace of love from God, my Heavenly Parent... in my survey of Ron's workshop I did not emphasize that it was life transforming, but now I realize that transformation can occur years later and lead to an encounter with God!

E21: ... In journaling with God I discovered clearly that God knows me and loves me unconditionally. These days I try to understand God's point of view even more than I used to. God is loving, wanting to guide and support, not wanting to judge

and punish. It is challenging to look at others from God's point of view with this knowledge in mind, but it is the only true way to perceive others...

E23: When I started journaling and just wrote and wrote, a very strong sentence entered my mind. I felt the response coming straight from God. S/he said, you talk too much, loud and clear. It just made me laugh because it is so true and it would never have been something I said to myself. It was funny and straight to the point and absolutely right. I felt God knows me really well and sometimes is amused by me. This was definitely unexpected.

E25: Consistently when I do (journaling) in the setting Ron creates, I feel God's love for me. It is a tangible feeling. Often as real as water on my skin. That is very important to me because I was raised an atheist. There is no logic that could get me to believe in God, only the skin touch experience.

God told me the reason they (my parents) had conceived me was because He wanted me. That He loved me an extreme amount and had planned for me for years and worked to bring my parents together. They were from completely different parts of the world. He really continued about how much He wanted me, exactly me. I felt so joyful.

Characteristics of God Revealed through the Experiencers' Testimonies

It is significant to note that there were several characteristics of these experiences that were repeated over and over through many of the testimonies.

- 1) Many of the experiencers were surprised. That surprise was oftentimes related to discovering that God knew them personally and uniquely.
- 2) Experiencers discovered that God loves them uniquely, personally, and unconditionally. The magnitude of the Love was usually surprising and sometimes almost overwhelming in its power.
- 3) God was humble. The humility was often surprising and noted for its absolute sincerity.

St. Mother Teresa noted it as well:

I can understand the greatness of God but I cannot understand his humility. It becomes so clear in him being in love with each one of us separately and completely. It is as if there is no one but me in the world. He loves me so much (St. Mother Teresa, 2006).

It can be seen in the journaling message from E7.

- 4) God was benevolent. His presence conveyed a sense that he had the highest good of each person at heart.
- 5) God encouraged. Like a coach or a parent, he infused experiencers with confidence and courage.
- 6) God was patient. Even after being ignored for years, he was always available and enthusiastic about resuming a relationship.
- 7) God was learning and growing through his interactions with human beings. This concept seemed similar to that posited by Alfred North Whitehead in his *process philosophy* (Simons, 2013).

This concept was epitomized in E7's journaling message below (Bold emphasis added).

Dearest ones,

If only you knew, could understand, how much I love you. You are everything to me. Why else would I have my roses smell as sweet, and the colors? All for you to enjoy. An apple, an orange, perfectly measured to fit your hand, my love!

Through war and famine, in all the tragedy, I am here, always, beside you, in the dark, in your shadow, I lie and wait for you to call, cry out. But will you? Can you see me? Can you hear me? Please look up from your pain, hear my voice in the wind, the rustling of the leaves in autumn, the hush of the snow on a blue street, my love, like a blanket falls softly. But does it fall on deaf ears? Can you hear me? Can you feel me?

Search for me in every blade of grass, and a moonlit night, when the wind catches the stars and brings the trees to dance. It's all for you! Can't you see? All for you, my loved ones! Beauty is not necessary for my world to function. Beauty is my gift to you, beauty is love -- my rainbow, my promise, all to remind you of me.

What now, my loves? Can we go on? Can my love, can beauty save the world from hate and fear? Can we survive this? Can I live without you? I could but do I want to? No. No. No. No. It makes no sense without you. I make no sense without you. Can't you see? Some days I think – I have had enough – that I want to walk away, that you will be happier without me. But no! I can't.

In you, I see hope and love, and despite all the mistakes, from both of us, my love will not allow me to leave you. Love is more powerful than I am. Did you know

that? I bow to love, love is my God. Are you surprised? Think about it, dear ones. Love is greater than I am.

But if I was to leave, can I trust you to love one another? Can you love as I love? I know you can but are you willing? Can you live in joy? Can you cast off fear? Can you fill the world with love and beauty? Can I trust you to be rid of anger? Can you love without motive? Can you live life as I had intended? I wanted you to be full of joy and happiness.

I don't need to be worshiped! I need a relationship with you, my child. Can we work together? All I ever wanted was a relationship, a love relationship with you. Is it too much to ask? Does it scare you? I am scared, too. I don't want to be hurt – I don't want to hurt you! So many misunderstandings in the past.

Can we start again? No churches, notebooks, no religious leaders, just you and me. Can you imagine? I can help you, even in the tiniest details of your life. You can ask me anything! When your heart is broken, come to me. My heart has been broken so many times, and yet here I am, ready to love again. I can help you to heal and to be courageous in the face of fear.

Forget all the mistakes, all the past hurt, hurt you have been victims to but also forgive yourself for all the pain you have caused. Yes. Forgive. It is all that will save you and all of mankind. Forgiveness is the highest expression of love. I have forgiven you. Forgive all those who fear and all you hold anger towards. I have forgiven all and everything.

Can you forgive?

Can you forgive me?

Proposal for Further Research

Data collected demonstrated that the techniques described in this dissertation project are effective at eliciting Mystical experiences. It is hoped that others will add to the research by attempting to replicate the results. For those who would make such an attempt, an essential caveat must be mentioned. Replicating spiritual phenomena is more difficult than replicating phenomena that involve exclusively material elements. For example, water will boil at 212°F no matter who is conducting the exercise. That person might be a great saint, under the influence of alcohol, might fall asleep during the experiment, or might not even be present during the transformation from liquid to gas. In all of these cases, the water will still boil.

That is not the case with these spiritual phenomena. Prayerfulness, humility, and pure intentions have important effects on the outcome of the exercises. The outcome is a result of a partnership between the participants and the Holy Spirit.

Another point that would be worthy of more research regards the 12% of experiencers who reported that the Mystical experience they had at the workshop was a one-time event. Further research would be helpful in order to gain understanding of why some participants have no subsequent Mystical experiences, as opposed to the vast majority of experiencers who continued to have more, reporting that their workshop experience contributed to further developing their relationship with God.

Chapter 6

Recommendation and Conclusion

It is the recommendation and hope of the author that this report will lead to the implementation of these techniques in the field. In particular, the Unification movement is well suited for this type of curriculum. Theologically, Unificationism encourages what Rev. Moon referred to as “authentic spiritual communication with the spirit of God” (Moon, 1985). Unificationism is well positioned from a cultural standpoint as well; members are accustomed to learning and participating in workshop settings. In addition, the Unification movement has seminaries in Korea and the United States, as well as other educational institutions which would be a good fit for this curriculum.

In the author’s view, this project strongly demonstrates the efficacy of using specific techniques to successfully elicit Mystical experiences, and that there are significant beneficial aftereffects to the experiencers. The central feature of these Divine encounters is the powerfully transformative nature of having a direct personal experience with the unconditional Love of God.

Teachers of spiritual formation, such as Fr. Henry Nouwen, refer to this phenomenon as a movement from the head to the heart. Jesus referred to it as being “born again.” The founder of the Unification Theological Seminary (now HJI) the Rev. Sun Myung Moon also exhorted his followers to seek a direct encounter with God: “Your opportunity to live on earth is at most 70 to 100 years, but it is important that in that time your body and mind are united into one and you experience the love of God” (Moon, 1977). In his commencement address to the 1985 graduating class, he said: “I have also endeavored for this campus to be a place where the students can develop deep personal faith and authentic spiritual communication with the Spirit of God” (Moon, 1985).

If ministers and religious educators adopt these techniques and replicate them, we might see a revitalization of the spiritual vitality of our congregants, students, and society at large. In the spirit of Charles Finney, Henry Nouwen, Jesus, and Sun Myung Moon, it is hoped that ministry and education will focus more on the heart than the head, more on religious experience than just book knowledge alone.

References

- Andersen, M.M., Schjoedt, U., Nielbo, K.L., & Sørensen, J.G. (2014). Mystical experience in the lab. *Method & Theory in the Study of Religion*, 26, 217-245.
- Barrett, F. S., Johnson, M. W., & Griffiths, R. R. (2015). Validation of the revised mystical experience questionnaire in experimental sessions with psilocybin. *Journal of Psychopharmacology*, 29(11), 1182-1190.
- Beale, S. (2013). 22 Biblical words for sin and what they teach us. *Catholic Exchange*. [22 Biblical Words for Sin and What They Teach Us \(catholicexchange.com\)](https://catholicexchange.com/22-biblical-words-for-sin-and-what-they-teach-us/) (Accessed August 29, 2024).
- Blum, J. N. (2009). *Mystical experience: Interpretation and comparison* [Doctoral dissertation, University of Pennsylvania] (Order No. 3414211). Available from ProQuest Central Essentials. (604116495). Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/mystical-experience-interpretation-comparison/docview/604116495/se-2> .
- Clark, N. (2012). *Divine moments: Ordinary people having spiritually transformative experiences*. 1st World Publishing.
- Dell'Angela, T. (2002, Nov 24). Strong medicine; The 'vision quest' has all but vanished as a rite of passage among the lakota sioux, but an aurora youth leader is showing that the ordeal of fasting and prayer can still redirect young lives: [Chicagoland final edition]. *Chicago Tribune*. Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/newspapers/strong-medicine-vision-quest-has-all-vanished-as/docview/419724147/se-2> (Accessed August 28, 2024)
- Descartes, R. (1637). *Discourse on the method*.
- Doyle, A. C. (1926). *The History of spiritualism*. George H. Doran Company.
- Eckhart, M. (1260-1328) *The essential sermons, commentaries, treatises, and defense*. Paulist Press. (Translation and introduction by Edmund College, O.S.A., Bernard McGinn.) p.248.
- Easwaran, E., (1991). *Seeing with the eyes of love*. Nilgiri Press, p.22.
- Eldredge, B. [Lectio Divina | Loyola Press](https://www.loyolapress.com/lectio-divina/) (Accessed August 6, 2024)
- Finney, C. (1858). Christian consciousness, a witness for god. *The oberlin evangelist*. June 23, 1858.
- Finney, C. (1876). *Autobiography of charles g. finney*. Adansonia Press. p.7.
- Forem, Jack. (2012) *Transcendental meditation: Maharishi mahesh yogi and the science of creative intelligence*. Hay House.

- Frankl, V. E. (1946). *Man's search for meaning*. Beacon Press.
- Gandhi, M.K. (1931), Gandhiji in Lancashire. *Young India: A weekly journal*, Volume 13, Number 42, 1931 October 15. Edited by M. K. Gandhi, p. 310, Column 1, Ahmedabad, India. (Young India archive at gandhiheritageportal.org).
- Granqvist, P., Fredrikson, M., Unge, P., Hagenfeldt, A., Valind, S., Larhammar, D., & Larsson, M. (2005). Sensed presence and mystical experiences are predicted by suggestibility, not by the application of transcranial weak complex magnetic fields. *Neuroscience letters*, 379(1), 1-6.
- Hood Jr, R. W. (1977). Eliciting mystical states of consciousness with semistructured nature experiences. *Journal for the scientific study of religion*, 155-163.
- IMERE (Institute for Mystical Experience Research and Education). Mystical Experience of Meister Eckhart. [Mystical Experience of Meister Eckhart | IMERE.org](https://www.imere.org) (Accessed October 28, 2024).
- International Association for Near Death Studies, Inc. [IANDS - the most reliable source of information on NDEs](https://www.iannds.org).
- James, W. (2019). *The varieties of religious experience*. Indo-European Publishing.
- Julian, O. N. (2022). *Revelations of divine love*. Czechia: DigiCat.
- Katz, S. T. (1978). Language, epistemology, and mysticism. *Mysticism and philosophical analysis*, 22-74. London: Sheldon Press.
- Maij, D. L., van Elk, M., & Schjoedt, U. (2019). The role of alcohol in expectancy-driven mystical experiences: a pre-registered field study using placebo brain stimulation. *Religion, brain & behavior*, 9(2), 108-125.
- Manning, P. R. (2020). Teaching contemplatively for unified hearts and communities. *Religious education Journal*. Volume 115, No. 3, p. 278-290.
- Moon, S. M. (1977). *The spirit world and physical world*, February 6, 1977.
- Moon, S. M. (1985). Unification Theological Seminary commencement address.
- Moon, S. M. (1996). *Exposition of the divine principle*. The Holy Spirit Association for the Unification of World Christianity.
- Moody, R. (1975). *Life after life*. Mockingbird Books.
- New International Version Bible*. (2011). Zondervan.
- [NewsweekBeliefnet Poll Results - Beliefnet](https://www.beliefnet.com). (Accessed June 25, 2024).

- Nouwen, H. (2010). *Spiritual formation: Following the movements of the spirit*. Harper Collins. p. xvi.
- Pappalardo, R. (2010). *Reconciled by the light: the after-death letters from a teen suicide*. Lulu Press. p.76,79.
- Pappalardo, R. (2012) *Reconciled by the light book II. Spirit messages from a teen suicide: Adventures of a psychic medium*. CreateSpace Books.
- Pappalardo, R. (2013). *Messages from god: 21st century prophets speak for a new age*. CreateSpace Books.
- Pappalardo, R., Pappalardo, C. (2015). *Experiences with god. Stories about mystics: A guidebook to your own divine encounter*. CreateSpace Books.
- Pappalardo, R. (2016). *The spirit world: How spirits live and interact with us: A guide to spiritual development*. 5 DVD set, Disc 1.
- Patterson, R. B. (2002). *Writing your spiritual autobiography*. Thomas More Publishing.
- Rohr, R. (2020) "At-one-ment, Not atonement."
[At-one-ment, Not Atonement: Breaking Up Old Logic — Center for Action and Contemplation \(cac.org\)](http://cac.org) (Accessed 7/13/2020).
- Sacerdote, P. (1977). Applications of hypnotically elicited mystical states to the treatment of physical and emotional pain. *International Journal of Clinical and Experimental Hypnosis*, 25(4), 309-324.
- Saint John of the Cross. (2016). *Ascent of mount carmel*. Martino Fine Books.
- Saint Mother Teresa. (2006). *Mother teresa: Her essential wisdom*. Carol Kelly-Gangi, Ed. Barnes & Noble. p. 12.
- Simons, P. (2015). Alfred north whitehead's process and reality. *Topoi*, 34(1), 297-305. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11245-013-9161-3>.
- Smith, H. (1991). *The world's religions: Our great wisdom traditions*. New York: Harper Collins. 1991.
- [The 4 Steps Of Lectio Divina - Practical Catholic Living](#) (Accessed August 6, 2024).
- Welch, S. (2022). A pragmatic piety: Experience, uncertainty, and action in charles g. finney's evangelical revivalism. *Open theology*, 8(1), 284-296. <https://doi.org/10.1515/opth-2022-0210>.

[William Walk Sacred. "Vision Quest." http://www.native-americans-online.com/native-american-vision.html.](http://www.native-americans-online.com/native-american-vision.html)

Yaden, D. B., Eichstaedt, J. C., Schwartz, H. A., Kern, M. L., Le Nguyen, K. D., et al. (2016). The language of ineffability: Linguistic analysis of mystical experiences. *Psychology of religion and spirituality*. The American Psychological Association (APA) Division 36. Washington, DC. Vol. 8, No. 3, p. 244.

Appendix A

Email to Workshop Participants

Date: Mon, 10 June 2024 16:22:31 -0400

Subject: Did you have an experience with God at my workshop?

Dear Friend,

Many people report that they had an experience with God while attending one of my workshops.

Are you one of them?

The reason I am asking is because I am currently writing my dissertation to complete my Dr. of Ministry degree.

I have been asked to report about the “God experiences” people have had at my programs, so that others may learn from them. I can't think of anything more important than helping others have a direct experience with God!

If you are one of these people, and you haven't done so already, please just reply “Yes,” and I will get back to you with more information.

Thank you so much for helping with this important project.

Sincerely,

Ron Pappalardo

PS By the way, the next workshop will be held on September 7th and 8th in Albuquerque NM. For more info click here:

<https://www.ronpappalardo.com/coming-soon>

Appendix B

Survey Participant Consent Form

Ron Pappalardo is a Doctorate candidate at HJ International Graduate School for Peace and Public Leadership. This research project under these provisions is approved for the Doctoral of Ministry degree at HJ International.

Title of the D.Min project: The God Effect: Exploring the Long Term Influence of Elicited Mystical Experiences

Consent to take part in research:

- I..... voluntarily agree to participate in this research study.
- I understand that even if I agree to participate now, I can withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any question without any consequences of any kind.
- I understand that I can withdraw permission to use data from my survey within two weeks after I submit the survey, in which case the material will be deleted.
- I have had the purpose and nature of the study explained to me in writing and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the study.
- I understand that I will not benefit directly from participating in this research.
- I understand that all information I provide for this study will be treated confidentially and only available to the researcher as identifiable data during the research process.
- I understand that in any report on the results of this research, my identity will remain anonymous.
- This will be done by changing my name and disguising any details of my survey which may reveal my identity or the identity of the people I speak about.
- I understand that disguised extracts from my survey may be quoted in the researcher's Doctor of Ministry dissertation, published papers, and conference presentations.

Participant - "All of my questions and concerns about this study have been addressed. I choose, voluntarily, to participate in this research project. I certify that I am at least 18 years of age."

Signature of participant -----

Date:

Signature of researcher -----

Date:

Appendix C

Survey Results

1. Religious Background that best describes you

25 responses

2. Gender assigned at birth.

25 responses

3. Age
25 responses

4. You have reported that you had a Mystical experience during one of my programs. Was this the first time you had an experience where God communicated something to you?

25 responses

5. What describes you best?

25 responses

6. Was this a one-time encounter with God, or did you have more experiences after the workshop?
25 responses

7. If there was a particular technique used during the workshop that triggered your experience with God, please check the boxes. You may check more than one.
25 responses

8. What effect has this experience had on you? Please check ALL That Apply to you. (n = 25)

9. What about your progress in your relationship with God?

25 responses

- My experience at the workshop had no effect on continuing my progress in my relationship with God.
- My experience at the workshop helped me continue to make progress in my relationship with God.
- My experience at the workshop made it more difficult for me to continue to make progress in my relationship with God.

10. What about relationships? Check as many as you like: (n = 25)

11. Did anything surprise you? Was there something about your experience that you did not expect?
25 responses

12. Did your experience have any effect on your beliefs or theology? You may choose more than one. (n = 25)

13. What about Love? Check ALL that apply to you. (n = 25)

Appendix D

Experiencer Testimonies

14. In your own words, please describe the effects the experience had on you. For example, if you answered that it was something you did not expect or surprised you, tell me why? You can tell me more about any of the answers you gave in the survey.

Please be as detailed as you can. Even a tiny detail that you might not think is very important could be very important for this research. Your answer can be as long or as short as you like. Please especially focus on your feelings, speaking from your heart:

(Optional) Feel free to also add any additional comments you would like to make about your Mystical experience, your experience at the workshop, or Ron Pappalardo's ministry. Your answer can be as long or as short as you like:

Experiencer #1

Dear Ron Pappalardo,

My history with you and Connie goes back several years. It is one that I feel has made a pivotal change in my life. I say this remembering my very first workshop that I attended at your lovely home. During that session I indeed felt a spiritual connection with our Lord.

That experience led me to realize that through clairaudience and clairvoyance that I was indeed receiving spiritual messages which would open my mind to believe in my gifts.

As I spent more time with your group sessions, I became more familiar with mediumship and realized that I also had a psychic ability with the use of psychometry and reading people in person.

Another session that I had with you was learning how to journal our spiritual meditations. This learning activity changed my life in that it opened my communications with my spiritual guide, those in spirit and more importantly, all my messages from Christ. Journaling also helped me to track my medical diagnosis and explained my health problems in ways that doctors could not. I was amazed how accurate and concise my messages were and at times coincided word for word with my doctors' words years later.

This journaling led me to grow my Faith, Hope and Love so much so that I recorded all my meditations into a book titled 'Dear Lord, I Am Listening.' My book was published on Amazon. Though I had achieved three different careers including my own business throughout my lifetime, I felt this book was written by the Holy Spirit and was by far the most significant accomplishment of my lifetime. I also will never forget that if it wasn't for Ron teaching me

these valuable spiritual practices of prayer/meditation, that it most likely would not have been possible.

My mediumship and meditation have helped me to provide insight and direction for family members as well as those who have been left grieving from the loss of their loved ones. It has given me great strength to accept my incurable diseases of Scleroderma, Heart Disease and Parkinsons' as well as a stroke with acceptance, Comfort and Peace. All this would not have been possible without my Faith, Belief, and Trust in my Lord that grew from my loving meditations and messages from my Lord.

I continue to want to serve God in every way possible and would like to continue to provide Peace and Comfort to those who are grieving. Every day, I look for ways to see Him in all things.

I am and will always be forever grateful to Ron for opening this door to my spiritual world and to one of eternal Peace and Love.

Your daughter in Christ,

XXXX

Experiencer #2

I had a significant experience with using the words from Matthew 3:17 in the way suggested by Ron. He asked us to say those words by adapting them to feel that our voice was God's voice talking to ourselves. Indeed, I had a profound emotion of feeling God's love for myself. It was liberating and helped me to really believe that God loves me in a most personal way. This contributed significantly to liberating me from self-loathing which had crippled me and made it difficult to free myself completely from an addictive behavior which I had been seeking freedom from. To this day I remain free from that behavior and feel liberated from this self-deprecation.

The following day when we came to attend the second day of the 2-day seminar, I felt very strongly the spirit of Father Moon coming into the room. The memory of this remains clear in my mind and heart.

Experiencer #3

For my first 40 years in our movement, I never had what I would consider direct communication with God. I prayed regularly and consistently, and sometimes I would have strong intuitions that turned out to be accurate. I could see God working regularly in situations around me, and on a few occasions, I felt God's spirit and was moved to tears. But even though I was originally interested in parapsychology, I honestly never had what I would consider "communication" with any spiritual beings, people or angels, nor did I have any actual conversation with God. Nor had I ever had any visions. The closest I came to some kind of spiritual communication would be when I was writing songs. On occasion, I would hear a melody, or sometimes, part of a lyric would come to me.

In 2015 that began to change. A friend of mine had had a good experience attending a seminar by Ron Pappalardo, an Associate Pastor in the Spiritualist Church, who was introducing people to various exercises to learn to communicate with God. My wife and I drove from Columbia Maryland to Columbus Ohio for a weekend workshop August 1 – 2 of that year. For two days, Ron guided us through numerous exercises, and meditations to try and communicate with God, or to at least become more in touch with our own spiritual senses. I found it quite frustrating. All around me, many of the participants were having legitimate and inspiring experiences. In my case, much to my own disappointment, nothing seemed to have any effect on me. However, at the end of the workshop, he tried one final exercise, which he called "journaling". It simply involved meditating for a bit, and then writing a sincere note from my heart to God. Once we finished that, we were then to begin writing a note back to ourselves from God. Ron instructed, "Just write whatever comes into your heart". Here is my first journal with God, dated 8/2/15. I transcribed God's "voice" in bold italics:

Dear Heavenly Parent.

Thank you for this seminar. It has made our connection so much more intimate, even though I still feel like I'm swimming through a pool of molasses and in a stupor trying to connect to you consciously. I'm sorry for being so thick.

What Ron just said about connecting with his own children, I am continually shocked by the resentment and sense of threatenedness that come back at me from my children...

I feel like I am completely unaware of the ways in which I threaten and hurt them. At this point they are all married, so in that sense I should certainly chill and just sit back and celebrate them and support them. Are you confident to take responsibility to reach out to the next generation without pressure and guidance from me to my children?

I understand that you have been working through history longing for three generations to be connected to you. So, I would hate to fail you somehow and let this opportunity slip away because of my own lack of discipline to train our children successfully. On the other hand, it would be so much more joyful, just to love them and endorse them and let them live their own

lives with confidence that they have received all that I can teach them and knowing that you will work with them and even more so with their children to guide them going forward.

I have done my best to organize our spirit world to support them and their families too. Did I do it effectively or are there ways I could improve? Is it enough? I would sure relish some feedback and guidance. Let's be a team, with active give and take on the strategy level. In the time I have left on Earth, I could sure get a lot more done for you and the providence if we could develop that active give and take.

I'll stop here and listen.

My dear son, thank you for all your efforts and hard work. You sure have grown over the years, and now, as a grandfather, you are beginning to understand my heart more. Each person has their own course. There is only so much you can guide them. However, if you love them unconditionally, the time may come when they will ask you for guidance. When that happens, then they can receive it more. People like to discover things for themselves. No one likes to be pushed. When you give something to someone who is longing for it, it is not a push, it is a gift. You are quenching a thirst. That is the exact opposite. That is why I wait until people long for me. To reach out to someone before then is counterproductive. And even then, it is important to be measured on how much you give. If you keep giving after an appetite is satiated, it quickly can turn to pushing.

Focus on unconditional love. Celebrate your amazing children. Ask them how you can support them in their dreams. Love them with my love. Let's do this together.

Wow. That's a paradigm shift! Please help me hold onto it in the moment.

Please continue journaling. I will welcome the opportunity to dialogue with you in this way. Let's do great things together.

When I showed Ron what I had written, he was very excited. He said "this is clearly in a different voice. I believe this is actually God speaking to you."

I thought about it for a few days, and finally decided, "No, I'm not going to play games and pretend I'm actually talking to God." And I filed it away...

It took me until July 13, 2022, before I reached the point where I could, in faith and confidence, begin a sincere and trusting dialogue with God.

Shortly after I began my journaling, I gained a deep sense of how incredibly vulnerable Heavenly Mother's heart truly is. I realized, to my great shock and distress, that my first journal message, at that weekend workshop with Ron Pappalardo, was the fruit of 63 years of her tears, longing for this prodigal son to return home. She had to be so careful and measured, so as not to chase me away. She could not reveal how much her heart was in stress, hoping that I wouldn't run away. She finished that message casually, with:

“Please continue journaling. I will welcome the opportunity to dialogue with you in this way. Let’s do great things together.”

But as I shared above, I didn’t continue. I left her hanging. Her long-lost child, finally home for 1 day, then gone. I imagine that she almost went crazy, each day, hoping for me to write another message, and each day being so hurt when I didn’t...

Eleven days after I started journaling in earnest, it hit me, just how much I had hurt Heavenly Mother’s beautiful heart, by turning my back on Her. On July 24, 2022, I sincerely apologized for taking so long to respond. Heavenly Mother just brushed it aside and said:

“Don’t worry about what you missed by not beginning your journaling earlier. I was dropping a seed. It had to germinate.”

God is Amazing.

Experiencer #5

Ron gave his first workshop in Barrytown, NY, which is where I was living at the time. I’m not sure of the year but I believe it was January of 2014. I know it was winter because it snowed during the first night of the workshop.

For a big portion of my life, I had felt suicidal on occasion mostly stemming from not feeling my value. I felt invisible, unimportant, and like a total failure as a human being. As you can imagine, the pain I carried around from feeling this way was heavy and extreme. A few months before Ron came to Barrytown to give his workshop, I was alone in the chapel at UTS in the dark. I often went there to pray because it was quiet and, in the dark, I felt I could be more honest with God. This one particular evening I told God that I was done living and that I was coming to Him that night. I wasn’t sure how I was going to do it but I had decided that that night I would commit suicide. And then I heard the train whistle. Down by the river, a fairly short walk from the chapel building, there is a space on the railroad tracks where there is no fence to prevent someone from going onto the tracks. It’s actually a road and the space is there so cars can cross the tracks and continue to drive on the road. I remember thinking, "If I leave the building and go to the left, I will be going in the direction of the railroad tracks. If I go to the right, that will be going towards home. I decided I would go to the left but, as I went through the door at the back of the chapel, it was like everything went blank. The only thing I remember was sort of "waking up" walking on the road by the big grey/white barn near Harvest House. My intention had been to go left towards the tracks but here I was, inexplicably, to the "right direction" and almost home.

I don’t remember changing my mind and I don’t remember walking the distance from the chapel to this point by the barn. I was so shocked that this had happened that I stopped and stood in the road. At this point in the road, I could see into the hallway of the apartment where I lived with my husband, and our daughter. I looked there now as I stood in the road and I watched for a

moment. They moved about the apartment in the glow of the hall light. Then the oddest thing happened. I was suddenly in the hallway outside our bedroom and then it was morning and I was sitting on the edge of the bed looking out the window. I don't remember anything in between standing on the road and sitting on the edge of the bed in the morning light. As I sat there, feeling like my consciousness had definitely been played with, I asked God what had happened and why. Why and how was I prevented from going down on the tracks? And why did I jump from road, to bed, to morning and not experience or remember anything in between? I also remember that, through this whole experience, God had said something to me but I couldn't, for the life of me, recall what it was that He said to me. I asked Him several times over the course of the next few days and weeks but, for His own reasons at the time, He would not tell me what He had said to me.

A few weeks after this experience, our neighbor at the time, Henry Christopher, told us about someone called Ron Pappalardo who was coming to Barrytown to speak about his experience with his son's suicide. I didn't know who Ron was, at the time, and I knew nothing about his life in the church or his family but when I heard that his son had committed suicide and that he would be talking about that AND Ron's tireless effort to understand what had happened, why, and how to communicate with his son. I knew I had to go and hear what Ron had to say. I was teetering on the edge of suicide myself and I was looking for help understanding this and any possible solutions from wherever I could get it. My heart went out to Ron and his family and the anguish they must still be feeling but I was so grateful for the hope that was offered. I remember being very serious at that workshop. I felt my life hanging in the balance. I listened intently in every session and prayerfully completed every exercise. In between sessions, I would spend time on my own going over the sessions and their lessons for me.

Right before the end of the workshop Ron gave a few readings to a few of the participants. He came to me and said, "God loves you so much", which is something I needed to hear. It had snowed the night before and Ron then said to me, "Do you see the snow? God wants me to tell you that just like each snowflake is unique, He loves you uniquely." This meant so much to me to hear this but how could I know for sure that Ron was really relaying a message from God to me? The next thing he said to me was the confirmation I was looking for. Ron said, "Do you like to make people laugh?" I said yes. Then he asked my husband, who was sitting next to me, if this was true and he also said "yes". Then Ron said, "Well, God wants you to know that you make Him laugh." I sat there kind of unable to speak. Years before, as part of my effort to make a relationship with God, I had had the following conversation with God:

Me: What do you like about me?"

God: "You make me laugh."

The answer came so clearly and easily that I thought I had made it up so I decided to test God by saying,

God: "I'm sure many people make you laugh."

His response came just as clearly and quickly as before.

God: "Not the way *you* do."

I had only told my husband about this experience and written about it in my journal. So, when Ron told me that God wanted me to know that I make Him laugh, it was confirmation for me that it was God speaking to me through Ron.

After the workshop, I went home and asked God one more time, "What did you say to me on that night when I was ready to take my life?" This time I finally got an answer. God said to me, "I know you want to come to me. I want you to come as well. But it isn't your time yet. I know your life is hard and you are lonely. This is why I brought Ron into your life. He understands me the same way you do so I brought him into your life so that you would not feel as alone. This will help you until we can be together more fully." I remember just crying and feeling so grateful for everything that had transpired. God is a personal God. He loves uniquely, intimately, and with great care and detail. He didn't tell me some version of "get over yourself." First, he carried me out of my dire situation and then he gave me someone who had experience with the exact thing I was struggling with. These were gifts, spiritual gifts, and experiences I carry with me to this day. I have had many, many such spiritual experiences that form the foundation of my *knowing* God exists, not simply *believing*. I will never forget the experience I had with Ron in this workshop and will be forever grateful to him and to God for bringing us together. I no longer feel like suicide is the answer and have found ways to work through difficulties that come my way.

Experiencer #6

My first experience with Ron Pappalardo and his workshops was from many years ago at a First Blessing Workshop in Los Angeles. There were only 11 participants. I had a deep experience with God, a spiritual experience, humbling, a presence. I didn't know what to expect but am always searching for experiences with God. That first workshop was deeply personal and inspiring and so I have gone to four other workshops with Ron. There were some good experiences in the last workshop in Albuquerque, New Mexico, especially in the journaling with God exercise. I haven't been able to duplicate that experience on my own but the workshops have a higher atmosphere that helps more people have experiences on their own with God and the high spirit world.

Ron has also done 74 zoom sessions beginning during the pandemic with people searching for experiences with God. I have participated in 71 of them. No other group gives you the experience of people sharing how they have broken through, sharing their techniques, dreams, visions, explorations. He has had many quest speakers of exceptional quality sharing their visions, near death experiences, flashes of God's love, journaling messages, books read, etc. I look forward to these sessions also.

I recommend Ron's workshops and also the zoom sessions. He also does private sessions with people searching for breakthroughs in their personal lives. These are spiritual readings. I had one private session with Ron and although he wasn't able to contact the spirits in spirit world I was seeking it was still a valuable experience.

Ron has a deep, personal and sincere relationship with God and you feel he wants you to experience that also. That is why he does the workshops and the zoom meetings. He wants you to feel as he has; you can feel his love and unselfish desire. He is a magnet because of his sincerity.

Thank you, Ron for all you have given to all of us!

Experiencer #7

In the Fall of 2018, I attended a workshop at Morning Garden in Gloucester, Mass.

Ron was leading the Portal Meditation. As he was guiding us through this field of flowers and towards a tower, I veered into a forest and it was Fall (my favorite time of year). It was a glorious scene and I was drawn to this small cottage in the woods. I knew God would be there. As I opened the door, I felt God's presence, all the love and warmth but someone else was with Father God. It was my father who had been killed when I was 7 years old. Strangely, I did not cry but was surprised and happy to see that he was with God and not lost in the spirit world (since I was thinking this for a long time).

The experience was short but very powerful and now when I think of my father, I remember this experience.

Experiencer #8

Dear Ron,

The "Journaling with God" activity had the most profound impact on me when I attended your workshop at the NextGen Academy farm in California in 2017. It was surprising because I wasn't expecting to receive something so deep and life changing for myself. The workshop was mainly for our young adult NGA participants, and I was there to support them.

I've had a long-time love for God since I was a child. Then, it was a simple faith and God was merely synonymous with Love. I would say the journaling activity helped me to return to and embrace this simple childlike faith. It launched me into a deeper personal relationship with God.

Previously, in my journaling, I would often use what I knew based on teachings I've learned to figure things out. It was a good practice at the time. This new practice became more of a conversation, where I stopped talking and began listening and receiving the most profound answers to my questions. The very first time I began journaling with God, the message I received was personal to me and one of overwhelming love and acceptance for who I am, as I am. God responded with a sense of playfulness, lightheartedness, and love. I felt to the core of my being how much God loves me. Tears welled up as I read the message that had flowed from my pen to the paper.

This short excerpt is what launched me into a new practice of receiving direct messages from God. "If you spend time with me every day, I promise I will convey my messages and love through you to many people in many places—just wherever you are. Relax and trust me. Play, have fun and enjoy life as you wish. That makes me most happy."

These words were so liberating for me. Being someone who would try so hard to be more and do more yet never quite measure up. I made a commitment to spend time with God every day. I have journals filled with simple yet profound wisdom that nurture my soul newly every time I read the words. I returned to a simple faith and trust in Spirit. I began a daily meditation practice which allows me to touch the divine essence within me. I attend silent retreats once or twice a year where I immerse in the quiet, in nature, and receive wisdom from the inner core of my being. I experience the Presence of God deep within my heart. I've experienced another reality, underneath the surface of this physical reality. "Love" doesn't capture it well enough. And amidst the challenges and scary things going on in the world, I feel at peace most of the time. I see so much beauty everywhere. God continually shows me that I am enough—we all are enough.

I am deeply thankful.

All the best,

XXXXX

Experiencer #9

Ron's workshops surprised me greatly. I felt his teachings on the nature of God's love and our ability to communicate with God were more compelling than anything else I had heard before. The workshops were a launching pad that set my life on an unexpected utter fascination for knowing the nature of God and experiencing the depths of God's love. It is the first time I fell in love with God. It is the first experience of feeling like I got in touch with an unfathomable wisdom and clarity. Journaling to God brought me to tears, and as I felt God inviting me to live a life of boldness and freedom, I believe I have touched a truth of the beauty and magnificence of God's love that has me coming back for more. And my journey to know God more fully and truly comes from a pure desire that has never left me since its awakening at Ron's workshops.

When I was planning to give a testimony at a sexual wholeness conference of 200 people, I was told not to share about how I watched gay porn. This was a bit of a relief as I was scared about revealing that so publicly anyways. Upon receiving communication during Ron's workshop, and being brought to tears by God's encouragement to be bold and free, I pushed back on the workshop coordinators' request to refrain from sharing my sexual story, which included same-sex attraction. Standing on that stage, I have never felt so set free. Here I am, sharing the most terrifying part of my story, knowing that this will mean I cannot hide anymore, and I felt so emboldened, like God had my back, standing right behind me. I remember I wrote out my testimony, but some words spilled out of my mouth that I had not planned to say. And these would be the words people would come up to me later and thank me for sharing them. These words, I suspect, were from a higher authority, as they brought a greater level of wisdom and emotive ferocity. This moment changed my life, as I found that being authentic and vulnerable were powerful, but to also have God behind me, there really are no words to describe my experience.

Experiencer #10

It is not very often that I am involved in a workshop (and I have been to many) that had such a life-changing effect on my life. Was it because I had no expectations to be affected or was it because I wanted to have an experience and invested myself 100% into the process? Regardless of the reason it did happen, I cannot deny it.

Rev. Ron had a very special workshop agenda that utilized his skills of organization, personal experiences and a wonderful ability to engender confidence in his participants. I took the plunge right away when he had us meditate. I had meditated before but in this group setting it took on a different sense of purpose. I was meditating not only for myself but for the group. Rev. Ron, I felt was giving 100% so I should do the same. The meditation was deeper than I had experienced before. In a short period, I was floating in a sea of unconsciousness that gave me confidence to go deeper. I was instructed to “feel the love of God” and try to be one with the feeling. “Could I feel God”, I thought. Doubt crept into my mind, but another voice was saying “you can do this”. After the meditation was over, we were instructed to write in our journals as if we were talking to our best friend but to God. Rev. Ron emphasized that God wants to communicate with you but you have to be open hearted and honest with yourself that you come with not judgement of yourself or anything else.

I truly believed that I could hear from God. Once long ago as a missionary during an all-night prayer vigil I heard from God. In the last hour before daybreak I heard God say, “I love you”. But this was after 6 hours of repenting. I wrote and explained this experience to God and how I wanted it again. As I wrote once again confidence rose up in my spirit. It was not intellectual confidence but a feeling that someone was waiting like a mother to embrace me. I decided to write on the top of the page “Dear xxxxx”. My thoughts were the same as I wrote the words that came to me. It was my voice in my head but as I wrote it was something that I would not say, it was God using my thoughts to speak to me. I feel as if I was translating a message and putting it into my own words.

I filled up a page in my journal. When the journaling session was over, I read what I had written. It was profound. I learned things about myself that I did not know. Things were explained to me that I had not voiced before but only dwelled in my heart. I pleaded to myself that I would continue to seek out God when I returned home. And I did.

After the six years from the time of the workshop I have been faithfully writing letters to God and getting answers to some of my most puzzling questions. Sometimes it comes immediately as a “Dear xxxxx” reply and sometimes it comes in daily life as a discovery. I have come to learn and feel that God is ever present and forever surprising me with His/Her attention to my desires if they are pure and sincere. I have filled up four notebooks of my conversations with God and working on a 5th. I hope to publish them someday to encourage others to believe that it’s possible to communicate with God just like I did in the workshop.

Sincerely,

xxxxxx xxxxx

Experiencer #11

I went to a retreat with Ron in 2015. He led us in meditation and I had a personal experience with God. When the meditation was complete, I felt so much of God’s love I was crying tears of joy. I also started meditating as a regular practice after that. It has helped me work through life challenges and bring me closer to God.

I have also had many deep experiences through the journaling technique. Here is a message I received on March 23, 2021.

Dearest ones,

If only you knew, could understand, how much I love you. You are everything to me. Why else would I have my roses smell as sweet, and the colors? All for you to enjoy. An apple, an orange, perfectly measured to fit your hand, my love!

Through war and famine, in all the tragedy, I am here, always, beside you, in the dark, in your shadow, I lie and wait for you to call, cry out. But will you? Can you see me? Can you hear me? Please look up from your pain, hear my voice in the wind, the rustling of the leaves in autumn, the hush of the snow on a blue street, my love, like a blanket falls softly. But does it fall on deaf ears? Can you hear me? Can you feel me?

Search for me in every blade of grass, and a moonlit night, when the wind catches the stars and brings the trees to dance. It’s all for you! Can’t you see? All for you, my loved ones! Beauty is not necessary for my world to function. Beauty is my gift to you, beauty is love -- my rainbow, my promise, all to remind you of me.

What now, my loves? Can we go on? Can my love, can beauty save the world from hate and fear? Can we survive this? Can I live without you? I could but do I want to? No. No. No. No. It makes no sense without you. I make no sense without you. Can’t you see? Some

days I think – I have had enough – that I want to walk away, that you will be happier without me. But no! I can't.

In you, I see hope and love, and despite all the mistakes, from both of us, my love will not allow me to leave you. Love is more powerful than I am. Did you know that? I bow to love, love is my God. Are you surprised? Think about it, dear ones. Love is greater than I am.

But if I was to leave, can I trust you to love one another? Can you love as I love? I know you can but are you willing? Can you live in joy? Can you cast off fear? Can you fill the world with love and beauty? Can I trust you to be rid of anger? Can you love without motive? Can you live life as I had intended? I wanted you to be full of joy and happiness.

I don't need to be worshiped! I need a relationship with you, my child. Can we work together? All I ever wanted was a relationship, a love relationship with you. Is it too much to ask? Does it scare you? I am scared, too. I don't want to be hurt – I don't want to hurt you! So many misunderstandings in the past.

Can we start again? No churches, notebooks, no religious leaders, just you and me. Can you imagine? I can help you, even in the tiniest details of your life. You can ask me anything! When your heart is broken, come to me. My heart has been broken so many times, and yet here I am, ready to love again. I can help you to heal and to be courageous in the face of fear.

Forget all the mistakes, all the past hurt, hurt you have been victims to but also forgive yourself for all the pain you have caused. Yes. Forgive. It is all that will save you and all of mankind. Forgiveness is the highest expression of love. I have forgiven you. Forgive all those who fear and all you hold anger towards. I have forgiven all and everything.

Can you forgive?

Can you forgive me?

Experiencer #12

My experience with God

I participated in Ron's workshop in Montreal, Quebec, I believe in 2014. What I knew about God was from religions. Growing up in the Catholic Church I did not pay attention to God at all. My mother became a widow at the age of 28 with four very young children and every time something bad happened she would say: "What did I do to God to deserve this?". She would blame God for all her misery. It seems to me that God was a punishing God and I wanted to have nothing to do with this entity (if it even existed).

I joined the Unification Church in my late 20's. The Church painted a different picture of what God could be and it intrigued me. But after many years in the UC, I began to stray. To be honest, I searched all my life for this "father" figure and never found it. I found God at Ron's workshop.

The workshop was a two-day weekend at the Unification Church center. At that time, my family was no longer going to Sunday Service and we did not have much contact with members. A Church member who knew my husband well contacted us about the workshop and encouraged us to come. I was reluctant to go but we ended up going anyway; myself, my husband and our oldest son.

The first day was great and many people were having wonderful spiritual experiences, the give and take with members was very uplifting and Ron was just fascinating to listen to. The second day came and everybody around me was having spiritual experiences, but not me. Nothing. At some point on the second day, I remember thinking, "Here we go again, nothing is happening for me, I am not good enough for God to pay attention to me." I regretted coming to the workshop. I felt so deflated.

That's when something happened. Ron was guiding us through a guided meditation. I remember him guiding us to a beach and sitting on a chair at the beach, and that's all I remember. It's really hard to describe what happened and how I felt. I wasn't in the room and I couldn't hear Ron's voice anymore. I was bathed in light, a blinding white light. I heard nothing but felt a presence. I suddenly felt a love that cannot be described in human words. It felt almost too much for me. This presence was love itself.

I knew without a doubt it was God's presence. I felt so immensely loved! I don't know how long the experience lasted but I suddenly felt my body begin lifting off from my chair! I started crying and the tears were just flowing. Then I heard my son talking to me and asking me if I was ok.

Once I heard my son's voice, I came back to earth. I didn't want to! I wanted to stay with this incredible light and love! When I opened my eyes, my cheeks were wet from my tears and I was sobbing. My son and my husband were sitting on each side of me and they looked worried. My son told me he was worried because I was crying but also because I was starting to lift off from my chair. He also felt himself starting to lift off from his own chair! I was completely baffled by what happened and really surprised! Finally, God knows I exist and HE loves ME!

Ron then asked if anyone would like to share their experience. I did. I recounted what happened in front of everybody with extreme enthusiasm and went back to sit on my chair. I was walking on clouds! Ron was still at the front of the room but was looking at me funny. He suddenly came to me and kind of kneeled in front of me and started to tell me things. And his eyes were looking at me very intently. I don't remember everything he said but I remember him telling me; "Do you remember when you were a child you would open things up because you wanted to know how they were made (such as a broken tv or radio); then he said "I put this sense of curiosity in you". And I was like, what? What is he talking about? I realized it wasn't Ron talking to me but God.

As a child, I was very curious and used to try to fix radios and electrical stuff. To this day, I am still very inquisitive and need to know the reasons for everything. Ron wouldn't have known that. He also said: "Remember that you are God's daughter in whom He is well pleased." This sentence stayed with me to this day. My son also noticed the change in Ron's eyes. After a few minutes, it was over and Ron was back to himself. I wonder if Ron was aware of what was going on but it was "freakingly" amazing to be honest. I always felt I wasn't good enough for God to love me but He took the time to show me His love and to talk to me directly. I knew for certain after that experience that God is always with me and that His love for me will never change.

I have spiritual experiences from time to time and I know they are signs from God. My relationship with God is an ongoing process and my love for Him is ever growing. I have since then discovered the realms of Angels, Archangels, Guardian Angel, and spirit guides through my practice of meditation and Reiki. I believe this experience was the starting point of my ongoing spiritual journey.

I will forever be grateful to Ron for coming to Montreal and to bring this workshop to us, and to my husband's friend for inviting us. And we received so much love from Ron and his wife Connie. I could feel their love for God and they helped many people on that day to reconnect with our creator. Thank you!

Experiencer #13

In 2020 when the Black Lives Matter movement arose, my casual comment in a house conversation on something related to BLM became a big deal among my family – my husband from Dr Congo (Democratic Republic of the Congo), and our son, then 19 years old. To them my innocent casual comment like "all lives matter" was against the rights of black people whose long-time socially oppressed agony was finally about to have a voice. I was surprised by their reaction and was confused. I sometimes even felt as if I was being punished for not being born black. I thought we love all people regardless of race. But this BLM movement became an emotional sensation outside and inside of the house. I was looking for help in my prayers.

One night I remembered Ron's guided meditation and practiced it. During the meditation, a person's face came up in my mind's vision. Without any expectation, I emailed her a short message. Next day she emailed me with an attached file of 3 or 4 pages on not only BLM, but also the background of the black race in social and Unification Church history. She is one of the earliest UC members in the USA, a professional counselor with a PhD. Reading the whole document helped me.

I clearly understood that I was ignorant. After a few days, I asked her if I could share the document with my friends who heard about it from me and were interested in knowing more about it. She said yes. It was not long after that I heard the document went viral among our church community nationwide. One day I heard on a zoom meeting that one elder American member who held local leadership in one state expressed his regret about the past UC history containing traces of some racism. He was almost crying while talking.

Experiencer #14

My mystical experience came when Ron was giving a presentation about how God has been working all through the founding of America. All of a sudden I was taken back to that night when I first heard a teaching called Divine Principle. I felt God's presence in such a clear and overwhelming way. It was as numerous facts that I had already known to be true coming together in a much bigger 3 dimensional picture. So many moving pieces coalescing to one vision about God's presence in this country. I had never heard anything put together quite like that. But again it wasn't just the facts lining up one after another. It was the feeling of experiencing an unmistakable presence and “heart” behind those facts. I have at various times in my life experienced the feeling of God. And although different each time always the fingerprints start to become somewhat familiar to me each time. This was surely one of the more explosive times to experience that. And a “plus side” was that after this experience, I feel my mind and heart and curiosity were wide open to studying more about America. And whenever I feel that feeling about ANY subject, I typically want more and more of it and never want it to end

One of the best things about Ron’s ministry imo is that he always seems to be able to channel a very healing spirit and energy wherever he goes. Both myself and my wife have taken part in such experiences like that and been rejuvenated in many ways through the years with him. Personally I can never forget one time when Ron was visiting and presenting a seminar at our house. During the break I noticed Ron stopped to chat with my neighbor Gary who had never met Ron but was just walking out to his car.

I don't know how he does it but within one-or two-minutes Ron seemed to uncover and cut to the heart of Gary’s lifelong pain. Previous to this time I had been minimally aware that Gary has had a difficult life. Just to see how much Ron was able to help this person in such a spontaneous and “on the fly” style made my heart smile. So I snapped a picture of it. (see attached). I can tell it has made a difference in the last few years in Gary’s life. These days, anyone who has been blessed with a genuine gift of helping to heal others is something that this world can never get enough of!

Ron Pappalardo (Left), ministering to my next-door neighbor, Gary.

Experiencer #16

I first attended the workshop led by Ron and Connie Pappalardo on their first foray beyond the East Coast to take their message to the rest of the country. An old friend contacted me and my husband to see if the Pappalardos could stay at our home when they would be leading the workshop over the weekend at a nearby UC property.

I had mixed feelings about attending for several reasons:

1. The event would be held at a UC property. At that time, I was coming off of a very difficult experience in the UC and trying hard to distance myself. I had been appointed to [a leadership position] by Rev. Moon directly. By the time of his Seung Hwa (passing) I was engaged in a moral dilemma. I had observed many practices at the highest level of leadership which did not sit right with me, and it became clear that ... these practices

would continue, be expanded going forward, and that I would have no voice or power to change them.

I submitted my resignation with a simple letter to HQ. "I will be eternally grateful that Rev. Moon trusted me to serve in a critical leadership role for America. At this time, my internal moral compass will no longer allow me to serve." No one contacted me after that.

2. My spiritual life was in shambles. While (my husband) and I continued to participate with each other in a daily prayer condition for our family, anyone we knew in need of prayer, and "unity in the True Family," it was just an exercise in speaking words....my heart was hurt, and I just couldn't find the power within me to reach out to God.
3. I did not know Ron and Connie well....and I wasn't sure I spiritually trusted them. In the end, I felt since they were staying with us....it would be rude not to attend the workshop...and so I went and so did my husband. That workshop became a turning point for me. It completely reawakened my spirit, helped me to connect with God directly and helped me to start on a healing journey, a path that I am still on today.

My first memory of that weekend...is a feeling of "home." I felt comfortable spiritually in a way I had not felt comfortable in a very long time. While I was inspired by the lectures...it was the spiritual exercises that were most profound to me. Everything felt "right," "true," and my heart was at peace. During the guided meditation, I had a profound experience with God as my parent. My loving, forgiving, supportive, embracing.... Parent. No judgement, no expectations. Just love. For the first time in several years...I felt SAFE.

After so many years of believing (at least in part) that God loved me in proportion to what I did, what I accomplished, how many spiritual children I brought, how much money I donated, it felt like "pure rain," "pure beauty" to experience my Heavenly Father who actually wanted nothing from me, just that I would receive from Him, a vast, warm, love emanating from His embrace. The deepest part of the workshop for me was near the end when Ron played a tape of a medium and Rev. Moon. On the tape, she asked him..."what do you think about the deification of True Parents and True Family?"

His response (paraphrased) was "I never meant that to happen. If it's (messiahship) meant to be in me, it's meant to be in you. I don't care if history doesn't remember me.... I only care that our members and all people in the world are able to make deep relationships with God" I only care about salvation! restoration! These were things I lived for as a member of the Unification Church. I cried almost violently when I heard this....a snorting, choking, heaving, cry that shook me to the core. When I came back to myself, I was on the floor and my husband was holding me.

Yes! I was right!! Rev. Moon was who I thought that he was all along. Not a "Messiah" in robes and crowns, but a "messiah" like me who had actually come to be an example, to help me to change and grow toward God, and a person who desperately longed and lived for the restoration of EVERY person.... every child of God on the earth.

I left that day with new hope in my heart. Hope that I was a more "spiritual person" than I thought, and even more than hope – a conviction that I could access a personal relationship with God and that this relationship with God was something that I could actually bequeath to my children and grandchildren, and perhaps more people along the way. It set me on a new path and I am continuing to walk that path.

Thank you so much Ron. My gratitude to you and to Connie flows beyond words.

Experiencer #17

Dear Heavenly Parents,

How can [my wife] and I become true friends, reach the point where we truly enjoy our time together; feel really/truly like the eternal soul mates we really are; as you intend us to be?

And how can [my children] find You, how can they find true healing and happiness, and how can [my child] find his true love? How?

Heavenly Parent's answer:

You are always trying to figure Me out; to get answers that you don't really need, or already have right in front of you. Just live, love...BE, and you'll be able to see it all more clearly. Don't worry about knowing about the answers, because you don't need them (in order) to be whole, to be full, to be free, to be at peace. You are already there but don't know it because you're trying too hard, looking too hard. Exhale...relax...let yourself drift freely on the breeze, and you'll see that where it takes you is your intended destination.

We all long for happiness; no news or surprise there. But it tends to escape us when we expect it to look like this or that. It will often (even always) look / BE very different than what you expected. So, don't expect - don't anticipate with a concept or vision of what it is or will be. Let that all...all fall away by the wayside.

The journey is part of the destination. Where you both/all are is where you're supposed, or need to be now/at this time. It's not for you or anyone in your family to DO, to CHANGE, to FIX anyone, or anything. Life needs to run its course...like the river to the sea. It has a way, a path, a mind of its own, and it is as unstoppable as MY LOVE...a force of nature that is untamable.

So...Be still, be open, be U. Be what you were born to be. The rest will take care of itself...and fall in place as needed. So often, you my children try to figure it all out, but truth be told, even I/We don't often know where the river of life will flow. All depends on the terrain, the boulders, soil, trees and elevation. Gravity does its thing, and I/WE just stand back

and watch in awe. Nice, no?

I'm for U and your family and tribe. That's all you need to know, to concern yourself with. The rest will take care of itself. Now, isn't that refreshing, liberating, a treat?

So, relax...don't try so hard, don't read into ME. That's not your job – or who I am: not why I'm here. Doesn't have to be so hard. U guys let yourselves get in the way of the river. That's why you get wet – soaked to the bone with icy cold water! Stand back, sit on the bank, feel the wind of the waves on your feet. Watch the river run, gawk in awe, and just sit there in stillness, and it will all be OK... Simple as that.

I'm no mystery; as simple as pie – with vanilla ice cream. Warm me up and enjoy! Slow your hand now, slow your heart now (Ron...my heart wants to explode with tears of joy and relief, even now as I'm typing this...) slow your mind now. It's all going to sort itself out as it all flows to the sea.

I am comfort, I am hope, I am calm.... I am the river.

(Me...Thank you Heavenly Parents).

Experiencer #18

Twenty-one years before the workshop I had a showdown prayer in my kitchen telling God: "I just want to know what you think of me. I don't care how bad it is. I can take it. I just want the truth but it has to come from you."

At the workshop: Ron did not know me nor I him. However, somehow he began speaking words from God to me. The main part of the message was, "Never forget how much I love you." That came as a shock to me. I felt it was a direct answer from God to my prayer in the kitchen 2 years prior. The effect was huge because prior to that I thought God did not want to hear from me. I considered a raging river between myself and God with no way to cross over. I only prayed out of desperation from time to time hoping He might be listening. But through my experience it was as though God crossed the river. Not me. He wanted a relationship with me. I was filled with happiness. The next morning I laid out all my shortcomings in prayer. Everything I could think of throughout my life. I felt God was with me.

The main effect on my life is that I now know that God wants me to pray to him. There is nothing which I cannot tell Him.

Experiencer #19

Ron's coverage of spiritualism in US history was valuable. I was not aware of most of that history, even though I studied American church history. It was left out of the main resource texts and professors' knowledge back in the 1980s. It is an important factor in the inception of the LDS, Seventh-Day Adventism, Spiritual churches in general, and Christian Science and Jehovah's Witnesses later in the 19th century, as well as Pentecostalism in the early 20th century.

Ron bridged the gap between objective social history and consideration of the spirit world. Ron was able to humanize access to the spirit world. It helps us feel that it is normal to relate with the spirit world as it is with the physical world, that the spirit world is always present, and that spiritual disciplines enable the spirit world to work with us. I remember to this day one young woman in the workshop telling me that she met my parents in the spirit world and that they are enjoying "sweet love." It was edifying.

The workshop helped me take a more objective perspective on my spiritual experiences, more disciplined. It was a very rich, peaceful and happy learning experience. Ron creates a good atmosphere for learning and personal growth in terms of developing one's relationship with the spirit world.

Experiencer #20

In 2015, I attended Ron Pappalardo's workshop in Jacksonville, Florida titled: *THE SPIRIT WORLD: HOW SPIRITS LIVE AND INTERACT WITH US: A GUIDE TO SPIRITUAL DEVELOPMENT*. I had an uplifting experience with God at the workshop, but I didn't recall the specific details. So, over the course of several days I watched all 5 DVDs again, and I took notes on the highlights. As a result, not only was my heart moved at the profound content of what Ron taught at the workshop, but I also had a mystical experience with God in the process! On the first day of the workshop, Ron gave us the opportunity to pray for one another and a woman named xxxx was chosen to pray for me. She prayed and received 2 messages for me: "You are loved, you are enough" and "Live in joy, you are safe." Afterwards, Ron discussed the content of her messages with me, and then he went on to ask: "Would I be correct in sensing that sometimes you have this kind of negative narrative going on in your head that 'You are not good enough,' 'I should be doing this,' 'I should be doing more?'" After I answered affirmatively, Ron went on to say: "This is so profound because it is like if God had the opportunity to visit you, to come to your house, he would want to say: 'xxxx, you are enough, just the way you are, you're OK. You don't have to do anything to earn my love. I already love you.'" Ron was so filled with God's heart that he had to hold back his tears. I felt that xxxx and Ron were both conduits for God to reach me with messages of love and encouragement. On the last day of the seminar, xxxx happened to pick my name randomly and shared a prophetic message she received about me that I should experience JOY through trials I was going through! This message was also a great encouragement to me.

Two years later in 2017, I had a spiritual reading with a professional medium, and part of the message I received contained nearly the same content I had received at Ron Pappalardo's workshop! 7 years later, in 2022, another medium also gave me a similar message! 9 years later, just last weekend, as I watched the recording of Ron Pappalardo's workshop, I had a mystical experience with God, as I realized that my Heavenly Parent has been trying to reach me with the same message of love through Ron's workshop, other mediums, and in numerous other ways! I didn't feel any judgment for not realizing this earlier, but like the prodigal son, I only felt the embrace of love from God, my Heavenly Parent! As a result of this encounter, I now keep in mind a wise saying I have heard from various spiritual teachers now has new meaning for me: "remember to remember!" In my survey of Ron's workshop I did not emphasize that it was life transforming, but now I realize that transformation can occur years later and lead to an encounter with God!

(Optional) Feel free to also add any additional comments you would like to make about your Mystical experience, your experience at the workshop, or Ron Pappalardo's ministry. Your answer can be as long or as short as you like:

Ron Pappalardo's workshops are AMAZING! He covers so many topics from discerning Biblical truth to how we can have a direct experience with God! His explanation about the origins and role of Spiritualism in United States history is fascinating and makes you examine your life of faith. The key to the impact of Ron's workshops is due to his heart, which God has been using as a conduit to share divine love. His wife Connie also provides the heartistic, logistical, financial, emotional, and spiritual support, that enables Ron to be used in this way to encourage everyone from any faith tradition to experience the love of God in a very personal way. Similarly, Ron's GEMs (God Experiencing Mystics) Zoom calls are very uplifting and are a wonderful tool where participants can share testimonies and receive further guidance from Ron about encountering God. Finally, his books are inspirational with the same message about meeting with God through meditation, prayer, journaling, etc. Ron's focus on eternal truths and connecting with the heart of God is why I support his important work.

Experiencer #21

Dear Ron,

I filled out the survey and hopefully submitted it properly. The survey questions are extremely relevant to my experience. In journaling with God I discovered clearly that God knows me and loves me unconditionally. These days I try to understand God's point of view even more than I used to. God is loving, wanting to guide and support, not wanting to judge and punish. It is challenging to look at others from God's point of view with this knowledge in mind, but it is the only true way to perceive others, even those we see as having strayed far from principled behavior.

Happy Independence Day and a Belated Happy 42nd anniversary to you and Connie,

XXXXX

Experiencer #22

Ron's workshop answered my questions about why our church has a painfully hard time to grow. Being a member for about 40 years I experienced the desperation in witnessing, (in 5 different countries in 3 continents) wanting so desperate to bring new people to our movement. The push was to bring new people, but so little or nothing was done to help members grow and to prepare for having a family. Soldiers forever, being frustrated human doers rather than fulfilled human beings.

Through the DP we received a great moral skeleton to hold us up, we found the Messiah, a spouse to love and to grow with, as our second Messiah, and our children as our Third Messiah. I am truly grateful

However to really be successful we needed to actually FULFILL the three Blessings, not just know how to draw all the circles and arrows to encourage others to join, and make the money for the needs of the church. We as members tried very hard to juggle all this with our best attitude, investing and often feeling we fell so short of what was expected of us, and often being reminded by leadership that we failed to reach our goals. Frustration, guilt and heaviness was a common feeling for me and many others, some ended up with resentment. That is a very sad situation indeed.

So, Ron's workshop that I went to back in 2014 was called First Blessing and it talked about how to develop out spiritual muscles and actually develop a relationship with God. In a clear and joyful way. Wow.

I was a member that spent my membership years reading spiritual books and attending other spiritual groups to be able to survive in the UC. Here was someone who actually had something valid to say to actually feel God in our lives, in the UC. Amazing.

Ron is a brave loyal son of God and of TP that has a big important job in reviving our wounded and sometimes dead precious members-soldiers. I wish our movement can start implementing the internal work of actually building our relationship to God, finding ourselves through that and actually living and breathing with God.

It does not come automatically through sacrifice and working hard while feeling one is never doing enough. Healed happy people carry a frequency, an energy that is very noticeable. Happiness can bring comfort and is an example of God's love in action. So many, many, almost all older members are dried out and spiritually struggling. I often feel God himself is checking out of the movement too. In 70 years of church history we find ourselves in the same dilemma as the 2000-year-old Christianity. Very very sad indeed. So the answer is to show the way to the water of life, -that no dogma, leader or hard work can bring. Go inside and find God and find ourselves. Feed God's sheep.

Ron has an important message. I hope there are ears to hear how much needed message to reform our movement and bring joy and healthy spirituality back in our hearts.

God Bless us all.

Experiencer #23

When I started journaling and just wrote and wrote a very strong sentence entered my mind. I felt the response coming straight from God. S/he said, you talk too much, loud and clear. It just made me laugh because it is so true and it would never have been something I said to myself. It was funny and straight to the point and absolutely right. I felt God knows me really well and sometimes is amused by me. This was definitely unexpected.

My experience of grasping for a message from God for another person in the room during a meditation session at the end of the WS was so profound. You told us halfway through not to will it, to strain for it, to force anything which was exactly what I was doing. Your guidance relaxed me and I just stretched my intuition instead of my mind. And the message came literally floating to me on the breeze that was wafting into the Morning Garden chapel, almost like a physical thing. It was Jesus who said, "my peace I give unto thee." It filled me with peace and I conveyed this message to the person for whom it was originally intended. It was a friend who had lost her son to suicide not too long previously.

My last experience was during the meditation where you guided us through a forest and meadow up a hill to a house. We were supposed to meet a person with whom we had issues or conflicts. Thinking back now I realized that it changed my relationship with this person, my older sister who had passed away in 2008. Ever since then I have been talking to her often, apologizing for my limitations, my fear of her judgment that had left me unable to reach out to her with love.

Experiencer #24

Ron's workshop and ministry is from the heart, which is what inspires me. For me, this is the premise to open communication with Spirit and each other. I am not much on dogma or belief structures, and would rather explore the world of unlimited possibilities, where we could be the best that we can be/or not! Forgiveness and nonjudgement are the key! Ron practices this, and it is manifested in his gatherings.

Thank you, Ron & Connie!

Experiencer #25

I want to begin by expressing my gratitude for all the work, classes etc. Ron has done to put him in a position to be leading the programs he leads. I have enjoyed them immensely. This workshop was not the first where we worked on journaling. Loosely it is a technique where you settle into a relaxed mood, with a paper and pen and write everything that comes to mind. You try not to filter but let the spirit come through you. Consistently when I do in the setting Ron creates, I feel God's love for me. It is a tangible feeling. Often as real as water on my skin. That is very important to me because I was raised an atheist. There is no logic that could get me to believe in God, only the skin touch experience.

On one occasion, doing forced deep, repetitive breathing exercise I felt God come and talk to me about my birth. I complained to Him I wasn't even wanted. I was conceived illegitimately, i.e., before my parents were married. They never brought it up, in fact I didn't know until I was 17 and saw the date on their wedding picture. But I know it was a shock to my mother and she feared my father would leave her. God told me the reason they had conceived me was because He wanted me. That He loved me an extreme amount and had planned for me for years and worked to bring my parents together. They were from completely different parts of the world. He really continued about how much He wanted me, exactly me. I felt so joyful. Unfortunately, I did not nurture this experience and I still lack confidence. My first thought when my husband xxxxxxx died, ...was I will never be with him in the spirit world. He is so much deeper and better than I am. Heavenly Parent will put him with someone else. (My husband) has told me through other people that is not true. My belief system tells me that is not true and we loved each other very much before he died. In fact a month before he said to me strongly, "(My name), I love you so much."

It was almost uncomfortable because it was so unlike him to be so forceful about love. Still I was struggling. Then while journaling at Ron's workshop I again felt God telling me how much He loved me. Reminding me of spiritual experiences I have had over my life, showing me how he wants me to live and have faith. He reminded me of the groups he has led me to where we meditate and I experience Him, or praying on a beach and chasing the waves and Him coming and telling me the waves were Him playing with me. Being shown all the specific ways God works in my life, helped me to feel safe and that somehow things will be ok without (my husband) for a while.

One thing that hurt my relationship with God was the Divine Principle concept of God having 95% and us 5%. Before that I thought God was always loving me and around me. He had found me and called me when I was a pretty "bad" person. So I thought all was fine. But after that 95-5 thing I felt unworthy and thought I never prayed enough or cried enough, and so God must not be near. It is unfortunate. So after many years at a workshop of Ron I had another experience with God. It was Him just fluttering around me, clucking about how happy He was that I, and each of us, existed. That we are now eternal, and would be with Him in joy eventually, no matter what. And He is extremely joyful about that.